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The Effect of Hands on Modeling Activities on the Achievement, Attitude, and Self Efficacy of Different Learning Style, Opposite Gender and Different Kind of School Biology Students

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By

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Visual, Auditory, Read Write and Kinesthetic	(VARK)
Non Kinesthetic	(NK)
Self Efficacy	(S.E.)
Multiple Choice Questionnaire	(MCQ)
Perceptual Learning Style Preference Questionnaire	(PLSPQ)
Biology Attitude Questionnaire	(BAQ)
What Is Happening In this Class?	(WIHIC)
Questionnaire on Teacher Interaction	(QTI)
The Test of Science Related Attitude	(TOSRA)
Students' Motivation Toward Science Learning	(SMTSL)
Students Metacognition, Learning processes and Self Efficacy questionnaire	(SMELIS)
Constructivist Connectivity	(CC)
Monitoring, Evaluation & Planning	(MEP)
Science Learning Self-efficacy	(SE)
Learning Risks Awareness	(AW)
Control of Concentration	(CO)
Coefficient of Variation	(CV)
Acquired Knowledge Domain	(A)
Reasoning Domain	(B)
Communication Domain	(D)

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The effect of Hands On Modeling Activities on the Achievement, Attitude and Self Efficacy of Different Learning Style, Opposite Gender, and Different Kind of School Biology Students

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to investigate 11th graders with different learning styles self efficacy, attitude, and achievement outcomes after implementing two months in modeling based activities teaching. Seventy two students in grade eleven were involved in the experimental group and experienced modeling instruction while other seventy nine students were involved in traditional group and taught by traditional lecturing.

Four instruments were used for data collection: The first instrument was a pretest that was given to control and experimental students in the beginning of the study. Those students had also to continue a post test at the end of the study to determine if there was any progress in their achievement. The pretests and post tests cover similarly the three domains Acquired knowledge, Reasoning and Communication.

Students' attitude and self efficacy toward biology multiple choice questionnaire were implemented in both groups in the beginning and at the end of the study. This attitude scale covered 4 subscales: attitude toward the teacher, attitude toward the learning environment, enjoyment and leisure.

Students also filled out VAK learning preference questionnaire in the beginning of the study to identify their learning style as kinesthetic (K) and non kinesthetic (NK) learners. At the end of the study, students in the experimental group had to continue an open ended questionnaire that covered same scales measured in the multiple choice questionnaire.

The data of the present study was analyzed by analysis of means and % of variations. T test, paired T test and Anova were conducted. Results of the study showed that the modeling approach improved students achievement in biology more than the traditional lecture. Students in the modeling group developed higher acquired knowledge and more increase in test marks was for K learners. Moreover, as to their gender and kind of school, all groups showed significant increase in their marks, female experimental students showed a greater increase, and the highest increase in achievement was for mixed schools. On the other hand, the modeling approach lead to higher attitude and self efficacy but the results were not significant. Modeling increased students attitude toward teacher and lead to more leisure and enjoyment. This increase in attitude was mainly for K more than NK but the results were not significant. In addition to that, Female students increase their attitude more than experimental mixed section and the boys alone sections .

On the basis of these findings , it's advisable to engage students in activities such as modeling to improve their achievement, attitude and self efficacy in biology.

Key words: modeling, learning style, attitude, self efficacy, achievement, gender.

CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

1.1- General Background:

Teaching – Learning science process is considered appropriate only if it addresses all the objectives of science education which are spread over knowledge domain, affective domain and psychomotor domain. The teaching of biology like other science subjects should focus on the development of scientific concepts, attitudes and skills. Indeed, the promotion of favorable attitudes towards science and the improvement of science achievement of students are among the main objectives of science education in many countries [Fraser ; Lyons ; OECD (as cited in Brok et al. ,2010)] and Lebanon is no exception in this respect. Nicolaidou and Philippou (2003) emphasized that human beings are not only cognitive individuals, but also social persons with beliefs, emotions and views that influence their development as learners. So teachers need to pay as much of attention to their students' affect world as to actual performance.

Recent studies reported that low achievement, negative attitude and low self efficacy are basic problems of biology education.(French and Russell ,2001; Gilbert ,2004; Tuan et al., 2005)

The number of students going to science majors is declining . This leads to ring the bells of worry and concern. Students' motivation toward science has been decreased after they enrolled in school (Tuan & Chin, 2000).

In addition to that, students show low interest and achievement in science and hence to a disinclination to continue the study of science beyond what is mandatory(Gilbert ,2004). The importance of attitude investigation becomes more relevant especially when studies reveal alarmingly low interest towards science [Ramsden (as cited in Usak et al.,2009)]. In the light of these results, researchers noted that these traditional methods in teaching courses were characterized by substantial declines in attitude (French and Russell , 2001) and emphasized that a change to a more student-centered pedagogy clearly affects students' attitudes toward biology. These efforts to create new strategies should also take gender issues into consideration. The low enrollment of females in sciences calls for double effort along that direction, it was also found that high school

girls scored lower than boys on their self efficacy in biology (DeBacker & Nelson, 2000). Seymour and Hewitt (as cited in French and Russell , 2001) reported that female students are more likely to abandon the sciences as a major than their male counterparts and suggested student centered pedagogies to balance this gender gap.

Thus, studies on teaching methods that enhances the motivation of students has become a very important area to science educators (Tuan et al.,2005) .Usak et al. (2009) emphasized that the curriculum developers, teachers and the students should set an important goal to develop positive attitude toward biology .

Many science educators criticized traditional methods of teaching and judged it as inadequate . This is because it was characterized by emphasis on acquisition of body of knowledge and science teaching in schools over the previous years has so much been armed with chalk , overheads and static images .Using these in lecture did not seem to be effective in conveying the dynamic aspects of biological processes (O’Dowd and Roca,2009; Pacurar and Tirla, 2009).

Di Carlo (2008) focused on how we teach considering that How we teach is much more important than what we teach because the traditional “lecture then test” format discourage a deep understanding of the subject as well as the development of lifelong skills such as critical thinking, problem solving, communication, and interpersonal skills. Di carlo (2006) considered that reading the recipe is not as useful as preparing the meal when learning how to cook recommending to change our approach from reading to “doing”. Students learn when they are actively involved in learning.

In spite of researchers awareness and criticism to these methods, still in many schools, the classes are teacher centered rather than dynamic student-centered, and research has shown that traditional lecture method, where the teacher speaks and students listen, still dominate the scene (Thaman et al., 2013).

As this method was found inadequate , the National Science Education Standards (as cited in French and Russell, 2001) emphasized the importance of shifting toward student-centered pedagogy. Recommended teaching strategies are based on aspects of constructivist theory (individuals construct meaning through hands-on and minds-on experience and socio-cultural models of learning, individuals learn through interaction with others, both as peers and apprentices). Students are engaged in this learning process . This creates their interest and open up their minds to lifelong learning . Moreover, these active learning strategies reach to all type of learners whether they

have a preference for visual learning, auditory learning, reading and writing or kinesthetic learning (Thaman et al., 2013).

In addition to the importance of the method of instruction, during recent years there was a conscious awareness of the increasingly important role of the learner in the learning process. Understanding the variety of learning styles that students bring to a science classroom will not only help some students learn more science, but also help more students learn any science (Tanner and Allen ,2004). To reach diverse audiences of learners, science teachers must differentiate and diversify their own teaching styles . (Tanner and Allen ,2004;Wehrwein et al.,2007; Dobson, 2009). Changing the way teachers teach and what they teach in science should be a continuing professional concern (Prokop et al., 2007). Teachers should have the knowledge of how students learn science and and how best to teach. Dobson (2009) noted that when information is presented using students' preferred learning style, teachers can tailor the course information to the styles that are most effective for their students and are better able to connect with them. Plato cited in (Tanner and Allen ,2004) advised teachers not to train youths to learning by force and harshness, but direct them to it by what amuses their minds so that they may be better able to discover with accuracy the peculiar bent of the genius of each. Moreover, the learning style theories encourage a belief that everyone can learn if their preferences are addressed (Wehrwein et al.,2007).

Teaching hard topics in biology as in any other subject requires that teachers update their methods and deepen their knowledge in their students learning styles. Talking about hard topics in biology, Genetics with no doubt comes among the first. The understanding of genetic concepts has been found to frustrate students (Lewis & Wood-Robinson, 2000; Law &Lee, 2004). The abstract nature of genetics make the concepts hard to understand by learners. There is therefore, the need to intensify efforts in creating new strategies of presenting these genetics concepts in a classroom situation so that learners can have a better grasp of their nature. Hence, there is an urgent need to change the traditional method of teaching to an active learning that can help students develop a deeper understanding of modern genetics.

To overcome the genetics difficulties mentioned above, one of the teaching techniques recommended by teachers and researchers is modeling. Kindfield (1992) wrote: "...My first and foremost recommendation to teachers (including myself) is to treat learning as model building and view students as model builders'' (p. 40), through active engagement. These hands on modeling activities coincides with recommendations

made over the last decade stressing that learning science is an active process— something students do, not something that is done to them [NRC (as cited in Rotbain et al., 2006)]. In addition to that , group activities such as modeling can decrease the amount of stress and negative attitude that may be associated with learning genetics concepts. This technique includes multiple modes of learning: Seeing, reading, hearing and physical participation. This combination ultimately enhances learning (Chinnici et al., 2004). The researchers concluded that the teaching-style practiced that included more active participation such as modeling was the determining factor affecting student attitude ,achievement. and self efficacy of different learning style students (Di Carlo ,2008; Harris et al.,2009; Thaman et al. ,2013; Breckler and Yu , 2011).

1.2- Statement of the problem:

The teaching procedures in classes tend to be poor in the method of conducting the lesson. The techniques used in classroom don't make the learning process sufficiently easy for students[Gabel (as cited in Attieh,2003)]. Poor funding, time constraint, and lack of creativity among teachers to improvise materials in their classes are identified as major constraints to effective utilization of models (Ezeasor et al.,2012), and Lebanon is not an exception. Many Lebanese schools face the crises of lack of adequate equipments/teaching materials for effective hands-on and minds-on activities. Moreover, Lebanese teachers rarely vary their methods of teaching to motivate and increase the interest of their students in biology . This is mainly because they are under a lot of pressure. The content they need to cover is still dense. They are restricted by the time element and require more than the periods allocated for the subject. Teachers practical opinions are of little consideration in the Lebanese educational system mainly due to the restrictions that make them focus on mechanical content coverage . Moreover, teachers are disregarding instructional techniques that cater to individual differences (Haddad, 2006).

With respect to Lebanese students, there is an increasing need to gather information regarding the learning styles of Lebanese students. Despite the fact that many researchers have discussed and confirmed the effect of a match between the teaching style of the teacher and the learning style of the students, there has been no study showing empirical data regarding the effect of this match on biology students. In Lebanon , very few studies have addressed differences in students learning style. Hadi

(2007) and Sabeh(2009) studied these differences. Sabeh (2009) findings revealed that a match between teaching and learning styles has a positive impact on students achievement in English.

The Lebanese Center for Educational Research and Development (CERD) developed new curricula with new objectives (CERD,1995). While writing objectives for the new curricula, educators have included some affective objectives in the hope of increasing students self confidence and improving their attitude toward science (See General Objectives, Science Curriculum, Decree10227, May 1997). This new educational system showed a lot of improvement in embedding new ideas like student centered learning and additional emphasis was placed on hands on, minds on activities (Boujaodi, 2002) . However prevailing practices and instruction in Lebanon are not always fulfilling such goals. On the other hand , the possible impact that a change in pedagogy as modeling may have in either the affective or cognitive domains has not been researched. Moreover, many studies showed that these constructivist approaches used in learning narrow the gender gap between males and females in their achievement, attitude and self efficacy [Seymour and Hewitt (as cited in French and Russell ,2001)]. So can modeling affect and narrow this gender gap between males and females as to their achievement, attitude and self efficacy to science?

In the light of the above, the following research questions were formulated:

1.3- Research Questions:

- 1- Research Question # 1: Do modeling activities compared to traditional lecturing produce higher achievement in biology in grade 11 scientific students?
 - Research Sub Question # 1: Are there any statistically significant differences in achievement among grade 11 biology students after implementing modeling related to Learning Style?
 - Research Sub Question # 2: Are there any statistically significant differences in achievement among grade 11 Biology students after implementing modeling related to Gender?
 - Research Sub Question # 3: Are there any statistically significant differences in achievement among grade 11 biology students after implementing modeling related to their kind of school?

- 2- Research Question # 2: Do modeling activities compared to traditional lecturing produce higher attitude and self efficacy in Biology in grade 11 scientific students?
- Research Sub Question # 1: Are there any statistically significant differences in attitude and self efficacy among Biology students after implementing modeling related to their learning style (kinesthetic and non kinesthetic)?
 - Research Sub Question # 2: Are there any statistically significant differences in attitude and self efficacy among grade 11 Biology students after implementing modeling related to gender?
 - Research Sub Question # 3: Are there any statistically significant differences in attitude and self efficacy among grade 11 Biology students after implementing modeling related to kind of school?

1.4- Research Hypothesis :

- 1- Research Hypothesis # 1: There's significant variation among students who received instruction with modeling activities and those who received instruction with traditional method in terms of achievement in favor of those who modeled.
- 2- Research Hypothesis # 2: There is significant difference between the mean scores of K (kinesthetic learners) and NK learners (non kinesthetic learners) in terms of achievement in favor of Kinesthetic learners.
- 3- Research Hypothesis # 3: There's no significant difference between the mean scores of girls and boys in terms of achievement after implementing modeling .
- 4- Research Hypothesis # 4: There's no significant difference between the mean scores of the different kinds of schools students in terms of achievement after implementing modeling.
- 5- Research Hypothesis # 5: There's significant variation among students who received instruction with modeling activities and those who received instruction with traditional method in terms of attitude and self efficacy in favor of those who modeled.
- 6- Research Hypothesis # 6: There is significant difference between the mean scores of K (kinesthetic learners) and NK learners (non kinesthetic learners)

in terms of attitude and self efficacy after implementing these hands on modeling activities in favor of Kinesthetic learners.

- 7- Research Hypothesis # 7: There's no significant difference between the mean scores of girls and boys in terms of attitude and self efficacy after implementing modeling.
- 8- Research Hypothesis # 8: There's no significant difference between the mean scores of different kinds of schools students in terms of attitude and self efficacy after implementing modeling .

1.5- Purpose of the study:

This study was thus undertaken to see how much modeling can improve the understanding of genetic concepts that are difficult to learners. So, a major target of this research is to implement a new instructional method and to examine its efficiency. In this research, the influence of teaching biology is addressed in two methods: traditional method and active method featuring modeling strategy. Therefore the purpose of this study was to indicate if there is any relation between the teaching method and students increase in attitude, achievement , and self efficacy of different learning style students after implementing modeling activities for grade 11 biology students in different kinds of schools(boys, girls, and mixed).

1.6- Significance of the study:

As noted in the problem statement, there is shortage of data regarding new methodologies implemented in Lebanese biology classrooms. In addition to that, this study examines the learning style of Lebanese students, but it differs from other studies regarding learning style since it examines the impact of a match of the learning style and the method of instruction followed. Here comes the importance of our study to give a feedback on the achievement of different learning style students after implementing modeling activities for grade 11 biology students in different kinds of schools(boys, girls, and mixed). This study will also assist in determining attitude change and the extent to which Lebanese students increase their self efficacy after modeling. Moreover traditional education methods have struggled to address the challenges in developing modern genetics literacy (Eklund et al.,2007). So, this study will help biology teachers to treat students difficulties in the complexity, invisibility , and inaccessibility of genetics concepts by using concrete models of everyday materials. It is hoped that the

results of this study will help improve teaching methods and provide Lebanese teachers, educators and curriculum designers knowledge about the learning style of their students and about the effect of implementing this new method on their attitudes , achievement and self efficacy.

1.7- Operational Definition of Terms:

Single sex Schools: are schools accepting students from one sex either boys or girls.

Mixed schools: are schools where students are from both sexes.

Academic achievement : operationally defined as success in a class based on test scores and course grades.

Gender : the sex, male or female, of an individual.

Self-efficacy : the confidence individuals have in their abilities that they can successfully perform particular tasks ,(Bandura, 1997).

Modeling: It is the process of developing models (Gobert & Buckley, 2000; Penner, 2001) .

Learning Style: It includes many definitions but under the VARK classification system it includes four categories : read-write (R) ,visual(V) preference ,auditory (A) and Kinesthetic (K)-style learners (Wehrwein et al.,2007)

Attitude: According to Pharaon (1984) , the author used Koslow's definition of attitude to refers to beliefs and feelings about the subject of science (Pharaon ,1984).

CHAPTER II

LITERATURE REVIEW

In this chapter, literature review is presented in eight sections. The first section discusses the theoretical framework that supports conducting modeling activities. In the second part, studies related to difficulties in genetics, modeling activities and its effect on achievement of students are presented. Of a special interest, in this part, many issues are covered: modeling effect on achievement, modeling effect on the achievement of students with different learning style, and modeling effect on the attitude and self efficacy of opposite gender and different kind of school students.

2.1- Theoretical Frameworks that Support Modeling Activities:

Since the major reform in science education dated back to 1960's, many researchers and educators have addressed modeling in their work such as Vygotsky(1962), Bruner(1966), Piaget (1970) , and Anderson (1983).

2.1.1- Bridging the Gap between Concrete and Abstract Thinking

According to Anderson (1983), there are two kinds of knowledge: Declarative and procedural knowledge, a student takes what the teacher says and makes a declarative encoding of what he/she has heard. If the declarative encoding is transformed into executable knowledge, then such coding becomes procedural knowledge. The use of concrete materials allows the proceduralization to begin. Because concrete materials help students construct procedural knowledge, learning through concrete materials makes new learning easier and more meaningful. In this way, students don't have to memorize declarative knowledge and without having to refer to long-term memory (Anderson, 1986). Teachers should explain the procedure using the concrete materials instead of using abstract ideas. This process helps teachers to see what the students are thinking when they are manipulating their thoughts. In other words, materials provide a visible analogy of the students' working memory. It also allows teachers some access to the student's cognitive processes and gives a chance for the teacher to intervene and

increase learning efficiency. As a result, the students are able to move from concrete representation of a process to a symbolic representation of that process (Hall, 1998).

Scholars such as Heddens (1986) and Sowell (1989) provided various suggestions about bridging the gap between concrete and abstract. Heddens reported that the role of the teacher is to provide activities involving many concrete experiences to help students make this transition. A model can be viewed as an intermediary between the abstractions of theory and the concrete actions of experiment. (Dori and Barak, 2001). The use of physical manipulatives has been advocated providing scaffolding for abstract concepts (Bruner, 1966). This was considered as “concreteness fading” by Herman et al. (2006).

The value of physical models in teaching abstract concepts was stressed by many authors in many subjects. Since students are introduced to many concepts through illustrations found in their books, many students fail to become engaged because they lack the basic understanding to interpret these abstract images. In addition to that, students face difficulty in the mental rotation of images as is documented more often for girls than for boys (Herman et al., 2006). On the other hand, many researchers such as (Wu and Shah, 2004; Roberts *et al.*, 2005; Sorby, 2005) recommended models to reach students with different learning styles.

Tanner and Allen (2004) raised awareness of the diversity among learners and suggested that we still have much to learn about how to reach all students. Sheila Tobias author of *They're Not Dumb, They're Different*, writes that “not every student who doesn't do science can't do science; many simply choose not to.” Sheila Tobias (as cited in Tanner and Allen, 2004). To provide open access to science learning, they suggested that teachers must begin to address the diversity of learning styles among the students in their classrooms. Similarly, Wehrwein et al. (2007) raised a question on how can we teach our students if we do not know how they learn and noted that teachers can reach more students when there is a better match between teacher and learner style. Hawk and Shah (2007) explained that teachers in higher education are uncomfortable experimenting learning styles other than their own preference because it takes them out of their own comfort zone. This may require instructors to stray from their own preferred mode(s) of teaching and learn to use a variety of styles, which will positively affect

learning. Active participation with physical models can reach all types of learners via the visual, auditory, kinesthetic, and tactile schemes of learning (Di Carlo, 2008).

2.1.2- Definition of Models and Modeling:

What are models?

The Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary (Oxford University Press, 2011) provides two definitions of a model that are relevant to this discussion: a copy of something, usually smaller than the original object and embodies features from the original in a way that says, "This is how the original is". In a general sense, a model is a simplified representation of a system that concentrates attention on specific aspects of the system (Ingham & Gilbert, 1991), that is ignoring unimportant details and focusing on the most important ones (Gilbert and Boulter, 1998). A model allows aspects of the system that are complex or abstract to be rendered either visible or more easily understood (Gilbert, 1995; Gobert & Buckley, 2000). "A model is a representation of an object, event, process or system" (Gilbert & Boulter, 1998).

As to their classification, Norman's (1983) identified models into the users' mental models and the researcher's or designer's conceptual models of the system. They defined mental models as personal internal representations of the target system being modeled, while expressed models as external representations of the target generated from one's mental models and expressed through action, speech, written description, and other material depictions. They acknowledged the social construction of knowledge by defining consensus models as expressed models that have been developed, tested, and agreed among scientists or among groups of learners. They also included teaching models as developed and used by teachers and curriculum writers to promote the understanding of a target system, while Blumschein et al. (2009) classified models into glass and black box models. In the traditional modeling, the learners don't get insights in the design of the tools itself, that is why they don't understand the functions, Blumschein called these black box models. Engaging learners in understanding and building is a great challenge and crucial for critical thinking. Such models would be called glass box models. Brunner (as cited in Coll and Lajium, 2011) classified models on the basis of their nature as falling into two broad types: physical models and

conceptual (symbolic) models. In this study, the concern is mainly in the physical models as defined by Gilbert (2004) or teaching models as Norman's (1983) called it.

The literature suggested different materials used by the students to build these physical models: cardboard tubes, Popsicle sticks, modeling clay, Styrofoam balls, springs, wooden dowels, pipe cleaners, balloons, rubber strips, tape, glue, tongue depressors, flexible straws, posterboard strips, string, and door hinges.

What is Modeling?

The process of developing models is called modeling and it is central to a scientist's daily practices (Gobert & Buckley, 2000). Modeling is important in science and the ability to use models is central to the understanding of science (Gilbert and Boulter, 1998). Engaging students in the practices that share features with those of scientists', such as modeling, provides a context for students to construct knowledge and integrate content and inquiry (Gobert & Buckley, 2000). Brodie et al. (as cited in Coll and Lajium, 2011) emphasized that the process of modeling involves a source and a target, the source is something that is known to us from everyday life while the target is what we want to understand and the model helps us bridge between the two. Similarly Gilbert (2004) defined modeling as an analogical mapping between a target and a source.

2.1.3- Modeling and Constructivism:

Applying Piaget's theory to instruction, one must remember that knowledge is a construction of the learner (Piaget, 1970). In traditional science teaching, ideas are presented as a set of truths that can be understood only through an abstract language. However, Piaget noted that understanding should begin with action. This usage of model is compatible with the constructivist view that knowledge must be built within the individual mind as well as collectively in science and society (Vygotsky, 1962). Social constructivism suggests that knowledge creation is a shared experience rather than an individual experience, it focuses on this socio cultural approach where students perform social interactions around modeling, thus participating in a community of practice.

Moreover, Chittleborough and Treagust(2009) recommended learning by doing as a process that leads to meaningful learning. Meaningful learning occurs through the internal construction process not via the direct transmission process and this requires learning by construction rather than by listening. Seel and Blumschein (2009) considered that the key to the success of this application of modeling is not so much in how the message itself is presented, but in the degree to which students can work out for themselves ways to reduce the dissonance between what the environment presents to the user and the knowledge and experience the user brings in when he or she enters the environment.

2.1.4- Modeling in Scientific Inquiry:

Models can play a role in scientific inquiry. Dori and Barak(2001) considered science as an attempt to model nature in order to understand and explain phenomena. Models help making predictions, guide inquiry, justify outcomes and facilitate communication (Gilbert & Boulter, 1998).

Penner et al.(1997) noted that for a successful modeling process, number of tasks should be stressed. First, the purpose of the model should be specified, then a version of the model is built. This model must be evaluated with respect to its purpose and revision should be done on the basis of the previous evaluation. This revision raises additional questions which can be explored by additional cycles of modeling where modification of this model occurs . In addition to that, models have a generative role which is concept generation by mapping of attributes from the known to the unknown. Wong (as cited in Coll and Lajium , 2011) noted that these generative models should be dynamic tools rather than static representations of phenomena.

A virtue of a good model is that it stimulates its creators and viewers to pose questions that take us beyond the original phenomenon through discovery, development, evaluation and exposition. Discovery occurs when the model contributes to the formulation of a hypothesis and then this model is used to develop this hypothesis and then in evaluating arguments for or against this hypothesis. By comparing their models, students construct a consensus. So, models are not just toy systems to describe complicated ideas, however model creation is a fundamental part in the scientific process where students are creating and testing models(Schwarz and white,2005). Schwarz et al.(2009) identified four elements of the modeling practice:

- model construction by the students
- model evaluation when students compare and evaluate different models
- model revision where students revise their models by taking into account any additional evidence .
- model use to illustrate or to explain .

2.2- Difficulties related to learning and teaching molecular genetics

In this part, the genetics concepts that most of the students find it difficult and confusing will be discussed. Many researchers reported that one of the most difficult content areas in science is genetics (Lewis & Wood-Robinson, 2000; Law & Lee, 2004). Previous studies showed that students have misconceptions, confusion and incoherent knowledge in genetic topics which include many abstract concepts hard to understand, to learn and to remember (Bahar et al ,1999; Lewis & Wood-Robinson, 2000

). Most of these studies emphasized on students understanding of the concepts of DNA, RNA, gene, chromosome, protein, and the processes of DNA replication, transcription, and translation. Students difficulties in learning genetics concepts are mainly due to that these micro-level concepts are invisible and inaccessible (Duncan and Reiser,2007). There are other difficulties related to teaching methods and textbooks, students had difficulty to explain the functions of genetic concepts, students memorized the concepts of genetics instead (Topco and Pekmez , 2009) . Bahar et al. (1999) reported that even students in higher education, who passed the university exam successfully, had difficulty in understanding genetics related concepts. Moreover, the current approach to science education did not appear to provide an effective preparation for students - either for future training as scientists or for interactions with science in their personal life (Lewis and Wood-Robinson , 2000).

Many studies researched students difficulties in genetics learning. Kindfield (1992) examined the understanding of replication , transcription and translation in secondary students and noted that, although genetics sub cellular processes (e.g., the processes of transcription and translation) are consistently cited as the most difficult components of biology to learn, it is important to teach them in high school, because they constitute a central organizing feature of biology that has relevance in all biology related disciplines. The author explained that what makes learning about subcellular processes difficult is that we have virtually no direct experience with them (Kindfield, 1992) . In

another study, Bahar et al. (1999) focused on students' understanding of the functions of DNA as genetic material. They found out that students are often not familiar with the definitions of the genetics related terms, they have confusion between mitosis and meiosis topics and they may get confused because many genetics terms look and sound very similar, e.g. "homologue, homologous, homozygous and homozygote". There are many genetics concepts which are hard to learn by students: gene, gamete, allele, mitosis and meiosis, monohybrid and di hybrid crosses and linkage (Law & Lee, 2004). In addition to this, students have confusion between genes, traits, genotype and phenotype (Lewis & Wood-Robinson, 2000; Lewis and Kattman, 2004; Duncan and Reiser, 2007; Eklund et al., 2007). On the other hand, Students have another difficulty in understanding the mechanism of inheritance (Lewis & Wood-Robinson, 2000; Lewis & Kattmann, 2004). Moreover, there are difficulties concerning the structure and function of somatic and germ cells, the macro micro flowing level concept and the mathematical expressions in genetics. In addition to that, difficulties in understanding the effect of environment on genetics were also reported in the literature (Boersma et al, 2005; Topco and Pekmez, 2009)

In their study, Lewis and Robinson (2000) examined the genetics knowledge and understanding of 482 British students, aged 14–16, and showed a poor understanding of the processes by which genetic information is transferred and a lack of basic knowledge about the structures involved (gene, chromosome, cell). Students often fail to connect genes to proteins and phenotypes, and as a consequence fail to recognize the importance of proteins in this process. The results of their study proved that one quarter of their sample showed genes are larger than chromosomes, and there was widespread uncertainty as to how genetic information is transferred from cell to cell within organism. They also focused on another obstacle that was not mentioned before which is the time available to teach this extensive genetics subject is limited. Similarly, the study of Lewis and Kattman (2004) showed that 14-16 aged students had little understanding of the difference between a gene and its expression as a trait, and little awareness of basic processes of genetics. Findings from this study of 10 German students aged 15 to 19 suggested that many students hold an everyday conception of genes as small, trait-bearing particles so this might restrict the ability of students to develop an understanding of the scientific explanation, if

genes are equated with trait then there is no clear distinction between genotype and phenotype (Lewis and Kattman, 2004). This result was supported by Duncan and Reiser (2007) who suggested that reasoning in molecular genetics requires mapping across ontologically distinct levels—an information level containing the genetic information, and a physical level containing proteins, cells, and tissues. Moreover, Boersma et al. (2005) in their review study on genetics education identified five major difficulties in genetics which include: the domain-specific vocabulary and terminology, the mathematical content of mendelian genetics tasks, the cytological processes, the abstract nature of the subject in the biology curriculum and the complex nature of genetics, a macro-micro problem . Similarly, Eklund et al. (2007) designed a high school curriculum unit for 9th/10th graders to support students' understanding of molecular genetics and genomics. The researchers identified the following big ideas that they felt students must understand in order to develop deep understanding of genetics: genes are instructions for assembling proteins, it is the protein that carries out the work of a cell, and an organism's traits reflect the actions (and inactions) of its proteins. The learning goals identified necessitated that they integrate content about proteins and genes in the same unit. In addition to that, the study conducted by Topcu and Pekmez (2009) recommended that curriculum should follow the process in which the learning ought to be from macro-level concepts such as cell, cell division to micro-level concepts such as chromosome and genes. They suggested that at first cell division topic should be taught, and then genetics topic to have a deep understanding and the precedence and timing schedule of genetics in science curriculum should be reconsidered.

Given these difficulties in molecular genetics instruction, researchers who take a constructivist approach recommend enhancing the teaching of molecular genetics through the use of models (Peebles & Leonard, 1987; Templin & Fetters, 2002). Teachers should use vehicles to provide more visibility and accessibility for the genetics concepts by using simulations, animations, tutorials and games (Topcu and Pekmez, 2009) or through integrating models in science education in general (Gilbert & Boulter, 1998; Justi & Gilbert, 2002a, 2002b; Van Driel & Verloop, 2002).

2.3- Using Models in Science Education:

In this section, studies on the use of models are reviewed. In addition to that studies on inquiry based modeling activities and modeling activities in genetics are also covered.

Many educators being aware of the traditional method followed in many schools, wanted to compensate the weakness of this method through the integration of active strategies. Some engaged their students in demonstrations, still others used lab activities, only few teachers are using the modeling activities in their classrooms especially in the secondary level.

Many researchers studied the effect of using models on students achievement , attitude and self efficacy. In addition to that, In some studies, the authors show awareness of students different learning styles and used modeling either alone or in combination with other methods to increase learning gains in different kinds of learners. While some researchers find it a successful tool for beginning learners only , others consider it as a successful tool for learners at all levels(junior, high school, and university students).

The concrete models have received the attention of researchers in different domains mainly in math, chemistry and biology. Heddens (1986) stated that concrete model experiences allow students to internalize mathematical concepts otherwise they will see math as rules to be memorized rather than as a unique and helpful way to look at the world.

There were mixed opinions regarding the effectiveness of models in classrooms for children at different ages. Fennema (1972) claimed that only beginning learners benefit from the use of concrete materials while Suydam and Higgins(1977) reported benefit for all learners. Similarly Dori and Barak(2001) , Jittivadhna et al. (2010) reported that concrete models play an important role in capturing the interest of students at both high school and undergraduate levels. Fenemma (1972) claimed that experiences with models should suit children's level of cognitive development considering that as children progress through middle school , the concrete models should be replaced with the symbolic ones. But, most of the middle school students have not yet moved from the concrete and semi concrete levels and manipulatives are not at all childish. In another study, Sowell (1989) conducted a meta analysis of 60 studies which ranged from kindergarten children to university students using manipulatives and concluded that the

duration of treatment and teachers training on using of models are the main factors that influence student achievement when using models. Similarly Harris et al. (2009) recommended multiple exposures to tools. Their data indicated that students benefit from using complex tools such as the hand-held models many times and over several weeks confirming the results of previous studies. In contrary to the previous studies that showed an increase in achievement after implementing models, Resnick and Omanson (as cited in Goldstone and Son,2005) found that mathematical knowledge by using models didn't generalize well to solving symbolic problems.

In biology and chemistry classes, different types of models have been used to improve students achievement and develop students positive attitude and self efficacy toward chemistry and biology. In addition to that , other studies emphasized on models usefulness either alone or in combination with other tools(Dori and Barak ,2001; Roberts et al., 2005;Herman et al., 2006; Harris et al. ,2009 ;Jittivadhna et al., 2009; Jittivadhna et al., 2010).

2.3.1- Superiority of models over any other tool:

On the other hand, Many researchers studied the superiority of models on text book illustrations(Roberts et al., 2005; Rotbain et al.,2006, Jittivadhna, 2009, O'Dowd and Roca ,2009). Roberts et al (2005) emphasized that learning with models is much easier than looking at 2D pictures, they noted that "models are valuable tools in learning not only structure but structural significance of protein". Also, Rotbain et al(2006) studied the advantage of a bead 3 D model over 2 D illustration activities in understanding processes and concepts in genetics. They explained their findings to the nature of the bead model which enabled a high level of manipulation by the students. Using models had been shown to be successful in classrooms (Wu andShah, 2004; Roberts *et al.*, 2005; Sorby, 2005). Wu and Shah (2004) cited several chemistry learning studies which found that students who manipulated physical molecular models had a more complete understanding of the abstract concepts underlying atomic and molecular symbols and two-dimensional imagery and did a better job of solving chemistry problems than their peers who did not use models and it helps students develop the “deeper understanding” . Similarly, Roberts et al. (2005) evaluated the usefulness of physical model as a tool, But in contrary to above results, their students did not feel that use of the physical

models during large lectures was helpful because the students didn't have the opportunity to manipulate the models themselves.

Similarly, Herman et al. (2006) explored the usefulness of physical models in communicating concepts of protein structure and function that have been difficult to teach. They found that physical models of proteins are effective thinking tools that capture the interest of students and motivate them to learn more about this invisible, molecular world and prompt them to ask questions. They emphasized on the importance of having modeling projects such as those models built by Smart Teams. Within these teams students learn that science is not simply the information found between the covers of the text books instead it is discovered in research laboratories. This bridges the gap between high school science classroom and the real world of science. Similarly, a 3-year field test of the use of physical models in a large freshman chemistry course at the University of Wisconsin-Madison showed that models captured students' interest in the subject of biomolecular structure and bridged the gap between the traditional disciplines of chemistry and biology.

Moreover, Jittivadhna et al. (2009) found limitations in using text book illustrations of sarcomere structure recommending the use of a hand held model of sarcomere made of strips of clear plastic sheetings. This model proved to enhance understanding and to dispel students alternative conceptions. Their sample of 343 public, private high school and undergraduate students showed a dramatic improvement in their post tests compared to their pretests. The majority of these students responded positively to the model remarking that they preferred it to text book illustrations.

To overcome the inherent limitations of the textbook pictures, rapid prototyping technology has been used by Harris et al. (2009) to produce hand-held, three-dimensional models. Harris et al (2009) considered that it might be the level of structural details displayed by the molecular models that confused the students in the experimental group. Their data also indicated that the repeated use of the hand-held models had no effect on students' ability to do typical assignments. Contrary to their predictions, the students in the control and experimental groups performed equivalently for 14 of the 16 performance variables. The researchers explained these results by noting that it might be that the lab assignments were not sufficiently comprehensive to accurately assess the sophistication of students' understanding and it might be also that

these biology students were too homogeneous in terms of their potential to understand so the intervention didn't affect that much. Moreover, Jittivadhna et al. (2010) reported that a hand-held skeletal model is superior to a computer-rendered one, even when the latter is rotatable.

In their studies, O'Dowd and Roca (2009) and Breckler et al. (2013) reported that using these models improves the lecture atmosphere, it increases interaction and provides a three-dimensional learning experiences approach that stimulates questioning and builds scientific skills that enhances students constructivist elements of active learning.

2.3.2- Inquiry Based Modeling Activities:

In other studies, researchers proposed inquiry activities based on the generation or construction of knowledge by students using a Model-Based Inquiry Instruction (MBII) (Lee, 2004; Schwarz and Gwekwerere, 2007; Haugwitz and Sandmann, 2010).

Lee (2004) used the pig heart model to demonstrate blood flow from coronary arteries to veins, as promoting biological knowledge generation using Model-Based Inquiry Instruction as well as the blockage of the coronary arteries in coronary artery diseases, in one class of senior secondary students in Hong Kong. The results showed that the model reinforced students' understanding of the circulatory system and its diseases.

In another study, Schwarz and Gwekwerere (2007) stated that models are essential tools for productive scientific reasoning among learners. Schwarz et al. (2009) argued that constructing models is least emphasized in schools recommending that students must realize that models are not just end-products of inquiry, but as explanatory tools aiding in knowledge generation, students must also reflect on both the effectiveness and accuracy of the model (Schwarz and Gwekwerere, 2007). Moreover, Haugwitz and Sandmann (2010) conducted a study aimed at determining how the models of the heart, pulse and veins would enhance students' understanding of function of heart and blood vessels among 40 seventh grade German students. These students were asked to verify hypothesis, plan, construct models, manipulate models and determine what model materials represented in their own bodies. The results showed three findings: most students found learning with models very interesting; students gained better biological

knowledge understanding of function of human heart & vascular system; and students achieved higher test scores after using the models (pre-test average score was 51% whereas post-test score was 64%). Similarly, Chabalengula & Mumba (2012) examined the impact of a Model-Based Inquiry Instruction (MBII) using a human leg model on 20 preservice elementary teachers knowledge generation and understanding of how a human leg functions. The sample was enrolled in an Advanced Science Methods course at a university in the mid west of the USA. Those teachers gained better conceptual understanding of how a human leg functions and achieved higher test scores (pre model test average score was 60.3% whereas post model test average score was 83.6%).

2.3.3- The use of physical models in genetics teaching and learning

In the light of these results, there was continued attempt and interest of teachers in finding new and effective ways of conveying the genetics difficult concepts to students and instructors at all academic levels struggling to find new ways to effectively present this difficult material.

Learning researchers recommended enhancing the learning of genetics through the use of three-dimensional physical models [Gow & Nicholl, 1988; Mensch and Ruba, 1991 ; Kindfield,1999 ; Clark and Mathis,2000 , Templin and Fetters, 2002 ;Chinnici et al., 2004 ; Roberts et al.,2005; Rotbain et al.,2005; Chinnici et al., 2006; Rotbain et al.,2006; Pacurar and Tirla,2009; Jittivadhna et al.,2010).Through a review on the literature there were listed many kinds of models used in genetics teaching.

In their study, Gow & Nicholla(1988) used simple models made up of wood, pins, nails, rubber tubing, pvc colored adhesive tape to illustrate the principles of tetrad analysis. These models enabled a practical approach to be used with students who experienced difficulty in understanding the concepts involved . The authors added that when the student used this practical approach by using models and worked his way through a cross generating the cross over patterns and tetrads in meiosis, the concepts can be made clearer than if a totally theoretical approach is taken.

In another study, Mensch and Ruba (1991) reported that teaching protein synthesis this highly abstract concept to students may of whom not yet reached formal reasoning is made more difficult by the lack of good hands on instructional aids. To understand protein synthesis , they recommended that students must understand the roles played by

DNA, m RNA, TRNA and ribosomes. Their models were constructed from materials like pvc pipe and fittings, polypropylene rope, white paneling, hook and loop fasteners. The rope and pvc fitting were used to represent sugar phosphate sugar side portions of DNA and m RNA while pvc pipe represent nitrogenous bases, their results showed no differences in achievement in acquired knowledge, on the other hand , most students who used the hands-on protein synthesis models gave accurate and detailed written descriptions of transcription and translation processes while essays of the control group students, in contrast, “often did not mention transcription or translation and tended to recall pieces of factual information in isolation from the protein synthesis process” (p. 168). Thus, using hands-on models of protein synthesis tended to increase students’ depth of knowledge of this topic.

In addition to that , Schanker(1999) outlined the advantages of converting abstract ideas in biology to concrete realities as a way for motivating students. To overcome the difficulty of the abstract concepts in meiosis and protein synthesis, the author often tried to convert abstract ideas to concrete realities that students can see and touch by making pop sickle sticks simulations for meiosis. Similarly, Clark and Mathis(2000) recommended using models, they cautioned on the commercially produced scientific models drawbacks and reported that these kinds of models have two crucial drawbacks . First, being expensive to purchase in quantity. Second, they are usually built for a specific purpose and applied to a limited set of science concepts lacking the flexibility to be applicable across a broad range of science content. To overcome these drawbacks, they used materials such as chenille stems, colored yarn, plastic straws, petri dishes, clothesline to show chromosomal structure, chromosome replication, synapsis, genetic segregation, independent assortment of alleles, reductional division, stages of mitosis and meiosis, and chromosomal non disjunction . Their activity also allowed the student to investigate how aberrant occurrences during nuclear division could result in human genetic disorders such as Down syndrome. Clark and Mathis (2000) pointed out that students struggle to distinguish between chromatids, chromosomes and homologous pairs of chromosomes. So , chenille stems of different color and/or length were used to represent chromatids . After feedback from teachers and college students, the researchers reported that more than 98 percent of secondary teachers completing the requested evaluation felt that the materials would be an effective means of teaching the processes of mitosis and meiosis in their classrooms. College genetics students at

Middle Tennessee State University have also responded positively to this modeling/ problem-solving approach. As to the questionnaire results, students found the materials to be especially purposeful , creative , and worthwhile . In the interviews , the responses were that these models make things more clear . This activity, helped both the student and teacher to identify misconceptions about the processes of nuclear division and to develop problem-solving skills rather than to simply memorize the sequence of events (Clark and Mathis,2000).

The effectiveness of instruction about protein synthesis can be greatly improved by using a hands-on model. Construction toys such as Lego building blocks provide a relatively low cost and ubiquitous means of modeling science concepts and processes. Templin and Fetters(2002) presented hands-on model" A Working Model Of Protein Synthesis Using Lego Building Blocks," They considered that their model improved on the previous models in including a ribosome that models the large and small subunits and actually holds the messenger RNA (mRNA), transfer RNA (tRNA), and nascent polypeptide chain. All other models of protein synthesis found in the literature used analogies for the ribosome as a simple line or a drawing to represent the ribosome or did not include a ribosome. Thus, other models reported in the literature give no indication of the importance of the three-dimensional structure of a ribosome to the protein synthesis process. In addition to that, their model preserves the distinction between covalent and hydrogen bonds which is crucial to understand that hydrogen bonding functions in base pairing. Also, Their model allows the polypeptide chain to form by simply and quickly snapping lego blocks together while other protein synthesis models reported in their literature do not result in a durable protein molecule that is free to move (Templin and Fetters, 2002).

Law and Lee (2004) pointed out that understanding of genetics requires understanding of both not observable and abstract conceptual entities and interactions among these entities. Moreover, Chinnici et al.(2004) noted that presenting the topic theoretically often leaves the weaker student with a somewhat confused grasp of the principle involved, students have trouble visualizing what happens inside the cell and modeling makes concepts more understandable and memorable.

In their study, Law and Lee (2004) suggested simulations built using an iconic modeling tool, World Maker (WM) to support the learning of difficult genetics topics.

This study revealed that students' exploration of genetic phenomena stimulates further construction of genetic understanding and it helped students to understand operationally difficult concepts like genotypes and phenotypes. On the other hand, Chinnici et al. (2004) suggested that a technique that includes multiple modes of learning: seeing, reading, hearing and physical participation enhances learning. Their role playing model by using labeled baseball caps and shirt tags to represent genes on chromosomes enhanced learning for non biology students in college settings. It also helped to model crossing over during meiosis and genetic variability among gametes as a consequence of meiosis. Their students feedback was positive and the performance of the 2 groups was statistically significant, the experimental group students averaged 55.1% correct on 10 multiple choice items while the control group averaged 47.9%. In addition to that, Chinnici et al. (2006) study revealed different models for chromosomes. After a review on the literature on different models, most of these were made up from: A simple string and paper to demonstrate the stages of meiosis, crossing over, breakage, and recombination, others from wooden blocks chromosomes, pin-boards, yarn and chenille stems, pieces of ribbon and wooden clothes pegs. Also "pizza chromosomes" that illustrate syngamy, crossing over, gene expression, and ploidy were used. To demonstrate Ploidy in Mitosis & Meiosis, Chinnici et al. (2006) built their "chromosomal socks" model using simple, inexpensive components to represent autosomal chromosomes, their students commented that the chromosomal socks were very helpful in understanding and remembering the distinction between diploidy and haploidy and the relationship between the chromosomes in a diploid cell and a haploid cell.

In their study, Rotbain et al. (2006) studied the effect of modeling and illustrations on students understanding of genetics. Three comparable groups of 11th and 12th graders participated: The control group (116 students) was taught in the traditional lecture format, while the others received instructions which integrated a bead model (71 students), or an illustration model (71 students). The authors found that students who used one of the two types of models improved their knowledge in molecular genetics compared to the control group. However, the open-ended questions revealed that bead model activity was significantly more effective than illustration activity. When interviewed, all the students from the bead and the illustrations groups answered that the activity helped them in gaining a better understanding of the subject matter. But the limitation in their study was that the modeling was accompanied by an activity, so it

was difficult to tell what actually helped the students, the model, the activity or the combination of both. One of the interview questions was: Do you find molecular genetics more difficult than other topics in biology? The students' explanations referred mainly to the multiplicity of new abstract concepts in the molecular biology studies, such as "It is hard to imagine the processes ...those are things that you can't see through a microscope" or "There are many concepts and it became complex, there are many processes going on at once and if you don't disentangle them one by one you can't understand from the beginning ...". After this modeling and illustration intervention, the students found that these activities made the subject easier. 54% of the interviewees in the control group evaluated the course in molecular genetics as very difficult as compared with 30% from the bead group and 24% from the illustrations group. Something else that arose in the personal interviews was the contribution of the activities to the diversification of the lessons. These findings, which revealed differences between groups through open-ended questions, but not multiple-choice questions, correspond with the findings of (Mensch and Rubba, 1991). These authors investigated the effectiveness of a set of hands-on protein synthesis models, which students could manipulate during protein laboratory exercises. They used a multiple-choice questionnaire to compare between the experimental group and a lecture-only control group. Analysis of these questionnaires revealed no differences between experimental and control. The researchers claimed that the multiple-choice questions did not measure the depth of understanding of protein synthesis gained by the students in the experimental group. To test more the achievement difference between the two groups, students were given an optional extra credit essay question dealing with the process of protein. In the experimental group, all students attempted to answer the question, and the majority gave a detailed description of protein synthesis. By comparison, nearly half of the control group members did not answer this question, and those who answered just recalled pieces of information in isolation from the protein synthesis process. Students added that the activities "broke the routine" of the traditional lecture format.

Moreover the results of the study conducted by Butler et al.(2008) suggested to use Genomics DNA Analogy Model for Educators (GAME), they considered GAME a successful way to enable the learning of gene sequencing by visually-impaired and blind students. The GAME approach aimed to enable learning in the area of molecular biology by using everyday concepts and materials, such as a town, Lego blocks, and

factories to represent scientific terminology and relationships. In another study, Pacurar and Tirla(2009) integrated models in teaching some lessons from the units "the cell" and "Heredity" for grade 9 students . They stated that the model-based method has the role to remove overloading lessons and filling students' minds with useless data. The learning progress among their students was seen in the quantity and quality of the information acquired and the usefulness of the knowledge. In the case of the "control" group the grade curve has shifted from grade 5, in the initial test, towards grade 6, in the final test while in the case of the "experimental" group, the average has grown significantly and the grade curve has shifted from grade 5, in the initial test, towards grades 7 and 8 in the final leading to the formation of students who think critically, who can assimilate knowledge and apply this assimilated knowledge.

In his model" A Simple Wooden Ribosome Model: Helping Students Understand Transpeptidation ", Klein(2010) emphasized that in teaching biology, it is critical to communicate broad concepts before considering more specific details of a process, considering transpeptidation as the most important step to understand translation. Criticizing the approach given in microbiology and biochemistry texts that shows movement of the nascent peptide attached to the P position t-RNA to the incoming single amino acid attached to the A position amino acid-tRNA by the use of arrows which makes it difficult to students to understand the process. His simple wooden easy-to-visualize model makes it possible for the students to understand transpeptidation and thus understand translation. Materials used by Klein were wood scraps and finishing nails, rigid foam and round wooden swab sticks, and beverage coasters. To increase students interest , Klein(2010) recommended that the materials could be taken from large black box followed by careful examination of each element. Similarly, Jittivadhna et al. (2010) conducted a study during the year 2006–2009 with 498 student volunteers: 9th–12th graders (aged 14–19) in high schools, freshmen and sophomores, and preclinical medical students (aged 17–20) on how their students learned more from using DNA and protein models assembled from colored computer-printouts on transparency film sheets , this helped their students to grasp various aspects of these biopolymers that they usually find difficult. When they asked their students to draw a sketch of the DNA double helix with as little details, students, including some graduates cannot do it well: no clear helical (right-handed)sense, haphazard hydrogen bondings between basepairs, no major and minor grooves, the strands are not antiparallel, and so

forth. Students do not perform much better with the bare-backbone polypeptide α -helix: no clear helical (right-handed) sense, haphazard hydrogen bondings, each amino acid residue is not quite correct. Taking these difficulties into consideration, students in the experimental group showed more understanding. Some students say: "I understand better now the directionality of the DNA chains after working with the physical model and similar to the results of Rotbain et al.(2006), some students noted "It is much easier than looking at the 2D illustrations and seeing the chains turn to the right as they move sideways, upward or downward" (Page:362). Jittivadhna et al.(2010) added that most students elaborated on the difficulties of understanding the abstract image of structural diagrams found in textbooks and believed that their understanding improved when handling this set of models. The findings from the pre test and post test questionnaire showed that in the pre test only questions 1 and 5 were answered correctly by more than 50% of the students where as in the post test the majority of the students had correct answers for all nine questions in the multiple choice questionnaire, achievement in students answers were also found in the open ended questionnaire in contrast to Mensch and Rubba(1991) where improvement was only revealed in the open ended questionnaire.

In their report "The truth about models: how well do mechanical models mimic the observed gender distributions in two-child families?" Stansfield and Carlton(2011) questioned the use of mechanical models, such as coin flipping, to represent the probabilities of gender distributions in sib ship families consisting of two children. Students understanding of probability greatly increase.

In addition to the role that models play in increasing achievement in genetics, many studies showed an improvement of students with different learning styles.

2.4 - Models and Learning styles:

In this part Learning style will be defined and general studies on Learning styles will be discussed, then more precisely studies on effect of modeling on achievement of students with different Learning style will be covered.

2.4.1- Definition of Learning Style:

Many researchers give different definitions for learning styles, Fleming (as cited in Hawk and Shah, 2007) defined learning style as “an individual’s characteristics and preferred ways of gathering, organizing, and thinking about information. The American Society for Cell Biology defined it as “the complex manner in which, and conditions under which, learners most efficiently and most effectively perceive, process, store, and recall what they are attempting to learn” (Slater et al.,2007; and Wehrwein et al.,2007) .Learning style, thus, is a phenotypic characteristic of an organism like any other(Tanner and Allen ,2004).

The field of learning styles is complex, with over 70 different learning style models identified in their review(Slater et al.,2007). Stensmo (2006) listed different kinds of learning styles by referring to the literature. He noted that Michael Grinder (1991/1999) distinguished between three modes of perception: Visual, Auditory and Kinesthetic (VAK) and Daniel Kolb (1984) differentiated between four modes of information processing: Concrete Experience, Reflective Observation, Abstract Thinking and Active Experimentation while Neil Fleming developed the Visual, Auditory, Read Write and Kinesthetic Questionnaire (VARK). Compared to Grinders learning styles, Fleming identified two categories the Visual (pictures) and the Read/write (written words) Fleming et al. (as cited in Stensmo,2006). Similarly, Hawk and Shah(2007) reviewed same learning styles as above and included five learning style instruments in their study (the Kolb Learning Style Indicator, the Gregorc Style Delineator, the Felder–Silverman Index of Learning Styles, the VARK, and the Dunn and Dunn Productivity Environmental Preference Survey). Wehrwein et al. (2007) followed the VARK classification system that included four categories : read-write (R, a mixed sensory modality that is not assessed under VAK).Students with a V preference learn best by seeing or observing while Learners that prefer A are best suited to learn by listening to or recording lectures. On the other hand, R-type learners learn through interactions with textual materials. K-style learners perform best by using physical experiences: touching, performing an activity, and manipulation of objects. Stensmo(2006) added that Kinesthetic learners do not sit still and concentrate on visual, oral or textual information the way the Visual, Aural and Reading/writing learners can do. They like practical opportunities to test their knowledge. When teaching Kinesthetic learners, the main media should be:field trips application- - real-life examples- hands-on approaches e.g. computing, laboratories and other practical sessions- teach from the known to the

unknown – practical to abstract (Stensmo ,2006). Despite the fact that there are many different learning style models, many of the studies have focused on the sensory modality used by students to learn and have used the VARK questionnaire to assess it .

2.4.2- Characteristics of The VARK Model:

Many studies administered the VARK Learning preference questionnaire to their students. The VARK questionnaire is a 13-item, self-reported, multiple- choice questionnaire that can be completed in 10 –15 min suggesting that longer questionnaires can be boring and taken less seriously by respondents [Fleming (as cited in Slater et al.,2007)].The newest version of the VARK questionnaire consists of 16 questions and can be accessed at <http://www.vark-learn.com/english/page.asp>. According to the VARK questionnaire, the first preference is the sensory modality that obtains the highest score, and depending on the score distribution among the four sensory modalities, there are unimodal and multimodal students (Ramirez, 2011). The VARK self-reported questionnaire has not been statistically validated (Slater et al. ,2007; Breckler et al. ,2008). Breckler et al. (2008) recommended that VARK is not a complete learning style inventory but rather provides users with a simple profile of their basic sensory learning preferences but Slater et al.(2007) added that a strong point of the VARK questionnaire is that its questions and options are drawn from real-life situations while Leite (as cited in Ramirez ,2011) clarified that it was then validated.

2.4.3- Performance in different learning style students:

Fleming presents the results of research that indicate higher student performance in courses when faculty match learning activities with students' learning styles as determined by the VARK instrument(Hawk and Shah, 2007). Many studies have focused on the possible relation between the preferred sensory modality used for learning and student academic performance (Roberts ,2002; Hawk,2007;Dobson, 2009; Frankel,2009;Ramirez, 2011) .These studies related course scores with sensory learning modalities and found either no relation or that K students or A students had the lowest scores.

Roberts (2002) began his research by investigating how to raise attainment focusing on improvement strategies related to learning preferences. Results from questionnaires focusing on two learning preference theories VAK and multiple Intelligence (MI) to

Year 11 students in the 13 schools showed that the accommodation of learning styles in teaching improved students' attainment. The findings from the VAK analysis suggested that boys' attainment in English and Math is affected by their VAK learning preference indicating that learning preference impacts more on the attainment of boys than of girls, results also indicated that visual learners attain and progress better than students who have a tendency towards kinesthetic learning.

In another study, Stensmo (2006) studied Perceptual preferences in learning among 70 teacher education students in practical subjects at Uppsala University. By referring to the VAK questionnaire on learning styles developed by Lena Bostrom and her colleagues, very few students classified themselves as Kinesthetic. Through a review on the literature the authors found that only 4,6 % of the teachers and students in a Swedish university were Kinesthetic learners. The kinesthetic learner is then underrepresented at the university, which is also confirmed in other studies [Murphy et al. and Soderberg (as cited in Stensmo, 2006)], while different results were found in Breckler's study. Breckler et al. (2008) studied the learning style of physiology students interested in health professions during a two year period at a public undergraduate institution in California. Their findings were that the majority of students interested in the health professions have multimodal learning preferences. The most common learning preference, preferred by nearly 69.3% of all respondents, was the K learning preference. Being K in the highest percentage then suggestions were made that teaching approaches that incorporate the K learning style might be very useful and improve learning. Similarly, Hawk and Shah(2007) studied using learning style instruments to enhance student learning. They suggested classroom activities that work with the different learning styles. On the other hand, Frankel (2009) aimed to highlight the importance of recognizing individual learning styles. After administering the VAK questionnaire, the findings were that the staff of 61 students predominantly preferred visual or kinesthetic learning with auditory the least preferred (chislett andchapman, 2005). In addition to that, Dobson (2009) researched learning style preferences and course performance in an undergraduate physiology class of 901 students but rather than using Fleming's questionnaire, students were given only one question to self-assess their preferred sensory modality. The results indicated that both females and males most preferred visual learning (46%) and least kinesthetic (4%) with no significant difference between females and males. This was unexpected because K model was often listed as the

modality that was most preferred by students in physiology courses after a review on the literature and because this course did have a fairly extensive laboratory (e.g., hands-on) component.

In another study, Ramirez (2011) claimed that the sensory modality used for learning affects grades. By offering a variety of interactive lectures with powerpoint presentations, blackboard drawings, oral discussion, and small-group tutorials for second year undergraduate students from 2008, 2009, 2010 cohorts. Multiple-choice questions (MCQs) and problems that required simple arithmetic calculations were applied to students of different learning styles. It was found that R uni modal students performed significantly better in arithmetic questions than A and K uni modal students. However, no differences were observed after MCQs in either unimodal or multimodal students.

2.4.4- Studies on Learning Style in Lebanon:

In developing countries, the picture on the learning style of students is still not clear. In Lebanon very few studies have addressed differences on students learning style. Hadi (2007) and Sabeh(2009) studied these differences. In 2007, a study was done on the learning style preferences of students at AUB on a sample containing 151 lebanese and 27 non Lebanese students majoring in different fields. Findings showed that according to Reid's (1984) six learning styles, the Lebanese students major learning styles are the kinesthetic and the tactile while they have a minor preference for visual and auditory. It was also found out that gender was a significant predictor of learning styles. Specifically, males were found to significantly prefer working in groups and were visual learners more than females (Hadi, 2007).

In another study, Sabeh (2009) investigated the impact of a match between teaching and learning styles on university students english achievement level. Results showed that lebanese students have a preference for multiple learning styles: auditory(87%), kinesthetic(79%), tactile(77%) and visual(66%) after using the perceptual learning style preference questionnaire (PLSPQ). Results also showed that lebanese students prefer to learn through listening to spoken and oral explanations and they tend to remember information better by reading it out loud or by moving their lips as they read. This is very typical of the lebanese students especially that is expected from them to sit and their curriculum requires a lot of memorization. In addition to that, results showed that

age and gender affect learning style of students. Students between the age of 16 and 18 favored kinesthetic(88%) but this percentage decreased as age increased. The authors findings revealed that a match between teaching and learning styles has a positive impact on students achievement in English. Results showed that 24.5% of the students whose learning styles don't match the teaching style of their teachers failed while only 15% of the students whose learning styles match the teaching styles of their teachers failed. As to gender, Lebanese Female students showed a higher preference for auditory, kinesthetic and tactile than males while lebanese males showed a higher preference for visual and group learning than females. Many studies indicate that young learners develop kinesthetic and tactile modalities then as they reach the secondary school the students auditory and visual modalities become more dominant [Dunn and Dunn (as cited in Sabeh,2009)].Also the field of study is a variable that affects the learning style where science students have a minor preference for auditory learning, on the other hand computer science and engineering students have a major preference for kinesthetic learning[Reid and Peacock (as cited in Sabeh,2009)].

2.4.5- Effect Of Models on students with Different Learning Styles:

Many researchers were aware of students different learning styles and recommended that active participation with physical models can reach all types of learners via visual, auditory, kinesthetic and tactile schemes of learning (Di Carlo, 2008). They designed hands-on modeling activities claiming that a match between teaching and learning styles may affect course performance (Wu and Shah, 2004; Roberts *et al.*, 2005; Sorby, 2005). The implicit prediction of these studies was that these physical models would markedly improve the understanding of learners . Thus, students favoring kinesthetic (i.e., hands-on) learning might be more engaged in their learning when a modeling activity is used.

In a study teaching alveolar ventilation to a class of 300 first year medical students at Wayne State University school of medicine, Detroit, Michigan , Di Carlo(2008) was aware of different learning styles, he noted that active participation with models can reach all types of learners (visual, auditory, kinesthetic and tactile). Four types of simple models were distributed to the students before class and designed to help students to understand *alveolar* ventilation. Students in this study appreciated manipulating models and these models encouraged their thinking about complex interactions . It also allowed

them to understand alveolar ventilation and promoted logic, reasoning, and creativity and research oriented learning. These data supported the findings of previous studies that reported relationships between tactile model use and student learning gains (Wu and Shah, 2004; Roberts *et al.*, 2005; Sorby, 2005).

In another study, under the VARK learning style frame work , Harris et al. (2009) recommended the use of physical models that enable tactile learners to understand microscopic structures that cannot be touched. The authors added that this combination is effective because the use of both tools (models and computer imaging) allows kinesthetic learners to better develop their visuospatial thinking skills, but his study did not assess learning styles directly before their study noting that some students were much more enthusiastic and dependent on the physical models than other students, suggesting that these students rely more on tactile learning. The implicit prediction would be that these physical models would markedly improve the understanding and attitudes of tactile learners while having much less effect with other students.

In another study, Breckler and Yu (2011) studied students responses to a hands-on kinesthetic lecture activity for learning about the oxygen carrying capacity of blood. The activity was designed to address the needs of students who have a preference for kinesthetic learning and to help increase their understanding and engagement during lecture. These students were enrolled in human physiology course at San Francisco State university and modeled by using simple, nontoxic, and inexpensive materials, such as tubes, beads, and water. Two post activity assessments showed that student performance was significantly improved on the posttest compared with the pretest and that information was largely retained at the end of the course. The researchers were surprised to find that all students responded very positively to the hands-on experience. Indeed, more than half of the physiology students selected the K learning style among their preferences. The researchers expected that students with a K preference would be more likely to perform better on written assessments but their findings were that very little difference existed between students who stated a K preference and those who did not. Performance on posttest 1 showed significant improvement by the class overall. Both K and NK groups performed well, with a mean score of 90.5% and 90.6% correct answers for K and non-K groups, respectively. Both groups also had very similar numbers of correct responses among individuals. There were, however, some differences noting that the K group had approximately twice as many students who gave

all three correct responses compared with the non-K group). The researchers also compared values from posttest 1 to posttest 2 to see how well students retained the information during the intervening period. Generally, both groups exhibited lower posttest 2 scores compared with posttest 1 scores. So, it was not an effective tool in solving misconception questions. This also showed the strength of the misconception that students had.

Similarly, Breer et al. (2012) tested using a video in conjunction with a model as a study tool for undergraduate students in an Immunology class. It was a kind of peer teaching that demonstrated how to create models of the heavy and light chains of an antibody using pipe cleaners, and how the process of gene recombination functioned. The authors recommended that it is important to address as many learning styles as possible with the teaching methods available allowing engagement of students with all learning approaches. Overall, this method of imparting knowledge has been successful in helping motivated students to visualize complicated, abstract concepts, and deepen their sense of understanding and to allow kinesthetic and visual learners to succeed in a classroom setting where lectures are often tailored to suit auditory learners. The data indicated that a teaching tool of this nature, which employs a visual and auditory video component coupled with a hands-on, kinesthetic model component, should be useful to a wide variety of students, particularly the 53% of students who identified themselves as possessing a combination of learning styles. 8% of students both watched the video and made the model. Further polling would be necessary to determine the reason for the lack of participation by 61% of students. After additional surveying, the researchers found that 91% of those who watched the video and/or made the model found it to be either 'extremely helpful' or 'somewhat helpful' allowing deeper understanding, as opposed to simple memorization techniques. In addition to that, Thaman et al. (2013) used active-learning strategies such as collaborative-learning exercises, pause procedure, think-pair-share, minute papers, role playing, models, seminars, case based studies to 100 first year medical students in physiology. They prepared simple models to make the students understand the concepts of mechanics of respiratory physiology. As to their findings, the overall feedback revealed that the active learning strategies helped the students in gaining better understanding and the test marks on an identical test, showed significant increase in the active learning cohort in comparison to the previous batch of traditional learning. The authors being aware of the students different learning

styles but did not assess if K students learn better than NK . Similarly, Rao and Di Carlo(2001) used a number of active learning strategies to teach respiratory physiology and concluded that it improved performance in the exams. With these active learning strategies, visual learners were targeted by presence of models and demonstrations. Auditory learners were reached through discussions, while manipulating models and role playing satisfied kinesthetic and tactile learners. Many studies emphasized that a change in the method of instruction leads not only to a more positive achievement but also to an increase in the self efficacy or attitude:

2.5 - Models, Attitude and Self Efficacy:

Many researchers reported that using models lead not only to a higher achievement but it also increases students attitude and self efficacy in the subject matter.

In this part, the effect of modeling on students self efficacy and attitude will be covered . Under these two sub headings, self efficacy and attitude will be defined and the results of the studies on these two variables in developed and developing countries are reported. In addition to that, the role of models in increasing attitude and self efficacy in genetics and its role in increasing these two variables in students with different learning styles are also presented.

2.5.1- Attitude:

According to Pharaon (1984) , the author used Koslow's definition of attitude referring to it as beliefs and feelings about the subject of elementary science. Literature refers to attitude as a learned predisposition or tendency of an individual to respond positively or negatively to some object, situation, concept or another person (Nicolaidou and Philippou,2003). While In the study of Ajzen's discussion of attitude(1989): an individual's attitude toward an object can be inferred from his responses toward this object and these responses can be: cognitive, affective and conative. Cognitive reflect perception of the object while affective are the feelings toward the object. Conative responses are the most important and refer to the behavioral intentions but the study here is just limited to the affective domain.

In the literature many questionnaires were developed to assess students attitude. Four questionnaires are similar to those used in this study (Biology Attitude

Questionnaire(BAQ), What Is Happening In this Class? (WIHIC), Questionnaire on Teacher Interaction (QTI), *and* the Test of Science Related Attitude (TOSRA).

Many instruments have been constructed for the affective domain related to science education. One of the most frequently used instruments was developed by Fraser (1978) .TOSRA consisted of seven scales dealing with attitude: social implications of science ,normality of scientists , enjoyment of science lessons , leisure interest in science , career interest in science , attitudes to scientific inquiry . Moreover the QTI is a 48-item version and has been developed and validated [Goh and Fraser (as cited in Fraser, 1998)] .It focuses on the nature and quality of interpersonal relationships between teachers and students. Drawing upon a theoretical model of proximity (cooperation-opposition) and influence (dominance-submission), the QTI was developed to assess student perceptions of eight behaviour aspects for example(friendly, helpful, understanding, dissatisfied, admonishing). In addition to that, the BAQ is of 30 items and measures attitude through six dimensions; interest, career, importance, teacher, equipment and difficulty, for example: I like my biology teacher, our biology teacher makes us do active work, (Prokop et al. ,2007).

Another questionnaire is the WIHIC questionnaire which was developed by Fraser et al. (as cited in Brok et al. ,2010). WIHIC questionnaire is one of the most widely-used instruments in the domain of learning environments research and has been validated. It covers the three major dimensions distinguished by Moos' (as cited in Brok et al.,2010) characterizing all human learning environments: relationship, personal growth and system maintenance and change. Whereas relationship dimensions are concerned with the nature and intensity of interpersonal relationships between students themselves and the students and their teachers (for example: teacher helps, be friends, and is interested in students). Brok et al. (2010) examined how 1,474 high school Turkish students perceived their biology classroom environment by collecting data with the WIHIC questionnaire. Results indicated that Turkish classrooms were perceived lower for cooperation involvement and investigation and low for teacher support while high in terms of task orientation. In addition to that, Telli (as cited in Brok et al., 2010) found medium attitude scores for students' science enjoyment for a sample of 7,484 secondary science students.

Eventhough research conducted in developed countries may inform work on attitude but still we have to mention studies in Lebanon. Few studies have investigated Lebanese students attitudes toward science (Pharaon ,1984 and Raad, 1997. Pharaon studied the effect of language of science instruction on fifth elementary students attitude toward science and found that students socioeconomic status rather than the language was related to attitude while Raad(1997) investigated gender differences in attitude. Both studies were limited in scope and didn't provide a clear picture of Lebanese students attitude .On the other hand , Nokari(1998) assessed students' attitudes toward science at the elementary, intermediate, and secondary school levels in Beirut area. It was found that students learning science when teachers used lectures had significantly more positive attitudes than students learning science by seeing demonstrations or working with computers, and that attitudes toward science decreased with grade level.

In the light of these results, researchers emphasized that a change to a more student-centered pedagogy clearly affects students' attitudes toward biology noting that traditionally taught courses were characterized by substantial declines in attitude, this attitude change was moderated in their revised course applied on biology students during spring 1998 through spring 2000 semesters for almost all student groups, regardless of sex, class standing, starting attitude, or performance on exam. Generally, it also appeared that attitudes were improving over time(French and Russell ,2001). In contrast, Ebenezer and Zoller (as cited in French and Russell ,2001) looked at the impact of a constructivist approach to teaching in secondary schools and found no change in attitudes that could be attributed to the change in approach.

Many studies emphasized that the impact of a constructivist approach to teaching is not just to increase students achievement and attitude but it also leads to an increase in self efficacy.

2.5.2- Self Efficacy:

Schunk (1991) discussed academic motivation in terms of one type of personal expectancy: self-efficacy which is defined as "People's judgments of their capabilities to organize and execute courses of action required to attain designated types of performances" [Bandura p. 391 (as cited in Schunk,1991) . It is the extent to which individuals are confident in relation to performance of tasks or goal attainment (Thomas et al., 2008) . Schunk(1991) discussed how self-efficacy might operate during academic

learning. At the start of an activity, students differ in their beliefs about their capabilities to acquire knowledge, perform skills. Initial self-efficacy varies and is enhanced when students perceive they are making progress in learning .

Many questionnaires were used to assess students self efficacy: Students' Motivation Toward Science Learning (SMTSL), and Students Metacognition, Learning processes and Self Efficacy questionnaire (SMELIS).Tuan et al. (2005) developed SMTSL questionnaire that measures 1407 junior high school Taiwanese six scales: self-efficacy, active learning strategies, science learning value, performance goal, achievement goal, and learning environment stimulation. The self efficacy part consisted of seven items . Similarly, Thomas et al. (2008) investigated science students meta cognition, learning processes and self efficacy by using SMELIS questionnaire of 30 items and five subscales: Constructivist Connectivity (CC), Monitoring, Evaluation & Planning (MEP), Science Learning Self-efficacy (SE) part consisting of six terms, Learning Risks Awareness (AW); and Control of Concentration (CO). On the other hand, ,Nicolaidou and Philippou (2003) explored relationships between 238 fifth-grade students' attitudes towards mathematics, self-efficacy beliefs and achievement, their results Indicated a significant relationship between attitudes and achievement but a stronger relationship between efficacy and achievement without any gender difference.

The research studies reviewed above have been conducted in developed countries. Research on self efficacy from developing countries is less common. In Lebanon, research was conducted to assess self esteem in general. Al-Abed (1998) conducted a study on a sample of four hundred twenty three students in grades one, two, three, and four of the intermediate cycle to assess their self esteem under four categories: general self, home- parents, school- academic and social –self peer. Results revealed no significant difference in the correlation coefficient between self esteem scores and academic achievement While Fakhreddine(2003) investigated the effect of cooperative learning on second foreign language achievement and self esteem of 7th grade Lebanese students, her results showed that the learning together model was proved to be more effective than whole class instruction on the self esteem of 7th grade students. On the other hand, Yacob(2012) studied the self efficacy and its relation to academic achievement and motivation among Bisha colleges students at King Khalid University(Saudi Arabia), results revealed that most of the students fell just at the average level of self efficacy.

Similarly, Asha et al. (2012) studied the effect of active learning strategies on the self efficacy and achievement of second year faculty of pedagogy students in Jordan. Results showed that there was increase in students self efficacy and achievement in the experimental group.

Studies showed a relation between students Learning style and their self efficacy. Tuan et al. (2005) investigated 8th graders with different learning styles motivation outcomes after implementing 10 weeks (40 hours) inquiry-based teaching. SMTSL indicated that after inquiry instruction students' motivation for the four different learning styles of students increased significantly without any difference between them than students who enrolled in traditional teaching[Tuan, Chin & Shieh (as cited in Tuan et al.,2005).

2.5.3 - Effect of Models on Students Attitude and Self Efficacy:

Elswick (1995) stated that models help students to overcome students anxiety about math and to increase their sense of confidence to think mathematically leading to a higher self efficacy. Similarly, in another study, O'Dowd and Roca(2009) reported that incorporation of physical models increased student engagement and improved attitudes in their classes. Their students comments indicated that they enjoyed watching their peers and feeling that they were an integral part of the lecture. Only 1% of the students made comments typically expressing a preference for traditional lectures. When students were asked, "What are the instructor's teaching strengths? The students made positive comments on their teachers use of the models, students mentioned that using models strengthens their understanding of the concepts" and that contributed to the interactive nature of the class by engaging or involving the students. In addition to that there were unexpected positive comments from students receiving "D's" and "F's", it was very clear that the students attitude toward their teacher increased reporting that a lot of time and effort by her is seen. This positive attitude was not only revealed on the students but also on the teachers. In addition to that, Blonder(2010) studied the effect of modeling on teachers attitude and self efficacy, the teachers in this study enjoyed working with the teaching model showing higher teachers' attitude and self-efficacy.

2.5.3.1- Role of Models in increasing students attitude and self efficacy in genetics:

Studies showed that modeling activities in genetics lead not only to an increase in achievement but also to a more positive attitude. Mensch and Ruba (1991) investigated students attitudes and reported that these activities helped students develop significantly more positive attitudes towards biology and biochemistry than lecture teaching methods covering the same topic. Similarly, Kindfield (as cited in Chinnici et al., 2004) stated that group activities around modeling can decrease the amount of stress and negative attitude that may be associated with learning mitosis and meiosis. Students wrote that they enjoyed and they gained benefit. Moreover, Rotbain et al. (2006) students said that modeling activities broke the routine of the traditional lecture format, and many students claimed (during the interviews, or on informal occasions) that they enjoyed the activity very much and would like to have more such activities in other biology topics as well. In addition to that, in the study of Pacurar and Tirla (2009), experimental class students showed an increase of interest for the study of biology, a better collaboration between students, a higher level of involvement and adaptation to face new situations, and a stronger motivation for study. Similarly, Jittivadhna et al. (2010) students showed a positive attitude. Their attitudinal data obtained provided clear evidence that a majority of students reacted positively to the models.

2.5.3.2- Role of Models in increasing the attitude and self efficacy of different learning style students:

This positive attitude toward the integration of activities in molecular instruction was also found in the study of Di Carlo (2008). The students showed more excitement, energy, and motivation. Students showed more leisure and enjoyment after modeling, also it seemed that their leisure increased, the students enjoyed taking the models home to demonstrate to friends and family how the body works as well as use the models as future study aids. Similarly, Harris et al. (2009) stated that access to hand-held models would increase students' enthusiasm, confidence and attitude for molecular biology. Students' attitudes toward the use of models were very positive. In addition to that, Thaman et al. (2013) reported that modeling leads to greater interest, better interaction among peers and to an increase in students attitude toward learning environment. While modeling, the students felt the teacher like a friend and they found the respiratory practical classes cheerful and fun.

In their study, Breckler and Yu (2011) researched how their modeling activity increases the attitude in general, especially their attitude toward learning environment.

The two strongest survey responses were that students fully participated by touching the objects and that the lecture activity was unique compared with other classes of this type. Interestingly, students felt that the activity reinforced what they already knew. Students with K preference were slightly more enthusiastic in their responses than others. In particular, students in the K group showed significantly stronger support in the areas of wanting more hands on activities during lecture recommending the experience to their peers and feeling that the activity was engaging and unique. Pearson X^2 test showed that K and NK groups were significantly different for the questions that addressed the hands on aspect suggesting that there might be a very slight preference for the activity among students with K preference.

2.5.4- Opposite Gender and Different Kind of School Students Achievement in Biology:

Many researches have shown that mean scores on measures of science achievement, attitude and self efficacy begin to differentiate by gender. In this part, achievement, attitude and self efficacy in opposite gender and different kinds of school are discussed.

2.5.4- Opposite Gender and Different Kind of School students achievement in biology:

Keeves and Kotte (as cited in Soyly, 2006) examined students from ten different countries and found that more females enrolled in biology in secondary school. In addition to that, there were no significant differences between males and females aged 10, 14, and 18 for biology achievement while Simpson and Oliver (as cited in Soyly, 2006) showed that boys have more positive achievements than the girls across the level.

2.5.4.1- Opposite Gender Students Achievement in Genetics:

Many studies' findings on gender differences in students' performance in biology were also inconclusive. Soyibo and Ishola (as cited in Bloomfield and Soyibo, 2008) found no significant gender differences in selected Nigerian 11th-graders' performance in genetics while Woolley (1979) reported that male British students performed better in genetics than female.

2.5.4.2- Different Kind of School students achievement in biology:

While some researchers have reported that students in mixed schools significantly outperformed students in boys' and girls' schools in biology (Bloomfield and Soyibo ,2008),other studies have shown that girls' schools performed better in many school subjects including science than boys' and mixed schools[e.g., Forrest (as cited in Bloomfield and Soyibo ,2008)]. While some research findings have shown that boys in all-boys' schools statistically significantly outscored students in all-girls' and mixed schools in biology (e.g., Soyibo & Pinnock, 2005).

2.5.5- Gender and Attitude

French and Russell(2001) investigated a major literature about attitudes to science and its implications. Seymour and Hewitt (1997) reported that female students are more likely to abandon the sciences as a major than their male counterparts and suggested the use of inquiry , collaboration and student centered pedagogies to balance this gender gap [Seymour and Hewitt (as cited in French and Russell ,2001)]. On the other hand, Simpson & Oliver (as cited in Soylyu ,2006) noted that in some studies, it was in favor of boys, during the middle school years . Moreover, they showed that both attitudes toward science and science motivation for boys and girls from grades 6 to 10 declined but boys have more positive science attitudes than the girls across the level. Similarly, males held more positive attitudes toward science than females [Keeves and Kotte (as cited in Soylyu ,2006)].

In contrast, other studies indicated no difference between males and females as to their attitude toward science [Shaw and Doan (as cited in French and Russell ,2001)] . While the results of the study of Prokop et al.(2007) revealed that biology is somewhat more attractive to females compared to males but this effect of gender was not significant. On the other hand, there was a significant interaction of students' interest in relation with gender where girls have more interest in biology. But the degree of interest decreased as the students got older. Also students' attitude was positive and their attitude toward biology teacher was strongly affected by teacher identity. The author suggested that attitudes are likely to be influenced by curricula (subject) and teacher can significantly affect students' attitudes toward biology and this outcome interest in biology depends on the topic. The author added that students' had positive attitudes toward practical settings ,(Prokop et al.,2007).

In another study, Usak et al. (2009) studied students' attitudes toward biology with a large sample of university students, the findings of their study were that the attitudes toward biology among Turkish university students considered as positive but contrary to general expectations, it did not support the idea that females prefer biology more than males.

In Lebanon, Raad(1997) investigated gender differences in attitude toward science at the intermediate and secondary school levels, her sample was selected from four schools in Beirut : two public single sex schools and two private coeducational schools, she found that males and females didn't differ in their attitude while Nokari (1998) found that students in mixed schools had more positive attitudes toward science than students in single-sex schools and males had more positive attitudes toward science than females.

Studies showed that self efficacy varied in Opposite Gender Students:

2.5.6- Gender and Self efficacy

Several studies have documented that females have lower levels of self-efficacy in math and science courses compared to males. For example, it was found that high school girls, regardless of achievement level, scored lower than boys on perceived ability in biology, chemistry, and physics (DeBacker & Nelson, 2000). On the other hand, other results revealed no significant difference in self esteem total score across gender(Al-Abed,1998).

2.6 - Gaps in the Literature and Implications of the Literature on the Present Study:

2.6.1- Gaps in the Literature

The literature provided a clear feedback on the use of concrete materials. However, some studies didn't provide details on the instruction followed during modeling and there were no examination on the teacher application of the modeling process (Blonder,2010). In other studies, there was time constraint and the scheduling of the modeling activities was difficult,(Thaman et al ,2013). In addition to that, in some studies, the topic that was explained through modeling was not a part of the syllabus (Blonder ,2010). Similarly, Breckler and Yu (2011) course was taught by two different

teachers who also adopted two different text books, so the coverage was somewhat different between the control and experimental classes. On the other hand, in some studies, the data collection method was not precise and the ratings were inflated (O'Dowd and Rocca, 2009), while in other studies the sample was not representative. Blonder (2010) sample was very small. Still another drawback in learning style studies where the instruments used to assess the learning style were not valid. Breckler and Yu (2011) learning preference was collected via self-reporting rather than by validating instruments.

2.6.2- Implications of the literature on the present study:

To sum up, most of these studies showed that students' achievement, attitude and self-efficacy increased after implementing modeling. In addition to that, some studies showed that modeling increased the attitude and achievement of different learning style students but mainly of kinesthetic learners due to the match between teaching and learning style. As to the kind of school or gender effect, many studies showed that these constructivist approaches used in learning narrow this gender gap between males and females in their achievement, attitude and self-efficacy.

In Lebanon, there are no published studies that give feedback on students' achievement in genetics. In addition to that, there are no studies on the effect of modeling activities on students' achievement, attitude and self-efficacy in opposite gender and different learning style students. Most Lebanese studies cover each of these variables in a separate way (either learning style alone or self-efficacy and gender, or attitude and gender) but there was no coverage for all these variables at the same time in this broad way as in our study here. The learning style of Lebanese students was assessed and their self-efficacy and attitude was measured but not upon changing the method of instruction and following a new active method of modeling for secondary biology students. Here comes the importance of our study to give a feedback on the increase in achievement, attitude and self-efficacy of different learning style students after implementing modeling activities for grade 11 biology students in different kinds of schools (boys, girls, and mixed).

CHAPTER III

METHODOLOGY

This chapter outlines the methodology of the present study, more specifically this chapter presents the subjects of the study and how the sample was selected. It also discusses instrument development for this study and the procedure followed, finally it describes the data collection and the data analysis followed.

3.1- Sample

The population of the present study consisted of grade 11 scientific students of an average age of 16 years, this was done by assigning numbers for boys alone, girls alone and mixed official schools prepared by the center for educational research and development in Lebanon . Secondary students learn genetics in their curriculum in grades 11 and 12 but grade 11 students were chosen because grade12 is just one section in most schools which impedes our study. In addition to that, there is no time to conduct studies in grade 12 whose curriculum is packed and have official exams. The researcher had many obstacles while choosing the sample, many schools had just one section for this class. In addition to that, many of the teachers refused to cooperate due to lack of time. Also, most of grade 11 sections were sorted those with high grades alone in a section and lower grades in another section.

The participants in this study were grade 11 scientific students in a mixed school, boys alone and girls alone school in Beirut , Baabda and Aley. The girls school was Birj Al barajneh school for girls in Baabda while the boys school was Al Rawas school for boys in Beirut and the mixed school was Baissour School in Aley ,(the schools were from different areas which was a limitation in our study). The number of participating sections were six. Two sections per each school where one was considered as control while the other was considered as experimental. The sample is presented in table 1 below.

Table 1: Distribution of the sample as to their kinds of school

Mixed School (40 students)		Boys School (58 students)		Girls School (53 students)	
Control (20)	Experimental (20)	Control (30)	Experimental (28)	Control (29)	Experimental (24)

The reason for choosing these schools were that among the schools we contacted and whose teachers accepted to cooperate with us, those were all heterogeneous in the distribution of students among the sections. The sections were not sorted those with high grades alone in a section and lower grades in another section and when comparing the average of the classes in these three schools, the averages were very similar, students were homogeneous. The two sections within the same school and the sections involved in the three schools had similar score averages during the first semester of the academic year. So, the researcher was confident that both experimental and control groups entered the study with comparable skills and showed no differences in previous pretest scores between them. Then any performance in their achievement would be due to modeling. In addition to that, The researcher aim of choosing girls alone, boys alone and mixed schools was to answer the research question and study if implementing the modeling treatment changes in opposite gender and different kind of school students.

3.2- Instructors

Three instructors having a wide experience in biology teaching participated in the study. All don't have any experience in modeling. The researcher had meetings with those teachers outside of regular class time to discuss the modeling activities instructions and conditions. In the interview, the researcher gathered some background information regarding awareness of modeling and teaching methodologies to be confident that all entered the study with comparable attitude toward modeling and showed no differences in modeling skills (check interview questions and answers in the appendix I).

3.3- Instruments

Four evaluation instruments were used in this study: pre and post evaluation test, attitude and self efficacy questionnaire, learning style questionnaire , and an open ended questionnaire just for experimental sections.

3.3.1- Attitude and Self Efficacy questionnaire

The reason behind using the questionnaire is that it is an unobtrusive way of collecting data where the observer has no influence on the results. This questionnaire gives us feedback on students attitude and self efficacy . The attitude scale consisted of four subscales: enjoyment, leisure, attitude toward the teacher and attitude toward the learning environment. The self efficacy scale consisted of ten items. The Biology

Attitude and Self Efficacy questionnaire was completed by the students before the implementation of the study and then again after the end of the study in order to compare possible differences regarding students self efficacy and attitudes towards biology before and after implementing modeling.

As to the attitude part, it was twenty items. The researcher wanted to measure the increase in the attitude as a whole and then to specify in which subscale of the attitude there was increase. There were five items for each subscale as followed (table 2):

Table 2: Subscales and the Items of Biology Attitude and Self Efficacy Questionnaire.

Subscales	Items
1. Enjoyment	1, 5, 9, 13, 17
2. Leisure	2, 6, 10, 14, 18
3.attitude toward the learning environment	4, 8, 12, 16, 20
4. attitude toward the teacher	3, 7, 11, 15, 19

The negative statements were: 1, 6, 9, 17, 19, 20 while the others were positive. In the self efficacy part: The negative items were :23, 25, 26, 27, 28, 30 while the others were positive. (check Appendix II)

The subscales in this questionnaire were adopted from questionnaires in the literature that were developed to assess students attitude and self efficacy . The four questionnaires which measured scales similar to those used in our study were WIHIC, and TOSRA. The two subscales enjoyment of science lessons and leisure were adopted from TOSRA (Fraser ,1978) .Moreover the attitude toward the teacher was adopted from another questionnaire the WIHIC questionnaire which was developed by Fraser et al. (as cited in Brok et al.,2010) that covers the relationship dimensions with the nature and intensity of interpersonal relationships having the teacher support as a dimension (for example: teacher helps, be friends, and is interested in students) and the attitude toward the learning environment(Cooperation and Involvement).

As to the self efficacy part: Many questionnaires in the literature were used to assess students self efficacy: Items 22,23, 27, 28 were adopted from the self efficacy scale in SMTSL questionnaire and the other items were chosen from the self efficacy part in SMELIS(Thomas et al ,2008).

The questionnaire was independently revised by two examiners from the faculty of pedagogy Lebanese University and a statistics expert in order to maintain validity. Selected items were then attached to a five-point Likert scale; ranging from “strongly agree” to “strongly disagree” with “neither disagree nor agree” as the pivotal point of the scale. Positive items were scored from 5 to 1, from “strongly disagree” to “strongly agree,” respectively, while negative items were scored in the reverse order.

3.3.2- Learning Style Questionnaire:

The researcher followed the VAK questionnaire taken from Chislette and Chapman (2005) but made little changes on it to suit students.

Before the treatment, students in both the experimental and control sections were asked to select their preferred learning preference(s) by following VAK questionnaire, example: *A. visual* (V: I like to learn by viewing graphs, drawings, or schematic diagrams), *B. auditory* (A:I like to learn by speaking, listening, or discussing material), *C. kinesthetic* (K:I like to learn by touching objects or doing hands-on activities),(Check appendix II part IV).To assess the learning style of any student, the researcher was following the same way mentioned in the literature review by counting and checking for the highest percentage of answers.

In the learning style, The researcher considered the V and A as non Kinesthetic(NK). So 1 and 2 are NK while the 3 is kinesthetic (K). The researcher wanted to know which students had stated a K learning preference, as she predicted that these students would respond differently to a hands-on kinesthetic activity than those who did not.

3.3.3- Pretest in biology achievement

An instrument for assessing students conceptual understanding in biology was developed for the purposes of the study. The instrument consisted of four parts for four lessons which were explained before the intervention(Karyotype, mitosis, structure of DNA and Replication). The researcher, who is a biology teacher, developed these tests and two other biology teachers (with more than 10 years of experience) assessed the tests validity making sure they accurately measured what they are supposed to measure . The items designed for these tests were aligned with the chapter objectives that were defined in terms of both content and the three domains (check Appendix III). The Lebanese official exams assess students according to these three domains: acquired knowledge, scientific reasoning and communication skills (CERD, 1995).The validation

of the post test was based on the matching validation with the objectives and the three Domains, acquired knowledge (A), reasoning (B), and communication (D). There was high percentage of agreement between the two teachers and the researcher .The researcher then met with each teacher to reach consensus and discuss and agree on the differences. These experts are biology controllers in the Lebanese official exams, they further checked if test items agree with the A, B, and D domains and with unit objectives. The pretest was piloted on a sample outside the study. All necessary changes were done prior to administering the test to our sample. The tests mostly included multiple-choice questions and open-ended questions.

3.3.4- Posttest

To assess the educational potential of the model. A post test was administered on the same sample that was pretested. The questions were on the activities Transcription, Translation, Proteins and mutations , incorporating some common student misconceptions from the researcher's' experiences,(Appendix IV). The post test had the same lay out as the pre test in the number of questions and in following the three domains . Also, It was validated by the same teachers who worked on the pretest and piloted on the same sample that was pre tested before. The total score was 10 points distributed on three domains. The marks in the pretests and post tests were distributed in the same way followed in Lebanese Official exams.

Domain A =4.5pts, Domain B = 4 pts, Domain D = 1.5 pts.

3.3.5- Open ended questionnaire

This questionnaire was distributed to students just after the treatment so that its collected data was used to shed more light on various issues of the treatment and its implementation from a qualitative point of view. It supported our multiple choice questionnaire since it covered same subscales found in the multiple choice questionnaire. Only students in the experimental group were encouraged to answer these questions regarding their experience in constructing model. It consisted of nine questions. One question gave us feedback on students past experience with modeling. Another question reflected their attitude toward modeling and solicited students opinions about the modeling activity. In addition to that, there were four questions that measured attitude in general and its subscales: leisure, enjoyment , attitude toward the learning environment and attitude toward the teacher. Moreover, there was also one

question that showed students reflection on this modeling activity. It was piloted on the same group of students outside the sample mentioned above. (Check Appendix V)

3.4- Piloting

A pilot study was conducted on a sample of 26 grade eleven students. These were grade eleven students selected from a school not a part of the sample otherwise the results will be contaminated. The piloting took place two weeks prior to the present study. The pilot study was conducted for the following purposes to check for clarity of items in the questionnaire. The second issue related to the format of the questionnaire and the time it took to complete. The researcher timed how long it took to complete each questionnaire, asked the students for their opinions on the clarity of the instructions and the questionnaire design: layout and font size. As a result of piloting changes were carried on.

The reliability (Alpha coefficient) of the twenty items of the biology Attitude Scale (BAS) was high. When it was used before the implementation of the study (pre), it was 0.709 and 0.721 when it was used after the implementation of the study (post). More specifically, reliability of each subscale items was also measured (check appendix VI). Moreover, the students were told the purpose of the study and that their results will be kept confidential.

3.5- Design and Procedure

Two months before the intervention began, the researcher had three meetings with a modeler who is also a teacher to discuss all the details of the modeling activities to make sure that the participating teachers don't create any misconception in the minds of the student. This modeler experienced modeling for her students for many years and instructed teachers on modeling activities practices. Prior to the treatment, the researcher collected informed consent letters from the principals of the three schools. The study was conducted during the first two months of the year 2013 January and February 2013 . One month before the intervention, the researcher also held several meetings with the teachers who taught the lesson in order to discuss the content and teaching approaches and made sessions with them on practice modeling to guarantee an optimum performance through out the activity. Same instructors taught the experimental and control sections in each school but different instructors taught in different schools but all don't have any experience in modeling .

The eight week study consisted of three phases presented in table 3: a) pretesting and administering multiple choice attitude, self efficacy and Learning style questionnaire
 b) five study sessions devoted to studying: either by modeling activities or traditional lecture

c) post testing and re administering multiple choice attitude and self efficacy questionnaire for control and experimental while open ended questionnaire was just administered to the experimental group.

Table 3: Weekly distribution schedule of the study

Pretreatment: Week 1	period 1: multiple choice attitude, self efficacy and Learning style questionnaire
Week 1	Period 2: pretest
Treatment: Week 2	Practicing modeling on old taught concepts period 1:DNA structure(application)
Week 2	Practicing modeling on old taught concepts period 2:Proposing a model for Replication(inquiry)
Week 3	period 1:lecture on DNA Histone Model
Week 3	period 2:Modeling DNA Histone Model (application)
Week 4	period 1:lecture on Transcription
Week 4	period 2:Modeling Transcription (application)
Week 5	period 1:lecture on Translation
Week 5	period 2:Modeling Translation (application)
Week 6	Period 1:proposing a model for mutation (inquiry)
Post treatment: Week 7	Period 1:Post test
Week 7	Period 2: multiple choice attitude and self efficacy questionnaire for control and experimental.
Week 8:	Period 1:administering open ended questionnaire for experimental sections only.

This schedule contained a detailed hourly breakdown of the materials to be covered to make sure that the three teachers covered the same materials using same methodologies

.It is important to note that the sections involved in the study although taught by three different teachers and had similar score average during the first semester of the academic year during which the study was conducted but the researcher didn't only refer to this but also conducted his own pretest for all these students to make sure that the sections are homogeneous according to the same evaluation. To answer the research question, if a revised teaching methodology that emphasized modeling affect the achievement, attitudes and self efficacy toward biology of different sub-groups of students (based on sex, kind of school, and Learning style), differentially. The learning style questionnaire and the attitude and self efficacy questionnaire were administered to students. More over, the researcher promised the students confidentiality and was there to answer any questions or clarify any ambiguities that the students might have encountered while filling in the questionnaire.

Using random selection, one of the groups was assigned as experimental while the other as control. The control group implemented the traditional method approach which is text based approach where the teacher was armed by the chalk to explain text book lessons required by the curriculum on the board and students were busy taking notes. Teachers in the control group were all following the same lecture method, just explaining on the board, no power points, showing illustrations found in books. The experimental group used the modeling activities approach which consisted of modeling activities that implemented the same text used in the traditional method in addition to modeling activities that made the lesson interactive. The modeling activities were conducted in the class in a way that the students work as pairs. The modeling activity way was adopted by the researcher from two sites:([http:Teach . Genetics. Utah.edu](http://Teach . Genetics. Utah.edu) and WWW.LessonPlanInc.com). The two teachers followed the instructions as it is so there was no teachers effect. This modeling approach didn't cancel or replace the role of the teacher, though the teacher was still responsible for presenting the lesson by lecturing and by checking that the modeling activity was properly applied and by making sure that the students were not disoriented.

The first treatment period consisted of training the experimental group students to use modeling. At the beginning of the period , the teacher introduced modeling to students, then an example on modeling which is building DNA was provided followed by an application for the remaining of first hour. Students in the experimental group were practicing construction of the model referring to the concept provided by the teacher

that was related to materials previously taught in class. These included biology concepts known to students in order to help the students focus on learning the process of modeling. Since the students were not trained to model before, the teacher proposed a design and they discuss it together in class. So, period one was a discussion of the problem: How to model DNA? There was a discussion of the model and it ends up on a convenient model guided by the teacher . In the following hours, the teacher asked the students to propose a model for replication which was a concept that was also taught before. So the problem was: how to model replication. The teacher didn't give the details of the procedure. She just gave the materials and the students proposed the models and compared it to their friends to reach a consensus model. Of course the teacher was giving little guidance whenever they needed. During the modeling process, the models were corrected by the teacher if the students could not do the correction by comparing their models to their friend models, though there was no rubric, students were getting feedback to help them ameliorate the skill of modeling.

While in the second week the second part of the treatment started, students had a lecture on DNA Histone Model followed by another period of modeling for this concept. During the third and fourth week, both groups started the protein synthesis chapter which took two weeks to complete. The students in the experimental group were required to submit once per week a modeling project constructed by using the concepts taught in class. So it was modeling activities in combination with lecture. while the control received the same periods of lecturing while in the modeling hours the teacher was busy re explaining unclear details or solving exercises and having students copy extra notes.

The researcher was observing in the three experimental sections to check that the new implemented way was applied in the same way in the three experimental sections and to ensure the authenticity of the treatment and to solve any problems during modeling. Post modeling, the students who were pre tested were then post tested .The pretests and posttests assessment scores were compared both within the group and across the three groups in order to evaluate the effectiveness of each procedure. In addition to that , To assess any change in their attitude and self efficacy that could be attributed to modeling, the attitude and self efficacy questionnaires were redistributed to control and experimental groups and compared to the ones delivered before. While the open ended questionnaire was filled only by experimental sections to collect feedback on these modeling activities.

3.6- Treatment Approach

The researchers adopted the modeling practice of Schwarz et al.(2009) where the author identified four elements of the modeling practice: model construction by the students, model evaluation when students compare and evaluate different models, then model revision where students revise their models by taking into account any additional evidence and at the end model use to illustrate or to explain . Another important aspect the researcher followed in this study was the condition of asking students to examine/evaluate the model and determine its weakness compared to the actual model, this condition of modeling practiced at the end of each activity was adopted from Chabalengula & Mumba(2012) who were aware of the limitation of the model. These modeling activities were not demonstrated by the teacher instead it was hands on activities where the students were actively building their models . The integration of modeling in class was done as a hands-on activity, which most of the time came with a set of instructions that enabled students to work independently, it was as an application(check appendix VII: Building DNA, transcription, translation and still there were cases where the students worked alone through the modeling just with the materials and without any instruction on how to build their model(Inquiry based modeling) check appendix VII(replication and mutation). In their modeling, the students followed a combination of both inductive and deductive approach. When students proposed the model and design it in replication and mutation, that was an inquiry based modeling activity while in the other activities the students were just applying. The following is a description of the modeling activities: students were provided with the materials. These modeling activities used content prepared based on the curriculum used by the school. Thus, the information presented to the students was exactly what they needed to study.

The students experienced six modeling activities. Building DNA, Replication, DNA Histone model, Protein synthesis: transcription and translation, and DNA mutations,(check Appendix VII and its six topics).

For example, in the DNA molecule model, a specific cardboard color and shape was used to represent the deoxyribose sugar, a red circular bead shaped cardboard represents the phosphate, Transparent plastic connections, tooth picks, cotton swabs or tapes represent hydrogen bonds and other colors of cardboard represent the nitrogenous bases. The fact that each part represents a component that appears in each nucleotide helps to

reduce information represented in the chemical formula of the DNA molecule. Rotbain et al. (2006) in his modeling activity was aware of this fact adding that this helps students to understand the basic structure of the DNA molecule.

The set of instructions for operating the modeling activities were conducted by a pilot group. Piloting was continued until the researcher found that the instructions were clear enough and the students were able to work with them (constructing and manipulating the molecules) independently. Students were asked to work in pairs for both practical and educational reasons: the practical reason concerned students' workload in building the model; the educational reason involved the advantages of cooperative learning. The entire activity took one hour. Students received detailed instructions on how to build and manipulate the model. Students in the modeling group were introduced to the chemical formula of the nucleotide (like the control group), then they were asked to build the four DNA nucleotides. Using these cardboard-nucleotides, they built, according to a given sequence, one strand of DNA molecule then created the double-helix DNA structure by adding the complementary nucleotides (T-A; CG). The DNA cardboard molecule was used later to explain, physically and visually, processes that relate to the DNA molecule, such as DNA replication (Topic 2 Appendix VII) and protein synthesis (Topics 4 and 5 Appendix VII) and DNA mutation (Topic 6 Appendix VII) .

In all activities, the teacher helped those who needed technical support with the model or required clarification regarding the modeling procedure.

Another hands-on activity called the DNA Histone Model activity was performed with these students ,(http:Teach . Genetics. Utah.edu).This activity was carried out with the experimental group students enrolled in the study.

To summarize the activity, each pair of students were first given a DNA molecule and asked about modeling this DNA with its corresponding histones to make it either accessible or inaccessible to Protein synthesis.

The fourth activity was: Transcription: The first step in Protein synthesis, using the Cardboard made nucleotides the students build their m RNA.

The fifth activity was Translation: The second step in protein synthesis. Using cardboard, the students build the components of the system: the ribosome, the T RNA combined to its corresponding amino acids and translated their mRNA into a polypeptide chain.

The sixth activity was mutation: The students proposed a model for different kinds of DNA mutations by using the same materials used above in building DNA. To learn the effect of different sequence of DNA on the amino acid sequences, they compared their sequences to their friends.

These models were easy to manipulate, thus providing students with opportunities for constructing. There was no specific grid for assessment but in the three schools the teachers were observing if the students were properly applying these modeling activities, making revision for their models and discussing its limitation in a way how it differs from the original.

3.7- Data Analysis

In our analysis, student data were placed into two groups based on whether a student reported a K preference among his learning preferences (i.e., K group) or did not report a K preference (i.e., non-K group). Percentages were obtained by dividing the number of students by the total number of respondents. In addition to that, student data were placed into two groups based on gender (male or female) and into three groups based on kind of school (girls alone, boys alone and mixed schools). Students scores on the pre test and the post tests were computed to be used in answering research questions. Moreover, scores on the four subscales of the biology attitude scale and self efficacy were computed to be used in answering research questions. Finally, qualitative data from students' responses on the open ended questionnaire were analyzed in order to support our findings in the multiple choice questionnaire since it covers same subscales.

3.7.1- Quantitative Data Analysis

The computer program SPSS was used to quantify the data collected via the questionnaires. The information and all questions were coded and entered into the SPSS computer program. The questionnaire items were coded and categorized. Since the 30 statements in the attitude and self efficacy questionnaire were designed on a likert scale from 1 to 5, the number which the student ticked was entered as it is.

Firstly the three variables of the present study were operationalized. Gender as (male versus female), kind of school (boys alone, girls alone or mixed) and learning style (Kinesthetic versus non kinesthetic).

Students' responses were coded as 1 referring to highest level attitude and 5 referring to lowest level attitude toward biology. Firstly, total score for whole instrument and then for each sub-scale was calculated.

Having performed the preliminary analysis for data cleaning (particularly, missing data and outlier analysis), the descriptive analysis (means, standard deviations, and coefficient of variation) were run and inferential analysis (T test, Paired T test and ANOVA) were conducted respectively.

- a. Mean: The most common expression for the mean of a statistical distribution with a discrete random variable is the mathematical average of all the terms. To calculate it, the values of all the terms should be added up and then divided by the number of terms.
- b. Standard deviation: A measure of the dispersion or spread of values of a variable around a population mean value.
- c. CV or coefficient of variation: It's an indicator to study exactly the dispersion or the concentration around the mean, when this indicator approaches to 100% , then it shows a strong dispersion and when it approaches to 0% then it means a strong concentration.
$$CV = \frac{\text{Standard deviation}}{\text{Mean}}$$

Paired t test , t test and ANOVA were also conducted. Paired sample t-test was used, it's a parametric test used to compare two means of the same group and to study if the difference is significant or not.

While the t-test is a parametric test used to compare two means of different groups and to study if the difference is significant or not while Anova test is a parametric test used to compare more than two means of the same group and to study if the difference is significant or not.

Means and standard deviations and coefficient of variation were calculated for the following variables in both groups: achievement in biology prior to treatment, achievement in biology after the treatment with its three subscales . It was also calculated for attitude with all its subscales. Also, to study the difference between pretest and posttest a paired sample t-test was used to compare its two means of the same group and to study if the difference is significant or not.

For the comparison between the experimental and control groups and to study opposite gender, different learning style, and different kind of school attitude, self efficacy and

achievement subscales, a t-test was used. T-test was used to compare its two means and to study if the difference is significant or not. On the other hand, for the school type and since it contains 3 options (Boys, girls and mixed) ANOVA was conducted.

3.7.2- Qualitative Data Analysis

In the open ended questionnaire, the data was analyzed qualitatively by developing categories for their answers on each question. In addition to that, the instructors whose students filled the questionnaire were interviewed to gather some background information regarding this new teaching methodology.

It is worth noting that all analyses of qualitative data were checked by a second coder until consensus was reached in order to insure the validity and reliability of results.

CHAPTER IV

RESULTS

This chapter reports the findings of the present study. The results are subdivided into two sections. The first section presents the quantitative results acquired from the analyzing the Pre tests post tests , VAK questionnaire and the Biology Attitude and Self efficacy questionnaire and its sub scales. The second section presents results acquired from analyzing qualitative data from students responses to the open ended questionnaire.

4.1- Quantitative Results

The total number of students in this study was 151students with72 students in the modeling experimental group and 79 students in the control group. The participants of this study were distributed by learning style, gender, and kind of school.

4.1.1- Descriptive statistics:

1. Control group

Figure 1 presents the number of control students who participated in this study by gender.

Figure1: Percentage of opposite gender students in the control
The percentage of male in the control is 45.57% compared to 54.43% for the female.

- Kind of school: The percentage of control students in the boys alone school is the highest 37.97% while in the girls alone school it is lesser: 36.71%, in the mixed school the percentage is 25.32%. Figure 2 presents the number of control students who participated in this study by kind of school.

Figure2: Percentage of different kind of school students in the control

- Learning style: The percentage of students with K learning style is 44% lesser than the non K (56%)

Figure 3 presents the number of control students who participated in this study by learning style distribution.

■ Non kinesthetic in VAK ■ Kinesthetic learners in VAK

Figure3: Percentage of different learning style students in the control

- Score of the three domains (Pretest):
- Table 4 presents control students score in the pre test.

Table 4: control students score in the pre test achievement subscales

	Acquired Knowledge (4.5 pts)	Scientific Reasoning (4 pts)	Communication (1.5 pts)	Total (10 pts)
Mean	3.32	0.91	1.21	5.44
Std. Deviation	0.91	0.67	0.54	1.29
CV	27.47%	73.90%	45.13%	23.71%
% of the total pts	73.77%	22.78%	80.38%	54.40%

The mean of the domain A (Acquired knowledge) is 3.32 which means that the control group acquired knowledge is high while those students show very low reasoning mean 0.91 from a total of 4 points. This means that the students failed in this part and showed low reasoning while their mean in the communication part 1.21 out of 1.5 which shows high communication skills. As to the CV (coefficient of variation), It is low for A (27.47%) which means that the students were all of the same level. Same for D domain (Communication), the CV was not high (45.13%) while for B domain (Scientific reasoning) the CV was high (73.90%) which shows that the dispersion in this domain was high and students were of different levels, some students were of high reasoning while others their reasoning was very low and they decrease the overall class marks. In the total marks, students in the control group gain 54.40% which means they are on the

average with highest percentage of total points in D domain 80.38% and lowest percentage in B: 22.78% while their A domain points percentage was 73.77% so it was their low reasoning marks that lower the total points of these students.

- Score of the three domains (Post test):
- Table 5 presents control students score in the posttest:

Table 5: control students score in the posttest achievement sub scales

	Acquired Knowledge (4.5 pts)	Scientific Reasoning (4 pts)	Communication (1.5 pts)	Total (10 pts)
Mean	3.10	2.13	0.94	6.17
Std. Deviation	0.68	0.74	0.34	1.34
CV	22.00%	34.70%	36.38%	21.80%
% of the total pts	68.92%	53.24%	62.45%	61.68%

As to the results of the post test, the control group students showed an increase in the percentage of total points to 61.68% with highest percentage of points in A domain: 68.92% while the scientific reasoning increased to 53.24% with CV: 34.70%, so their CV in reasoning decreased which means that the dispersion in their marks becomes lesser and their marks in this domain became similar while their D domain decreased to 62.45%.

- Results of the Attitude and Self Efficacy and its subscales (Pre test):
- Table 6 presents control students results in the attitude and self efficacy questionnaire in the beginning of the study.

1	2	3	4	5
SA	A	N	D	SD

SA: strongly agree; A: agree; N: neither agree nor disagree; D: disagree; SD: strongly disagree

Table 6: control students results in the attitude and self efficacy questionnaire (pretest)

	Mean	Std. Deviation	CV
Enjoyment	2.68	0.95	35.23%
Leisure	3.20	0.72	22.61%
Attitude toward Teacher	3.00	0.97	32.36%
Attitude toward the learning environment	2.09	0.57	27.26%
Attitude	2.74	0.61	22.08%
Self efficacy	2.44	0.77	31.44%

As to the results of control students to the attitude and self efficacy questionnaire. These students were neutral as to their results in the attitude toward biology (mean: 2.74), more specifically they were neutral in the following subscales enjoyment(mean:2.68), leisure(mean:3.20) and attitude toward the teacher sub scales(mean:3.00) while their attitude toward the learning environment was positive(mean:2.09), also their self efficacy was positive(mean:2.44).

- Results of the Attitude and Self Efficacy subscales (Posttest):
- Table 7 presents control students results in the attitude and self efficacy questionnaire at the end of the study.

Table 7: control students results in the attitude and self efficacy questionnaire (post test)

	Mean	Std. Deviation	CV
Enjoyment	2.63	0.91	34.71%
Leisure	3.13	0.77	24.71%
Attitude toward Teacher	3.04	0.96	31.63%
Attitude toward the learning environment	2.19	0.57	25.83%
Attitude	2.75	0.58	20.99%
Self efficacy	2.44	0.63	25.77%

There was no significant variation in any of these scales and subscales after control students were post tested in their attitude and self efficacy questionnaire. These students were still neutral as to their results in the attitude toward biology (mean: 2.75), enjoyment (mean:2.63) , leisure (mean:3.13) and attitude toward the teacher sub scales(mean:3.04) while their attitude toward the learning environment was still positive(mean:2.19), also their self efficacy was positive(mean:2.44).

2. Experimental group

- Gender
- Fig 4 presents the number of experimental students who participated in this study by gender.

Figure 4: Percentage of opposite gender students in the experimental
The percentage of males in the experimental is 51.39% compared to 48.61% for the female

- Kind of school: The percentage of students in the experimental boys alone school is the highest 38.89% while in the girls alone school it is lesser: 33.33%, in the mixed school the percentage is 27.78%.
- Figure 5 presents the number of experimental students who participated in this study by kind of school.

Figure 5: Percentage of different kind of school students in the experimental

- Learning style: The percentage of students with K learning style is 34.33% lesser than the NK (65.67%).
- Figure 6 presents the number of experimental students who participated in this study by learning style distribution.

Figure 6: Percentage of different learning style students in the experimental

- Score of the three domains (Pretest): Table 8 presents experimental students score in the pretest.

Table 8: Experimental students results in the achievement test sub scales (pretest)

	Acquired Knowledge (4.5 pts)	Scientific Reasoning (4 pts)	Communication (1.5 pts)	Total (10 pts)
Mean	3.33	1.10	1.26	5.68
Std. Deviation	0.89	0.87	0.50	1.55
CV	26.87%	78.98%	39.87%	27.33%
% of the total pts	73.92%	27.43%	84.03%	56.84%

The mean of the domain A is 3.33 which means that the experimental group acquired knowledge is high while those students show very low reasoning mean 1.10 from a total of 4 points. This means that the students failed in this part and showed low reasoning while their mean in the communication part 1.26 out of 1.5 which shows high

communication skills. As to the CV, It is low for A (26.87%) which means that the students were all of the same level. Same for D Domain the CV was not high (39.87%) while for B domain, the CV was high(78.98%) which means that the dispersion in this domain was high and students were of different levels, some students were of high reasoning while others their reasoning was very low and they decrease the overall class marks. In the total marks, students in the experimental group gain 56.84% which means they are little bit higher than the average with highest percentage of total points in D domain 84.03% and lowest percentage in B: 27.43% while their A domain points percentage was 73.92% so it was their low reasoning marks that lower the total points of these students. The results of the pretest marks in the experimental were similar to those in the control.

- Score of the three domains (Post test): Table 9 presents experimental students score in the posttest.

Table 9: Experimental students results in the achievement test sub scales (posttest)

	Acquired Knowledge (4.5 pts)	Scientific Reasoning (4 pts)	Communication (1.5 pts)	Total (10 pts)
Mean	3.43	2.50	1.01	6.93
Std. Deviation	0.58	0.80	0.37	1.36
CV	16.91%	32.18%	37.03%	19.56%
% of the total pts	76.23%	62.41%	67.13%	69.34%

- As to the results of the post test, the experimental group students showed an increase in the percentage of total points to 69.34% with highest percentage of points in A domain: 76.23% while the B domain increased to 62.41% with CV: 32.18%, so their CV in reasoning decreased which means that the dispersion in their marks becomes lesser and their marks in this domain became similar while their D domain decreased to 67.13%.
- Results of the Attitude and Self Efficacy and its subscales (Pretest): Table 10 presents experimental students score in the attitude and self efficacy and its subscales before the study

Table 10: Results of the Attitude and Self Efficacy and its subscales (Pre test)

	Mean	Std. Deviation	CV
Enjoyment	2.74	0.92	33.71%
Leisure	3.22	0.76	23.67%
Attitude toward Teacher	2.73	0.69	25.38%
Attitude toward the learning environment	2.18	0.65	29.76%
Attitude	2.72	0.57	20.80%
Self efficacy	2.46	0.65	26.55%

As to the results of experimental students to the attitude and self efficacy questionnaire. These students were neutral as to their results in the attitude toward biology (mean: 2.72), more specifically they were neutral in the following subscales enjoyment(mean:2.74), leisure(mean:3.22) and attitude toward the teacher subscales(mean:2.73) while their attitude toward the learning environment was positive(mean:2.18), also their self efficacy was positive(mean:2.46). The results of the experimental group were similar to the results of the control as to their attitude and self efficacy toward biology.

- Results of the Attitude and Self Efficacy subscales (Post test): Table 11 presents experimental students score in the Attitude and Self Efficacy and its subscales at the end of the study

Table 11 : results of the attitude and self Efficacy subscales (Post test)

	Mean	Std. Deviation	CV
Enjoyment	2.53	0.91	36.07%
Leisure	3.11	0.77	24.76%
Attitude toward Teacher	2.62	0.77	29.28%
Attitude toward the learning environment	2.25	1.24	55.17%
Attitude	2.63	0.70	26.65%
Self efficacy	2.40	0.68	28.33%

There was no significant variation in any of these scales and subscales after experimental students were post tested in their attitude and self efficacy questionnaire. These students were still neutral as to their results in the attitude toward biology (mean: 2.63), enjoyment (mean: 2.53), leisure(mean: 3.11) and attitude toward the teacher sub scales(mean: 2.62) while their attitude toward the learning environment was still positive (mean: 2.25), also their self efficacy was positive(mean:2.40).

4.1.2- Inferential statistics: Pre and Post Achievement Test Subscales for Control and Experimental Group Students.

In this section, the difference between the pretest and posttest for both experimental and control groups with the comparison between the two groups was studied.

The results of subscales were also studied in opposite gender, different school type, K and NK learning styles.

4.1.2.1- Achievement Test Subscales for Control group

- Comparison between pre and posttests:
- Table 12 and figure 7 present control students% of variation in the pre tests and post tests and its subscales in the beginning and at the end of the study.

Table 12 : comparison between pre and post achievement subscales in control group:

	Means		Sig	% of variation
	Pre	Post		
Acquired Knowledge	3.32	3.10	0.041	-6.58%
Scientific Reasoning	0.91	2.13	0.000	133.68%
Communication	1.21	0.94	0.000	-22.31%
Total	5.44	6.17	0.000	13.45%

As to control group, there was significant variation in students marks between the pretests and posttests. The % of increase from pre test total marks to post test marks was % of var:13.45% (sig:0.000<0.05).Students showed a significant increase in reasoning(% of var:133.68%,, sig:0.000<0.05) while those students showed a significant decrease in their acquired knowledge(% of var:-6.58% ,sig:0.041<0.05)and a significant decrease in communication skills(%of var:-22.31%, sig:0.000<0.05).

Figure 7: comparison between pre and post achievement subscales in control group students

The pre and post achievement test subscales in different learning style, opposite gender and different kind of school control group students were presented in appendix(VIII) since these data are not required to answer any of the research questions.

- The sections below show the processes for computing the results for the research questions . Each section addresses one of the 8 research questions of the present study.

4.1.2.2- Achievement Test Subscales for Experimental group

In order to answer the first research question:

Do modeling activities compared to traditional lecturing produce higher achievement in Biology in grade 11 scientific students?

4.1.2.2.1- Comparison between pre and post tests achievement marks:

- Table13 and figure 8 present experimental students % of variation in the pre tests and post tests and its subscales in the beginning and at the end of the study.

Table 13 : comparison between pre and post tests achievement marks in experimental group:

	Means		Sig	% of variation
	Pre	Post		
Acquired Knowledge	3.33	3.43	0.368	3.13%
Scientific Reasoning	1.10	2.50	0.000	127.53%
Communication	1.26	1.01	0.000	-20.11%
Total	5.68	6.93	0.000	21.99%

As to experimental group marks, experimental students showed a significant increase in their total test marks (% of var:21.99%, sig:0.000<0.05),this was due to the sig increase in scientific reasoning (% of var:127.53% with sig0.000<0.05),experimental students showed increase in A domain but it was not sig (% of var:3.13% with sig0.368>0.05. As to D domain, students show a sig decrease in their communication skills (% of var:-20.11% with sig 0.000<0.05).

Figure 8: comparison between pre and post achievement subscales in experimental group students

4.1.2.2.2- Pre and Post achievement subscales in different learning style students : In order to answer the research sub question : Are there any statistically significant differences in achievement in biology among grade 11 scientific students after implementing modeling related to learning style?

- Table 14 and figures 9 and 10 present experimental students % of variation in the pre tests and post tests and its subscales in the beginning and at the end of the study by referring to learning style.

Table 14 : Pre and Post achievement subscales in K and NK learning style experimental students

% of variation	NK		K	
	% of variation	Sig	% of variation	Sig
Acquired Knowledge	1.88%	0.656	6.86%	0.296
Scientific Reasoning	115.27%	0.000	163.64%	0.000
Communication	-16.98%	0.010	-19.01%	0.050
Total	20.90%	0.000	27.57%	0.000

- As to experimental group learning style, both NK and K showed a significant increase in their total marks with NK (% of var:20.90%, sig:0.000<0.05), while K showed more increase(% of var:27.57%, sig:0.000<0.05). As to A domain, both NK and K showed no significant variation in this domain, (for NK, % of var: 1.88%, sig:0.656>0.05; while for K, % of var:6.86%, sig:0.296> 0.05). Both also showed a significant increase in reasoning with the % of var:163.64%, sig:0.000<0.05 in K more than NK(115.27%,sig 0.000<0.05).Only NK group showed a significant decrease in D (% of var:-16.98%, sig:0.01<0.05) while in K the decrease was not significant (% of var: -19.01%, sig:0.05).

Figure 9: comparison between pre and post achievement subscales in experimental NK group students

Figure 10: comparison between pre and post achievement subscales in experimental K group students

4.1.2.2.3- Pre and Post achievement subscales in opposite gender students: In order to answer the research sub question : Are there any statistically significant differences in achievement among grade eleven scientific students after implementing modeling related to gender?

- Table 15 and figures 11 and 12 present experimental students % of variation in the pre tests and post tests and its subscales in the beginning and at the end of the study by referring to gender.

Table 15 : Pre and Post achievement subscales in opposite gender experimental students:

% of variation	Male		Female	
	% of variation	Sig	% of variation	Sig
Acquired Knowledge	-5.32%	0.169	14.29%	0.019
Scientific Reasoning	109.74%	0.000	156.20%	0.000
Communication	-13.89%	0.090	-26.23%	0.000
Total	17.39%	0.000	27.89%	0.000

As to experimental group gender, male students showed a significant increase in their total test marks (% of var.: 17.39%, sig: 0.000<0.05). This was due to a significant increase in male group scientific reasoning (% of var: 109.74%, sig 0.000<0.05) while they showed decrease in their marks in A and D domains but this decrease was not significant,(for A, % of var: -5.32%, sig 0.169>0.05; for D, % of var: -13.89%, sig 0.090>0.05). Similarly, female experimental students showed a significant and greater increase in their total marks (% of var.:27.89%, sig:0.000<0.05).This was due to a more significant increase in their scientific reasoning(% of var :156.20%,sig:0.000<0.05). Female students increase in their A domain and this increase was significant (% of var: 14.29 %, sig 0.019<0.05) while they showed a significant decrease in their D domain (% of var: -26.23%, sig:0.000<0.05)

Figure 11: comparison between pre and post achievement subscales in experimental male group students

Figure 12: comparison between pre and post achievement subscales in experimental female group students

4.1.2.2.4- Pre and Post achievement subscales in different kind of school students: In order to answer the research sub question : Are there any statistically significant differences in achievement among grade eleven scientific students after implementing modeling related to kind of school?

Table 16 and figures 13, 14, 15 present experimental students % of variation in the pre tests and post tests and its subscales in the beginning and at the end of the study by referring to school type.

Table 16: pre and post achievement subscales in different kind of school experimental students

% of variation	Mixed		Boys		Girls	
	% of var	Sig	% of var	Sig	% of var	Sig
Acquired Knowledge	16.87%	0.038	-7.58%	0.095	6.97%	0.260
Scientific Reasoning	195.59%	0.000	93.25%	0.000	138.82%	0.000
Communication	-5.88%	0.532	-20.29%	0.026	-31.71%	0.000
Total	40.33%	0.000	12.72%	0.011	20.00%	0.002

As to kind of school variable in the experimental section, all mixed, boys and girls showed a significant increase in their total test marks with the highest increase for mixed (% of var.:40.33%,sig:0.000<0.05) more than girls (% of var.:20.00%,sig:0.002<0.05) which is in turn more than boys (% of var.:12.72%, sig:0.011<0.05). The three experimental sections showed a significant increase in their scientific reasoning. In mixed, (% of var.:195.59%, sig:0.000<0.05) more than girls (% of var.:138.82%, sig:0.000<0.05) which is in turn more than boys (% of var.:93.25%,sig:0.000<0.05), only boys and girls sections showed a significant decrease in D (% of var.: -20.29%, sig:0.026<0.05 for boys and % of var.: -31.71% and sig:0.000<0.05 for girls),while the decrease in D in mixed was not significant (% of var.: -5.88%, sig: 0.532>0.05). Students in the mixed also showed a significant increase in A domain with (% of var.:16.87%, sig:0.038<0.05) while boys showed a decrease in A domain that was not significant, (% of var.: -7.58%, sig: 0.095>0.05). On the other hand, girls school increase in A domain was not significant, (% of var.: 6.97%, sig: 0.260>0.05).

Figure 13: comparison between pre and post achievement subscales in experimental mixed group students

Figure 14: comparison between pre and post achievement subscales in experimental boys group students

Figure 15: comparison between pre and post achievement subscales in experimental girls group students

4.1.2.3- Comparison between experimental and control groups in their achievement test subscales:

Tables 17 and 18 present comparison between control and experimental students in the pre tests and post tests and its subscales in the beginning and at the end of the study.

Table 17 : comparison between pre and post tests achievement marks in experimental and control group:

	Pretest			Posttest		
	Control	Experimental	Sig	Control	Experimental	Sig
Acquired Knowledge	3.32	3.33	0.963	3.10	3.43	0.002
Scientific Reasoning	0.91	1.10	0.141	2.13	2.50	0.004
Communication	1.21	1.26	0.523	0.94	1.01	0.228
Total	5.44	5.68	0.287	6.17	6.93	0.001

Table 18 presents comparison between control and experimental students % of variation in the pre tests and post tests and its subscales in the beginning and at the end of the study .

Table 18 : comparison between control and experimental students pre and post test subscales

	Control		Experimental	
	% of var	Sig	% of var	Sig
Acquired Knowledge	-6.58%	0.041	3.13%	0.368
Scientific Reasoning	133.68%	0.000	127.53%	0.000
Communication	-22.31%	0.000	-20.11%	0.000
Total	13.45%	0.000	21.99%	0.000

Experimental students showed a more sig increase in their total test marks (% of var:21.99%, sig:0.000<0.05) than the control(% of var:13.45%, sig:0.000<0.05),experimental students showed increase in A domain but it was not sig(% of var: 3.13%, sig: 0.368>0.05)

. while those control group students showed a significant decrease in their acquired knowledge (% of var:-6.58% ,sig:0.041<0.05). As to D domain, both groups students showed a sig decrease in their communication skills (% of var:-20.11% with sig 0.000<0.05) for experimental while (%of var:-22.31%,sig:0.000<0.05) decrease in communication skills for control. Both groups students showed a significant increase in reasoning. Control group students showed a significant increase in reasoning(% of var:133.68%, sig:0.000<0.05) while increase in scientific reasoning(% of var:127.53% with sig0.000<0.05) for experimental students.

4.1.3- Comparison between Pre and Post Attitude and Self Efficacy Subscales in Control and Experimental Group Students

4.1.3.1- Attitude and Self Efficacy Subscales in Control Group Students

Comparison between pre and post Attitude and Self Efficacy Questionnaire:

- Table 19 and figure 16 present control students% of variation in the attitude and self efficacy and its subscales in the beginning and at the end of the study.

Table 19: control students attitude and self efficacy subscales (pre and post test)

	Means		Sig	% of variation
	Pre	Post		
Enjoyment	2.68	2.63	0.454	-1.86%
Leisure	3.20	3.13	0.306	-2.13%
Attitude toward Teacher	3.00	3.04	0.648	1.33%
Attitude toward the learning environment	2.09	2.19	0.077	4.79%
Attitude	2.74	2.75	0.911	0.18%
Self efficacy	2.444	2.441	0.960	-0.12%

More the scores decrease more the results are positive since we defined the answers as follow:

1 = SA, 2 = A, 3 = N, 4 = D, 5 = SD

Also when the coefficient of variation is negative this indicates that there was an increasing in the results of the subscales.

- There was no significant variation in any of the attitude, attitude sub scales and self efficacy after control group were post tested, (sig > 0.05 in all sub scales).

Figure 16: comparison between pre and post attitude and self efficacy sub scales in control group

The attitude and self efficacy subscales in different learning style, opposite gender and different kind of school control students were presented in appendix(VIII) since these data are not required to answer any of the research questions:

4.1.3.2- Attitude and Self Efficacy Test subscales for experimental group students:

4.1.3.2.1- Comparison between pre and post tests in the attitude and self efficacy subscales:

In order to answer the second research question :

- Do modeling activities compared to traditional lecturing produce higher attitude and self efficacy in biology in grade eleven scientific students?
- In order to answer this research question on students attitudes towards biology, the Biology Attitude Scale (BAS) was administered before and after the implementation of the study. As mentioned in Chapter III, the biology attitude scale consisted of four subscales (an enjoyment scale, a leisure scale, and an attitude toward the teacher scale and attitude toward the learning environment scale). Therefore, first the total score of the four subscales was conducted between the two groups, then each scale alone.
- Table 20 and figure 17 present experimental students% of variation in the attitude and self efficacy and its subscales in the beginning and at the end of the study.

Table 20: experimental students attitude and self efficacy subscales(pre and post test)

	Means		Sig	% of variation
	Pre	Post		
Enjoyment	2.74	2.53	0.039	-7.60%
Leisure	3.22	3.11	0.175	-3.41%
Attitude toward Teacher	2.73	2.62	0.290	-3.96%
Attitude toward the learning environment	2.18	2.25	0.603	3.22%
Attitude	2.72	2.63	0.230	-3.29%
Self efficacy	2.46	2.40	0.358	-2.32%

As to experimental group, there was an increase in the over all attitude and self efficacy but this increase was not significant for attitude (% of var: -3.29%, sig:0.23 >0.05) while for self efficacy (% of var:-2.32%, sig:0.358 >0.05). As to each of the attitude sub scales, only the attitude toward learning environment decrease but this decrease was not significant (sig:0.603 >0.05). However the enjoyment sub scale showed a significant increase after students experienced modeling (% of var.: -7.66%, sig:0.039<0.05).

Figure 17: comparison between pre and post attitude and self efficacy subscales in experimental group

4.1.3.2.2- Attitude and Self Efficacy subscales in different learning style experimental group students:

- In order to answer the research sub question : Are there any statistically significant differences in attitude, and self efficacy in biology among grade eleven scientific students after implementing modeling related to learning style?
- Table 21 and figures 18 and 19 present experimental students% of variation in the attitude and self efficacy and its subscales in the beginning and at the end of the study by referring to learning style.

- Table 21: K and NK experimental students attitude and self efficacy subscales(pre and post test)

% of variation	NK		K	
	% of variation	Sig	% of variation	Sig
Enjoyment	-7.88%	0.112	-9.24%	0.057
Leisure	-1.50%	0.673	-7.38%	0.115
Attitude toward Teacher	-7.96%	0.074	-0.40%	0.970
Attitude toward the learning environment	6.93%	0.434	-3.63%	0.606
Attitude	-2.80%	0.419	-5.65%	0.217
Self efficacy	-2.67%	0.368	-0.47%	0.912

As to learning style, the experimental NK section did not show any significant variation in any of the self efficacy, attitude and all its subscales. There was increase in enjoyment, leisure, and overall attitude but this increase was not significant while in the K section there was more increase in enjoyment, leisure, and total attitude but also not significant .(As to enjoyment, % of variation: -7.88%, sig: 0.112>0.05 for NK while % of variation: -9.24%, sig: 0.057>0.05 for K. In leisure, % of variation: -1.50%, sig: 0.673>0.05 for NK while % of variation: -7.38%, sig: 0.115>0.05 for K. In the total attitude, % of variation: -2.80%, sig: 0.419>0.05 for NK while % of variation: -5.65% , sig: 0.217>0.05 for K students)

As to attitude toward learning environment, there was decrease in the NK section but this decrease also was not significant (% of var.:6.93 % , sig:0.434>0.05) while the experimental K section showed non significant increase (% of var.: -3.63%, sig:0.606>0.05) . NK showed more increase in their attitude toward the teacher (% of var.: - 7.96%, sig: 0.074>0.05) and self efficacy (% of var.- 2.67%, sig: 0.368>0.05) than K but this increase was not significant(% of var.: -0.40%, sig: 0.970>0.05 for the attitude toward the teacher in K students; % of var.: -0.47%, sig: 0.912>0.05 for self efficacy in K students).

Figure 18: comparison between pre and post attitude and self efficacy subscales in experimental NK group

Figure 19: comparison between pre and post attitude and self efficacy subscales in experimental K group

4.1.3.2.3- Attitude and Self Efficacy subscales in opposite gender experimental group students:

In order to answer the research sub question :

Are there any statistically significant differences in attitude and self efficacy in biology among grade eleven scientific students after implementing modeling related to gender?

- Table 22 and figures 20 and 21 present experimental students% of variation in the attitude and self Efficacy and its subscales in the beginning and at the end of the study by referring to gender.
- Table 22: Opposite gender experimental students attitude and self efficacy subscales(pre and post test)

% of variation	Male		Female	
	% of variation	Sig	% of variation	Sig
Enjoyment	-2.60%	0.662	-12.54%	0.002
Leisure	-6.34%	0.117	0.00%	0.974
Attitude toward Teacher	1.12%	0.838	-8.96%	0.094
Attitude toward the learning environment	9.83%	0.352	-4.50%	0.321
Attitude	0.00%	0.950	-6.72%	0.038
Self efficacy	4.10%	0.334	-9.27%	0.001

As to gender, the experimental male section did not show any significant variation in any of the attitude and self efficacy subscales (% of variation : 0.00%,sig: 0.950>0.05 for attitude while % of variation: 4.10%, sig: 0.334>0.05 for self efficacy). However, there was increase in enjoyment and leisure but it was not significant (% of variation: -2.60%, sig: 0.662>0.05 for enjoyment while % of variation: -6.34%, sig: 0.117>0.05 for leisure.), while the experimental female section showed a significant increase in enjoyment (% of variation:-12.54%,sig:0.002<0.05) and a sig increase in the overall attitude and self efficacy, attitude(% of v ar.: -6.72% sig:0.038<0.05) while self efficacy(% of var.: -9.27% ,sig:0.001<0.05).As to the attitude toward the teacher subscale, experimental male section showed non significant decrease(% of var.1.12%, sig:0.838>0.05) while female section showed a non significant increase with (% of var.-8.96%, sig:0.094>0.05). As to the attitude toward the learning environment sub scale, experimental male section showed non

significant decrease (% of var.:9.83%, sig:0.352>0.05) while female section showed a non significant increase with (% of var.-4.50%, sig:0.321>0.05).

Figure 20: comparison between pre and post attitude and self efficacy subscales in experimental male group

Figure 21: comparison between pre and post attitude and self efficacy subscales in experimental female group

4.1.3.2.4- Attitude and Self Efficacy subscales in different kind of school experimental group students:

- In order to answer the last research sub question : Are there any statistically significant differences in attitude , and self efficacy in biology among grade eleven scientific students after implementing modeling related to kind of school?
- Table 23 and figures 22, 23, 24 present experimental students% of variation in the attitude and self efficacy and its subscales in the beginning and at the end of the study by referring to school type.
- Table 23: Different kinds of school experimental students attitude and self efficacy subscales(pre and post test)

% of variation	Mixed		Boys		Girls	
	% of var	Sig	% of var	Sig	% of var	Sig
Enjoyment	-0.40%	0.943	-2.56%	0.736	-18.43%	0.000
Leisure	1.77%	0.756	-7.08%	0.143	-2.39%	0.421
Attitude toward Teacher	1.14%	0.836	6.04%	0.341	-18.21%	0.005
Attitude toward the learning environment	0.53%	0.965	12.60%	0.325	-7.69%	0.166
Attitude	0.81%	0.891	1.42%	0.783	-11.70%	0.001
Self efficacy	-4.00%	0.360	6.02%	0.233	-10.38%	0.001

The experimental boys alone section didn't show any significant variation in the self efficacy, attitude and all its sub scales. There was increase in enjoyment and leisure but not significant (For boys , self efficacy: % of var: 6.02 %; sig:0.233>0.05; attitude : % of var: 1.42%; sig:0.783>0.05; enjoyment : % of var: -2.56%; sig:0.736>0.05;leisure: % of var: -7.08%; sig:0.143>0.05;attitude toward the teacher: % of var: 6.04%; sig:0.341>0.05;attitude toward learning environment: % of var: 12.60%; sig:0.325>0.05 ;while for mixed there was increase in enjoyment and self efficacy but not significant (for enjoyment :% of var: -0.40% sig:0.943>0.05; for self efficacy: :% of var: -4.00%; sig:0.360>0.05) while no significant variation in attitude and its other sub scales(for attitude: % of var: 0.81%, sig:0.891>0.05 ; leisure: % of var: 1.77%, sig:0.756>0.05; attitude toward the teacher: % of var: 1.14%

sig:0.836>0.05;attitude toward learning environment :% of var: 0.53%
 sig:0.965>0.05). As to experimental girls alone school, there was significant increase in enjoyment (% of var: -18.43%; sig:0.000<0.05) and a significant increase in the attitude toward the teacher(% of var:-18.21%; sig:o.oo5<0.05). Also the girls showed a significant increase in the overall attitude scale(% of var: -11.70%; sig:0.001<0.05). In addition to that girls self efficacy also increased significantly after modeling (% of var:-10.38%, sig:0.001<0.05),also leisure and attitude toward learning environment increase but this increase was not significant,(for leisure: % of var: -2.39% sig:0.421>0.05 ;for attitude toward learning environment: % of var: -7.69% sig:0.166>0.05.

Figure 22:Comparison between pre and post Attitude and self efficacy subscales in experimental group mixed school students

Figure 23: Comparison between pre and post Attitude and self efficacy subscales in experimental group Boys school students

Figure 24: Comparison between pre and post Attitude and self efficacy subscales in experimental group girls school students

4.1.3.3- Comparison between Experimental and control groups in their attitude and self efficacy sub scales:

Table 24 presents comparison between experimental and control groups in the attitude and self efficacy and its subscales in the beginning and at the end of the study.

Table 24: experimental and control students attitude and self efficacy subscales(pre and post test)

	Control		Experimental	
	% of var	Sig	% of var	Sig
Enjoyment	-1.87%	0.454	-7.66%	0.039
Leisure	-2.19%	0.306	-3.42%	0.175
Attitude toward Teacher	1.33%	0.648	-4.03%	0.290
Attitude toward the learning environment	4.78%	0.077	3.21%	0.603
Attitude	0.36%	0.920	-3.31%	0.230
Self efficacy	0.00%	0.960	-2.44%	0.357

In the control, there was no significant variation in the total attitude and self efficacy after control group were post tested (% of var : 0.36%, sig :0.920>0.05 for attitude while % of var: 0.00%, sig: 0.960>0.05 for self efficacy) while in the experimental group, there was an increase in the over all attitude and self efficacy but this increase was not significant (% of var:-3.29%, sig:0.23>0.05) for attitude while for self efficacy(% of var:-2.32%, sig:0.358>0.05).

As to each of the attitude subscales, in both, the experimental and the control groups, the attitude toward learning environment decrease but this decrease was more in the control group (For control :% of var : 4.78%, sig :0.077>0.05; for experimental % of var : 3.21%, sig :0.603>0.05). However, the enjoyment subscale showed a significant increase only in the experimental section after students experienced modeling (% of var: -7.66%, sig:0.039<0.05) for experimental while for control :(% of var: -1.87%, sig: 0.454>0.05). The leisure subscale increased in the experimental more than control but this increase was not significant (% of var : -3.42% ; sig: 0.175>0.05) for experimental while for control (% of var : -2.19% ; sig:0.306 >0.05). While the attitude toward the teacher decreased in the control (1.33% but it was not sig, sig:0.648>0.05) and it increases for the experimental(% of var: -4.03%, but it was not significant ,sig:0.29>0.05)

Section II

4.2- Qualitative Results:

In an attempt to gain a deeper understanding to their answers in the multiple choice questionnaire, an open ended questionnaire was administered to the students. Each of the three experimental students sections answers to the nine open ended questionnaire questions was indicative of many points, notions and interpretations. The questionnaire was analyzed qualitatively by trying to identify categories in the data. The initial categories identified were: modeling experience, attitude toward modeling, understanding, and reflection in addition to the scales and sub scales that were covered in the open ended questionnaire: self efficacy, enjoyment, leisure, attitude toward the teacher, and attitude toward learning environment. Only the experimental group students were asked to answer questions in this questionnaire:

The sample was 72 students (the experimental in the three sections: in the boys alone school, girls alone school and mixed school).

4.2.1- Students Modeling Experience

As to students answers to question 1: Have you ever experienced modeling with your teachers in the previous years? (modeling experience)

Their answers were as follows (fig 25):

Fig 25: % of students in the modeling experience subscale
 - 27.14% of the students replied yes while 72.86% replied no. So most of the students didn't have any modeling experience.

Nineteen replied yes (most of them experienced modeling in lower grades: grades two, three, seven, eight, and nine) while fifty-one replied no.

The % of students with modeling experience as to their kinds of school is presented in fig 26

Fig 26: % of students with modeling experience as to their kinds of school

- 36.84% of them are from the mixed while 42.11% from the boys alone school still 21.05% from the girls alone school.

4.2.2- Students Attitude toward Modeling

As to students answers to Question 2: Did you like this modeling activity in biology classes? If yes, why? If no, why not? (attitude toward modeling).

Their answers were as follows (fig 27):

Fig 27: % of students with positive and negative attitude toward modeling

- 82.86% of the students replied yes while 17.14% replied no. So most of the students showed a positive attitude toward modeling, only few had a negative attitude. Students gave different answers to support this positive or negative attitude, still a part didn't justify their choices.

The % of students positive answers categories (attitude toward modeling) was presented in figure 28

Fig 28: % of students positive answers categories (attitude toward modeling)

- Fifty eight replied yes: most of the students , thirty eight out of them liked it because it helped to understand more while eighteen found it entertaining and funny, seven liked it because in this way they would never forget what they learn, four liked it because there was cooperative work, two liked it because they were making mistakes and learning from these mistakes. Some students were answering two answers of the categories down.

The % of students negative answers categories(attitude toward modeling) was presented in figure 29

Fig 29: % of students negative answers categories (attitude toward modeling)

Twelve students answered no: six out of them found it waste of time, three preferred lecturing while two didn't like the materials and found it far from reality still one didn't like the subject biology whatever was done. The sample was very small so we couldn't generalize.

The % of students with negative attitude toward modeling as to their kinds of school was presented in figure 30

Fig 30: % of students with negative attitude toward modeling as to their kinds of school

Among those who had negative attitude toward modeling, most of them were boys. More precisely, among those who said no: 8.33% from the mixed, 25% from girls alone school and 66,67% from boys alone school.

4.2.3- Students Understanding

As to students answers to Question 3: Did this modeling activity help you in getting better understanding in biology? If yes, why? If no, why not? (understanding).

Their answers were as follows (fig 31):

Fig 31: % of students in understanding sub scale

81.43% of the students answered yes while 18.57% answered no. So most of the students showed a better understanding after modeling. Only few showed no progress in their understanding after modeling.

Students gave different answers to support their choices presented in fig 32, still a part didn't justify their answers.

Fig 32: % of students positive answers categories in understanding subscale

Fifty seven answered yes, their answers were listed in the following categories

: nineteen out of fifty seven had more understanding because they were practicing what they learned. While fifteen explained that in this way the information would be imprinted in their minds . Nine of the students showed more understanding because they were aware for more details in the process, while six students found it more clear than lecturing . In addition to that, four students said it was simple and easier than lecturing. Three students had more understanding because it was not the teacher who was modeling, they were modeling by themselves. While one of the students replied: I was at least thinking in this hour. While the % of students negative answers categories were presented in table 25.

Table 25: % of students negative answers categories in understanding subscale

	Frequency	Percentage
They didn't find that they made an improvement after the modeling	3	25.00%
It was confusing	3	25.00%
It didn't add anything to lecturing	2	16.67%
Didn't mention the cause	2	16.67%
Didn't like to work in groups	1	8.33%
It was a waste of time	1	8.33%

Thirteen answered no: their answers were listed in the following categories . Three out of thirteen replied by no because they didn't find that they made an improvement after modeling. While other three students found it confusing and another one didn't like to work in groups , also one student said that it was a waste of time, and two students considered that it didn't add anything to lecturing, while the other students didn't mention the cause.

The sample was very small so we couldn't generalize.

The % of students negative answers categories in understanding subscale as to their kinds of school was presented in fig 33

Fig 33: % of students negative answers categories in understanding subscale as to their kinds of school

Among those who had negative answers, most of them were girls. More precisely, among those who said no were 53.85% from girls alone school, 38.46% from boys alone school and 7.69% from the mixed so it was least from the mixed.

4.2.4- Students Enjoyment

As to students answers to Question 4: Did you find the biology hour more enjoying while modeling? If yes, why? If no, why not? (attitude enjoyment).

Their answers were as follows (fig 34):

Fig 34: % of students in enjoyment subscale

- 90.00% of the students answered yes while 10.00% answered no. So most of the students showed more enjoyment after modeling, only few showed no increase in their enjoyment after modeling.

Students gave different opinions to support their answers, still a part didn't justify their choices. The % of students positive answers categories in enjoyment subscale were presented in table 26.

Table 26: % of students positive answers categories in enjoyment subscale

	Frequency	Percentage
There was group work	14	22.22%
It's not boring	11	17.46%
It was entertaining where students were playing and learning at the same time	10	15.87%
They were not just sitting and listening	9	14.29%
Didn't mention the cause	8	12.70%
It was a new non traditional method	6	9.52%
We were working for ourselves	5	7.94%

Sixty-three answered yes. Their answers were listed in the following categories. Fourteen out of sixty-three students enjoyed because there was group work while eleven students found it as not boring, also nine students enjoyed because they were not just sitting and listening, ten students found it entertaining where students were playing and learning at the

same time. In addition to that, six students enjoyed more because it was a new non traditional method while five students mentioned that they were enjoying because they were working for themselves and the other students didn't mention the cause.

While the % of students negative answers categories in enjoyment subscale were presented in fig 35.

Fig 35: % of students negative answers categories in enjoyment subscale

Seven replied no: Their answers were listed in the following categories .Three students found it time wasting while one student found it boring .One student preferred any other method other than modeling while two students did not mention the cause.

The sample was very small so we couldn't generalize.

The % of students negative answers categories in enjoyment subscale as to their kinds of school was presented in fig 36

Fig 36: % of students negative answers categories in enjoyment subscale as to their kinds of school

Among those who had negative answers, most of them were boys. More precisely, among those who replied no were none from the mixed while 71.43% from boys alone school and 28.57% from girls alone school.

4.2.5- Students leisure

As to students answers to Question 5: Do you like to make more modeling activities in biology as projects in your free time at home? (attitude leisure sub scale)

Their answers were as follows (fig 37):

Fig 37: % of students in leisure attitude subscale

- 35.71% of the students answered yes while 64.29 % answered no. Most of the students showed low leisure attitude after modeling, only few showed an increase in their leisure after modeling.

Students gave different opinions to support their answers, still a part didn't justify their choices. The result was surprising :only twenty five replied yes while forty five students replied no. The % of students positive answer categories in leisure attitude subscale were presented in table 27.

Table 27: % of students positive answer categories in leisure attitude subscale

	Frequency	Percentage
No answer	14	56.00%
Good way to understand a hard lesson	3	12.00%
Better than Homework	2	8.00%
It is exciting and helpful	2	8.00%
Knowledge about the modeled concept will be deeper	2	8.00%
Would make it only if this is marked	1	4.00%
In this way my family will have an information about the subject matter in biology	1	4.00%

Twenty five replied yes: Their answers were listed in the following categories . Three out of those found it a good way to understand a hard lesson while one student would model

only if this is marked, still one student said: " In this way also my family will have an information about the subject matter in biology. "one student found it better than homework , still two considered it exciting and helpful and other two students said that knowledge about the modeled concept will be deeper while few did not mention the cause.

While the % of students negative answer categories in leisure attitude subscale were presented in table 28.

Table 28: % of students negative answer categories in leisure attitude subscale

	Frequency	Percentage
Didn't mention the cause	21	46.67%
They have no enough time at home to make extra activities	9	20.00%
Not interested	5	11.11%
They would make modeling at home if they worked with their friends as group	4	8.89%
Didn't like such activities	2	4.44%
Prefer applications from the book	2	4.44%
It is not his hobby to model	1	2.22%
Prefer relaxation at home	1	2.22%

Forty five students answered no: most of those students didn't mention the cause. Nine out of forty five students said that they had no enough time at home to make extra activities while five were not interested, still other four students replied that they would make modeling at home only if they worked it as group work. Two students didn't like such activities and preferred applications from the book, one student mentioned that it was not his hobby to model still another one prefer relaxation at home

The sample was very small so we couldn't generalize.

The % of students positive answer categories in leisure attitude subscale as to their kinds of school were presented in fig 38

Fig 38: % of students positive answer categories in leisure attitude subscale as to their kinds of school

Among those who had positive answers, most of them were from mixed school. More precisely, among those who answered yes, 44% students were from the mixed while 32% from girls alone school and 24% from boys alone school

4.2.6- Students attitude toward the teacher

As to students answers to question 6: Do you like to have a teacher who makes modeling activities so often? If yes, why? If no, why not?(attitude toward the teacher)

Their answers were as follows (fig 39):

Fig 39: % of students in the attitude toward the teacher subscale

- 75.71% of the students replied yes while 24.29 % replied no. Most of the students showed an increase in their attitude toward the teacher after modeling. Students gave different opinions to support their answers, still a part didn't justify their choices. The % of students positive answers categories in the attitude toward the teacher subscale were presented in table 29.

Table 29: % of students positive answers categories in the attitude toward the teacher subscale

	Frequency	Percentage
Understood more with a teacher who made modeling	27	50.94%
The teacher added enjoyment to her hour	16	30.19%
Liked a teacher who used a new nontraditional way	3	5.66%
They liked the teacher who brought materials to the class	3	5.66%
They found biology with such a teacher easier and more clear	3	5.66%
I liked it because I never thought I could stay wake up in biology hours	2	3.77%
I just loved it	1	1.89%
This made the relation between the student and the teacher and between the students themselves stronger	1	1.89%

53 students replied yes: Their answers were listed in the following categories: 27 out of 53 answered yes because they understood the lesson more while 16 students said that the

teacher hour became more enjoying, 1 student replied "I just loved it" another 3 students liked it because it was a new non traditional way "we had never modeling before." 2 students replied "I liked it because I never thought I could stay wake up in biology hours, one student replied: "this made the relation between the student and the teacher and between the students themselves stronger." 3 students said yes because they liked the teacher who brought materials to her class, 3 students mentioned that they found biology with such a teacher easier and more clear.

While the % of students negative answers categories in the attitude toward the teacher subscale were presented in fig 40.

Fig 40: % of students negative answers categories in the attitude toward the teacher subscale

17 answered no: Their answers were as follows. 4 out of those 17 students preferred a teacher who explained while 5 students found it a waste of time. One student replied that he preferred technology interventions. Two other students found the hour boring still one student didn't understand with a teacher who modeled. The sample was very small so we couldn't generalize. The % of students negative answers categories in the attitude toward the teacher subscale as to their kinds of school were presented in the fig 41.

Fig 41: % of students negative answers categories in the attitude toward the teacher subscale as to their kinds of school

Among those who had negative answers, most of them were from boys alone school. More precisely, among those who answered no, none from the mixed said no so we suppose that their attitude toward the teacher should improve while students who gave negative answers were 58.82% from boys alone school and 41.18% from girls alone school.

4.2.7- Students attitude toward the learning environment

As to students answers to question 7: How was the relation with your friends while modeling? (attitude toward the learning environment).

Their answers were as follows (fig 42):

■ Positive relation ■ Negative relation

Fig 42: % of students in the attitude toward learning environment subscale

- 91.43% of the students showed positive relation while 8.57% showed a negative relation. Most of the students showed an increase in their attitude toward learning environment after modeling. Students gave different opinions to support their answers, still a part didn't justify their choices.

While the % of students negative answers categories in their attitude toward learning environment subscale were presented in table 30.

Table 30: % of students negative answers categories in their attitude toward learning environment subscale

	Frequency	Percentage
I just didn't like everything	1	16.67%
It's a noisy and disturbing hour	1	16.67%
The relation with friends is still negative	1	16.67%
The modeling was not serious	1	16.67%
No true cooperative work	1	16.67%
Didn't mention why	1	16.67%

- 64 students found it positive relation while only 6 students considered it negative relation: one student replied: "I just didn't like everything." While another found it a noisy and disturbing hour while one student commented that his relation with his friends improve but

his relation with the teacher was still negative. 1 student replied the modeling was not serious , and another replied that there was no true cooperative work.

While the % of students negative answers categories in their attitude toward learning environment subscale as to their kinds of school were presented in fig 43

Fig 43: % of students negative answers categories in their attitude toward learning environment subscale as to their kinds of school

Among those who had negative answers were: none from the mixed while 33.33% were from the girls alone and 66.67% were from the boys alone school .

4.2.8- Students Self Efficacy

As to students answers to question 8: Did you find yourself a good biology learner during this modeling activity? If yes, why? If no, why not? (Self Efficacy) Their answers were as follows (fig 44):

Fig 44: % of students in self efficacy subscale

- 75.71% of the students answered yes while 24.29% answered no. So most of the students showed an increase in self efficacy after modeling. Only few showed no progress. Students gave different opinions to support their answers, still a part didn't justify their choices.

The % of students positive answers categories in their self efficacy subscale were presented in fig 45.

Fig 45: % of students positive answers categories in their self efficacy subscale

- 53 answered yes: Their results were as follows: 33 out of them commented that they understood more. Two students said yes because in this way they would never forget what they learned, six students said yes because they liked it, three students because they were practicing, three students replied that it caught their attention all the time.

- 17 answered no: Their results were as follows. Three students out of them replied no because they didn't like modeling . The other five students said no because they didn't like biology, four students said no because modeling didn't cause their progress, while one student replied that it was hard to model.

The % of students negative answers categories in their self efficacy subscale as to their kinds of school were as follows (fig 46)

Fig 46: % of students negative answers categories in their self efficacy subscale as to their kinds of school

The sample was very small so we couldn't generalize. Among those who had negative answers, most of them were from boys alone school. More precisely, among those who said no, 5.88% from the mixed, 41.18% from the girls alone school and 52.94% from the boys alone school.

4.2.9- Students reflection on this modeling activity

As to students answers to question 9: What are the things that you would like to change in this modeling activity? (students reflection on this modeling activity)

Their answers were as follows (fig 47):

Fig 47: % of students in reflection subscale

- 69.35% of the students replied by " nothing" while 30.65% wanted to make changes. Students gave different opinions to support their answers, still a part didn't justify their choices.

While the % of students who didn't like to change any materials on this modeling activity as to their kinds of school were as follows (fig.48)

Fig 48: % of non reflecting students as to their kinds of school

- 43 students said nothing to be changed , majority of those were from the mixed school (37.21% from the mixed while 30.23% from the girls alone and 32.56% from the boys alone).

The % of students answers categories in the reflection subscale were as follows (fig 49)

Fig 49: % of students answers categories in the reflection subscale

While 19 students wanted to make changes: three students recommended more time for these modeling activities, six students recommended changing the materials. While two recommended more extra notes while modeling, five students recommended to change it all, other two students preferred to cancel and make lab or dissection instead, still one student recommended organized group work.

CHAPTER V

DISCUSSION OF THE RESULTS

The section below discusses the results of the present study. This discussion is divided into eight sections, each related to one of the eight research questions. The results will be compared to the findings of the literature. Thus, they will be confirmed, refuted, or added to existing data.

5.1- Effect of modeling on the achievement of Lebanese students :

- Discussion for the First Research Hypothesis :

Research Hypothesis # 1: There's significant variation among students who received instruction with modeling activities and those who received instruction with traditional method in terms of achievement in favor of those who modeled.

The post-test results indicated that students in the modeling group achieved significantly higher than students in the traditional group. Experimental students showed a more sig increase in their total test marks than the control (% of var:21.99%, sig:0.000 for experimental while % of var:13.45%, sig:0.000 for the control). Therefore, the above results present evidence that the modeling approach improved students achievement in biology more than the traditional lecture. This could be explained by the fact that, unlike students in the traditional lecturing, students in the modeling group had room for testing and explorations with the freedom to plan their own models. The students were working more to achieve the learning objectives. So with no doubt the information will stick in their minds. These results are in line with previous modeling studies in the literature.

In the literature, biology students increased their achievement after modeling (Dori and Barak, 2001; Rao and Di Carlo,2001; Roberts et al., 2005 ; Rotbain et al.,2005; Jittivadhna et al.,2009; Pacurar and Tirla,2009; Jittivadhna et al.,2010; Breckler et al.,2013; Haugwitz and Sandmann,2010; Chabalengula &Mumba,2012; Breckler et al.,2013). In addition to that, Rotbain et al.(2005) analysis of the post-tests showed that the mean score of the experimental group was significantly higher than that of the control group. In the study of Pacurar and Tirla(2009), the experimental group students

average has grown significantly ,and Haugwitz and Sandmann (2010) students pre-test average score was 51% whereas post-test score improved to 64%. Moreover, Jittivadhna et al.(2010) findings showed that in the post test the majority of students who modeled had correct answers for all questions in the multiple choice questionnaire. In contrary to the previous studies that showed an increase in achievement after implementing models, Resnick and Omanson (as cited in Goldstone and Son,2005) , and Rotbain et al.(2006) and Harris et al.(2009) studies didn't show that students increase their achievement after modeling. Rotbain et al.(2006) claimed that the multiple-choice questions did not measure the depth of understanding of protein synthesis gained by the students in the experimental group. Moreover , Harris et al.(2009) reported that differences between the experimental and control group students were only revealed during students interviews.

5.1.1- Discussion Students Achievement in Acquired knowledge Domain:

As to the acquired knowledge part in the post test, our results illustrated that the majority of students in the modeling group developed higher acquired knowledge. Experimental students showed increase in A domain but it was not sig (% of var:3.13% with sig0.368>0.05)while those Control group students showed a significant decrease in their acquired knowledge(% of var:-6.58% ,sig:0.041). Students in the experimental group were applying the steps .This means that executing all steps in an activity provide students in the modeling group the ability to think through the steps being used in the activity. This will increase their knowledge retention leading to an increase in their acquired knowledge in the tests. By comparing to literature, our results contradict with Mensch and Ruba (1991) results that showed no differences in achievement in acquired knowledge.

5.1.2- Discussion Students Achievement in Reasoning Domain:

In our study, both control and experimental groups students showed a significant increase in reasoning, control group (% of var:133.68%,, sig:0.000) while experimental students (127.53% with sig0.000). So modeling has neutral effect on their scientific reasoning. One can't deduce that modeling leads to an increase in reasoning . These modeling activities weren't mainly inquiry based so they werenot supposed to increase the reasoning .

In addition, students in this group did not have a lot of chance to test their own thinking and reflect on their own ideas. All these might have affected their reasoning ability. Our students didn't show increase in reasoning, this contradicts with the results of Clark and Mathis (2000) , Schwarz and Gwekwerere (2007), and Breckler et al.(2013) . In their activity, Schwarz and Gwekwerere (2007) and Breckler et al.(2013) using of models stimulated questioning and built scientific skills that enhanced students constructivist elements of active learning .

5.1.3- Discussion Students Achievement in Communication Domain:

As to D domain, both experimental and control group students showed a sig decrease in their communication skills(% of var:-20.11% with sig 0.000) for experimental while (%of var:-22.31% ,sig:0.000) for control. Thus, modeling didn't result in an increase in the communication skills probably because the students were not writing any summaries at the end of the modeling sessions, even they didn't give any oral description for their work. This could be also due to their low language proficiency levels which hindered expressing themselves. In contrary to our results where .modeling didn't result in students increase in communication skills, Mensch and Ruba (1991) and Rotbain et al.(2006) results showed increase in communication skills after modeling, most of their students gave accurate and detailed written descriptions of transcription and translation processes while control group students just recalled pieces of information in isolation from the protein synthesis process.

5.1.4- Discussion Students Understanding in the Open Ended Questionnaire:

Similar to the results of the post tests that showed increase in achievement, results from the second instrument (the open ended questionnaire) supported the previous results and showed that students increased their understanding after modeling. As to students answers on the contribution of models to their understanding: Most of the students showed a better understanding after modeling (81.43%), only few showed no progress in their understanding after modeling. These results are in line with the literature, Most of the students found modeling more clear and easier than lecturing. This was supported by the results of Gow & Nicholla(1988), Dori and Barak(2001), Wu and Shah (2004) , Lee (2004), Rotbain et al.(2005), Roberts et al.(2005), Rotbain et al.(2006) , Chinnici et al.(2006) ,Schwarz et al.(2007), Pacurar and Tirla(2009) ,

O'Dowd and Roca (2009) , Harris et al.(2009), Haugwitz and Sandmann(2010), Jittivadhna et al.(2010) ,Stansfield and Carlton(2011) ,Breckler and Yu (2011), and Chabalengula &Mumba(2012) who all showed that the model reinforced students' understanding and made concepts more memorable.

5.1.5- Effect of modeling on the achievement of students with Different Learning Styles(kinesthetic and non kinesthetic):

Discussion for Second Research Hypothesis:

Research Hypothesis # 2: There is significant difference between the mean scores of K (kinesthetic learners) and NK learners (non kinesthetic learners) in terms of achievement in favor of Kinesthetic learners.

In addition to the role that models play in increasing achievement in biology, many studies showed an improvement of students with different learning styles.

As to experimental group learning style, both NK and K showed a significant increase in their total marks with NK(% of var:20.90%, sig:0.000), while K showed more increase (% of var:27.57%, sig:0.000). The reason for the significance increase in achievement towards biology between the two groups (K and NK) could be attributed to the fact that this was a new teaching student centered method. Hence, both groups were interested to learn through modeling. But higher achievement was for kinesthetic learners.

This is consistent with the results of past research that showed that matching between kinesthetic method of teaching and kinesthetic students learning style will lead to more student gains(Roberts ,2002; Wu and Shah, 2004; Roberts et al., 2005; Sorby, 2005; Hawk and Shah, 2007; Di Carlo, 2008 ; Sabeh ,2009; Harris et al.,2009; Breckler and Yu ,2011; Breer et al.,2012 and Thaman et al.,2013). They considered that this method allow kinesthetic and visual learners to succeed in a classroom setting where lectures are often tailored to suit auditory learners.

In contrary to our results, the study of Di Carlo(2008) showed that all kind of learners improve noting that active participation with models can reach all types of learners (visual, auditory, kinesthetic and tactile).Similarly, Breckler and Yu (2011) findings were that very little difference existed between students who stated a K preference and those who did not.

As to reasoning domain, in our study both groups showed a significant increase in reasoning but in K more than NK,(the % of var: 163.64%, sig:0.000 for K ; % of var: 115.27%, sig 0.000 For NK). Thus, matching between kinesthetic method of teaching and kinesthetic students learning style will lead to more increase in scientific reasoning for K learners. This could be justified in that K students were thinking more through the modeling steps than the N K. In the literature, Di Carlo(2008) noted that models promoted logic and reasoning, and creativity and research oriented learning for all kinds of learners.

As to D domain, Only NK group showed a significant decrease in D(% of var:- 16.98%,sig:0.01) while in K the decrease was not significant(% of var: -19.01%, sig:0.05).Thus matching between kinesthetic method of teaching and kinesthetic students learning style didn't result in increase in the communication skills. Therefore the decrease in D is due to its decrease in K and non K sections but mainly due to its decrease in the NK.

5.1.6- Effect of modeling on the achievement of students with opposite gender:

Discussion for Third Research Hypothesis:

Research Hypothesis # 3: There's no significant difference between the mean scores of girls and boys in terms of achievement after implementing modeling .

As to experimental group gender, both male and female students showed a significant increase in their total test marks. This increase in total marks in both groups was due to the fact that students were working more for themselves. They were not just sitting and listening to the teacher. The lack of gender differences in biology achievement in this study could be explained as a determination from Lebanese girls to show that they are capable of achieving similar results as boys even more. Therefore our hypothesis was validated but female experimental students showed greater increase in their total marks(% of var.:27.89% sig:0.000) for female while (% of var.:17.39%,sig: 0.000) for male .

This is consistent with past research that showed that female achieve in biology better than male. Keeves and Kotte (as cited in Soyly, 2006) found that more females enrolled in biology in secondary school. In contrary to the above results past research also

showed that there were no significant differences between males and females aged 10, 14, and 18 for biology achievement [Soylu, 2006 ; Soyibo and Ishola (as cited in Bloomfield and Soyibo, 2008)], while Simpson and Oliver (as cited in Soylu, 2006) and Woolley (1979) showed that boys have more positive achievements than the girls across the level.

In addition to that , there was increase in both male and female group scientific reasoning(% of var :109.74%, sig 0.000 for male) and more significant increase in their scientific reasoning for female (% of var :156.20%,sig:0.000). Modeling leads to increase in reasoning mainly in female students. Male students showed decrease in their marks in A and D domains but this decrease was not significant,(for A, % of var: - 5.32%, sig 0.169>0.05; for D, % of var: -13.89%, sig 0.090>0.05). While Female students increase in their A domain but this increase was not significant, (% of var: 14.29 %, sig 0.019<0.05). Thus, modeling leads to an increase in the acquired knowledge in female students only. Female students were thinking through the modeling steps more than male students , this allowed the information to stick more in their minds and to get better results in acquired knowledge while female students showed a significant decrease in their D domain, (% of var:- 26.23%, sig:0.000). It might be that the females felt shy to express themselves or they had low language proficiency that affected the progress in their D domain. The increase in A is mainly due to its increase in female students. The decrease in D domain is due to its decrease in male and female students but mainly due to its decrease in female students.

5.1.7- Effect of modeling on the achievement of different kind of school students:

Discussion for the Fourth Research Hypothesis:

Research Hypothesis # 4: There's no significant difference between the mean scores of the different kinds of schools students in terms of achievement after implementing modeling.

As to kind of school variable in the experimental section, all mixed, boys and girls showed a significant increase in their total test marks. Therefore, our hypothesis was validated but the highest increase was for mixed (% of var.:40.33%,sig:0.000) more than girls (% of var.:20.00%,sig:0.002) which is in turn more than boys (% of var.:12.72%, sig:0.011). This is consistent with the results of Bloomfield and

Soyibo(2008) . In contrary to our results, other studies have shown that girls' schools performed better in many school subjects including science than boys' and mixed schools [e.g., Forrest (as cited in Bloomfield and Soyibo ,2008)]. While some research findings have shown that boys in all-boys' schools statistically significantly outscored students in all-girls' and mixed schools in biology (e.g., Soyibo & Pinnock, 2005). This highest increase in marks for mixed could be attributed to the fact that this boy girl interaction is a better environment for learning and leads to better achievement.

These results are in line with the open ended questionnaire where highest achievement was also found for mixed. As to the open ended questionnaire results, among those who had negative answers and showed no progress in understanding, most of them were girls(53.85%). 38.46%from boys alone school and 7.69% from the mixed so it was least from the mixed.

The three experimental sections showed a significant increase in their scientific reasoning . In mixed, (% of var.:195.59%, sig:0.000) more than girls (% of var.:138.82%, sig:0.000) which in turn more than boys(% of var.:93.25%,sig:0.000).Thus, highest increase in reasoning was for mixed. Only boys and girls sections showed a significant decrease in D(% of var.: -20.29%, sig:0.026 for boys and % of var.: -31. 71% and sig:0.000 for girls), while the decrease in D in mixed was not significant(% of var.: -5.88%, sig: 0.532>0.05). Students in the mixed also showed a significant increase in A domain with (% of var.:16.87%, sig:o.o38) while boys showed a decrease in A domain that was not significant, (% of var.: -7.58%, sig: 0.095>0.05). On the other hand, girls school increase in A domain was not significant, (% of var.: 6.97%, sig: 0.260>0.05). It could be that this boys girls interaction in the mixed that leads to better results in their acquired knowledge and as to my observation the students in the mixed were more interacting and discussing more the steps of the modeling activity. These positive results in the mixed section could be due to their modeling experience. As to the results of the open ended questionnaire, most of the students didn't have any modeling experience(72.86%).The highest percentage of those who had modeling experience were from the boys alone and mixed schools (42.11% ; 36.84%) while the lowest percentage of students with modeling experience were from the girls alone school(21.05%).

5.2- Attitude and Self Efficacy:

Effect of modeling on the attitude and self efficacy of control and experimental students:

Discussion for Fifth Research Hypothesis:

- 1- Research Hypothesis # 5: There's significant variation among students who received instruction with modeling activities and those who received instruction with traditional method in terms of attitude and self efficacy in favor of those who modeled.

As to students results from the multiple choice questionnaire, In the control, there was no significant variation in the total attitude and self efficacy after control group were post tested(% of var : 0.36%, sig :0.920 for attitude while % of var: 0.00%, sig: 0.960 for self efficacy) while in the experimental group, there was an increase in the overall attitude and self efficacy but this increase was not significant(% of var:-3.29%, sig:0.23 for attitude while % of var:-2.32%, sig:0.358 for self efficacy). Therefore our hypothesis was not validated. Thus, modeling leads to higher attitude and self efficacy but the results were not significant.

With no doubt the students attitude toward biology will be improved when the students are interacting and not just sitting and listening to the teacher. These results are in line with past research(Mensch and Ruba ,1991; French and Russell ,2001; Chinnici et al., 2004; Rotbain et al.,2005; Prokop et al.,2007 and Jittivadhna et al., 2010).

In their study, French and Russell (2001) noted that traditionally taught courses were characterized by substantial declines in attitude toward biology. Similarly, Kindfield (as cited in Chinnici et al.,2004) stated that group activities around modeling can decrease the amount of stress and negative attitude that may be associated with learning genetics. In contrary to our results, Ebenezer and Zoller (as cited in French and Russell ,2001) looked at the impact of a constructivist approach to teaching in secondary schools and found no change in attitudes that could be attributed to the change in approach.

Moreover, Nokari(1998) found that students learning science when teachers used lectures had significantly more positive attitudes.

As to each of the attitude sub scales, in both, the experimental and the control groups ,the attitude toward learning environment decrease but this decrease was more in the

control group (For control :% of var : 4.78%, sig :0.077>0.05; for experimental % of var : 3.21%, sig :0.603>0.05). Thus, modeling effect was neutral as to the attitude toward the learning environment because this decrease was found in both control and experimental sections. So, the multiple choice questionnaire didn't show that modeling increase students attitude toward the learning environment. In contrast to our results, past research showed increase in the attitude toward learning environment after modeling, (O'Dowd and Roca ,2009; Pacurar and Tirla,2009; Breckler and Yu ,2011 and Thaman et al.,2013). O'Dowd and Roca (2009) reported that these models increased students interaction and engagement. Similarly in the study of Pacurar and Tirla(2009), their experimental class showed a better collaboration between students and a higher level of involvement.

These results in the literature are in line with the results of the open ended questionnaire that contradicts with the multiple choice questionnaire. In the open ended questionnaire, students answers as to the attitude toward the learning environment were positive, (91.43% of the students showed positive relation with their friends while 8. 57% showed a negative relation considering it a noisy and disturbing hour).

However, the enjoyment subscale in the multiple choice questionnaire showed a significant increase only in the experimental section after students experienced modeling(% of var.: -7.66% , sig:0.039 while % of var: -1.87%, sig: 0.454 for control) .Thus modeling leads to more enjoyment. These results are in line with past research(Rotbain et al.,2006; Di Carlo ,2008 and O'Dowd and Roca,2009). Di Carlo (2008) and O'Dowd and Roca(2009) students showed more excitement and energy.

As to the results of the open ended questionnaire, it was in parallel with the above results. Most of the students showed more enjoyment after modeling (90.00%). Students enjoyed more because it was a new non traditional method only few showed no increase in their enjoyment after modeling. This is in line with the results of Rotbain et al.(2006) whose students enjoyed and announced that the modeling activities “broke the routine” of the traditional lecture format.

As to leisure in the multiple choice questionnaire, the leisure subscale increased in the experimental more than control but this increase was not sig. (% of var.: -3.42%, sig: 0.175>0.05 for experimental while % of var.: -2.19%; sig:0.306 >0.05 for control). Thus, modeling leads to more leisure . Of course, the students who experienced modeling at class and enjoyed it would like to go home and repeat it and talk about this

new experience to their family and friends. These results are supported by the study of Di Carlo (2008) whose students showed more leisure and enjoyment after modeling the students enjoyed taking the models home to demonstrate to friends and family “how the body works”.

This contradicts with the results of the open ended questionnaire, As to students leisure attitude after modeling, Most of the students showed low leisure attitude after modeling (64.29 %), only few showed an increase in their leisure after modeling(35.71%). Those who showed a decrease in their leisure said that they have no enough time at home to make extra activities.

As to the attitude toward the teacher in the multiple choice questionnaire, it decreased in the control(1.33% but it was not sig,sig:0.648) and it increased for the experimental(% of var.: -4.03%, but it was not significant ,sig:0.29>0.05).Thus modeling increase the attitude toward teacher. With no doubt the student prefer a teacher who gives them a little bit of freedom to be active.

As to the results of the open ended questionnaire, its results are consistent with the above results. Most of the students showed an increase in their attitude toward the teacher after modeling (75.71 %). This is aligned with the results of the study of O’Dowd and Aguilar-Roca(2009) whose students made positive comments on their teachers use of the models adding that such teacher loves what she does and puts a lot of time and effort into preparing for each lecture .

As to self efficacy, our study showed that modeling leads to higher self efficacy. Many studies are in line with our results and showed that self efficacy increased after using active methods in teaching (Elswick,1995; Fakhreddine,2003; Tuan et al ,2005; Harris et al ,2009 ; Blonder,2010 and Asha et al.,2012). Elswick(1995) stated that models help students to overcome students anxiety and to increase their sense of confidence.

Moreover, Harris et al (2009) stated that access to hand-held models would increase students’ enthusiasm and confidence . Similarly, Blonder(2010) participants enjoyed working with the teaching model showing higher attitude and self-efficacy.

Our results in the multiple choice questionnaire were supported by the results of the open ended questionnaire . As to students results from the open ended questionnaire, students increased their self efficacy after modeling: 75.71% of the students increased their self efficacy while 24.29% not. So most of the students showed an increase in self efficacy after modeling. This increase in self efficacy was expected because any student

centered method will lead to more self confidence. The students had the chance to work by themselves and to reflect into their own work. They were interested to accomplish their modeling activities, and they were busy working with the materials, enjoying and being proud for accomplishing their models. This all leads to an increase in their self efficacy.

As to students attitude toward modeling, results of the open ended questionnaire indicated that most of the students showed a positive attitude toward modeling(82.86%), only few had a negative attitude. These results are supported by past research(Jittivadhna et al.,2009; Breckler and Yu,2011). Jittivadhna et al. (2009) students responded positively to the model remarking that they preferred it to static 2D text book illustrations.

5.2.1- Effect of modeling on the attitude and self efficacy of different learning style students (kinesthetic and non kinesthetic).

Discussion for Sixth Research Hypothesis:

Research Hypothesis # 6: There is significant difference between the mean scores of K and NK learners in terms of attitude and self efficacy after implementing these hands on modeling activities in favor of K learners.

As to learning style, the experimental NK section did not show any significant variation in any of the self efficacy, attitude and all its subscales. In the NK, there was increase in enjoyment, leisure, and overall attitude but this increase was not significant while in the K section there was more increase in enjoyment, leisure, and total attitude but also not significant .(As to enjoyment, % of var: -7.88%, sig: 0.112 for NK while :% of var - 9.24%, sig: 0.057 for K. In leisure, % of var: -1.50%, sig: 0.673 for NK while % of var: -7.38%, sig: 0.115 for K. In the total attitude, % of var: -2.80%, sig: 0.419 for NK while % of var: -5.65% , sig: 0.217 for K students).Therefore, our hypothesis was not validated. Thus modeling increased the leisure, enjoyment and total attitude of K learners more than NK but the results werenot significant. So all kinds of students enjoyed but with no doubt K students will enjoy more because the method of instruction matches with their learning style. In addition to that, those kinesthetic students like to make modeling activities at home, so of course they will have higher leisure attitude. These results are consistent with past research (Harris et al.,2009 ; Breckler and Yu , 2011). For instance, Harris et al.(2009) considered that these physical models would

markedly improve the attitudes of tactile learners while having much less effect with other students .In another study, Breckler and Yu (2011) students with K preference were slightly more enthusiastic in their responses than others.

As to attitude toward learning environment, there was decrease in the NK section but this decrease was also not significant (% of var.6.93 %, sig:0.434) while the experimental K section showed none significant increase (% of var.-3.63%, sig:0.606).Thus matching between the learning and teaching styles has positive effect on students attitude toward the learning environment. With no doubt, kinesthetic students will interact and will be engaged more in this kinesthetic modeling activity showing more cooperation with their friends than NK due to matching between teaching and learning style. This all lead to a higher attitude toward the learning environment. This is in line with studies that showed students favoring kinesthetic (i.e., hands-on) learning might be more engaged in their learning when a modeling activity is used. (Wu and Shah, 2004; Roberts et al., 2005; Sorby, 2005; Breckler and Yu ,2011). In Breckler and Yu (2011) study, students who have a preference for kinesthetic learning increased their engagement leading to a higher attitude toward the learning environment while in Breer et al.(2012) study , this teaching method allowed engagement of students with all learning approaches.

In our results, NK showed more increase in their attitude toward the teacher (% of var.- 7.96%, sig: 0.074) and self efficacy (% of var.- 2.67%, sig: 0.368)than K but this increase was not significant.(% of var: -0.40%, sig: 0.970 for the attitude toward the teacher in K students; % of var -0.47%, sig: 0.912 for self efficacy in K students)

So matching between the teaching style of the teacher and learning style of students didn't seem to have an effect on students attitude toward the teacher and their self efficacy. It could be the duration of the intervention was not enough to induce a significant increase in self efficacy or attitude toward the teacher. This contradicts with the results of Tuan et al. (2005) who indicated that after their intervention, 8th graders students' self efficacy for the four different learning styles of students increased significantly without any difference between them. In contrary to our study, Thaman et al. (2013) reported that while modeling all kinds of students increased their attitude toward the teacher and felt the teacher like a friend.

5.2.2- Effect of modeling on the attitude and self efficacy of opposite gender students:

Discussion for Seventh Research Hypothesis:

Research Hypothesis # 7: There's no significant difference between the mean scores of girls and boys in terms of attitude and self efficacy after implementing modeling.\

As to gender, the experimental male section did not show any significant variation in any of the attitude and self efficacy subscales(% of var : 0.00%,sig: 0.950 for attitude while % of var: 4.10%, sig: 0.334 for self efficacy).There was increase in enjoyment and leisure but it was not significant(% of var: -2.60%, sig: 0.662 for enjoyment while % of var: -6.34%, sig: 0.117 for leisure.), while the experimental female section showed a significant increase in enjoyment (% of variation:-12.54%,sig:0.002)and a sig increase in the overall attitude and self efficacy,(% of var:.-6.72% sig:0.038 for attitude while % of var:-9.27% ,sig:0.001 for self efficacy). Therefore, our hypothesis was not validated. This could be attributed to the fact that as to the researcher's observation, boys teacher did not seem to mind the high level of noise in the classroom. This climate could have affected negatively boys attitudes towards biology and caused them to have lower scores than girls. As for girls, the teacher was managing the classroom properly, making sure to keep students on-task, which could have encouraged girls to participate more in class and have better attitudes towards biology. Those results are in line with the results of the open ended questionnaire because most of those who had negative attitude toward modeling were boys. Among those who had negative attitude toward modeling, most of them were boys (66.67%), while only 8.33%from the mixed, and 25% from girls alone school . This negative attitude toward this new method in the boys might affect their attitude in biology and lead to its decrease.

As to the attitude toward the teacher subscale, experimental male section showed none significant decrease (% of var.1.12%, sig:0.838) while female section showed a none significant increase with (% of var.-8.96%, sig:0.094). The increase in the attitude toward the teacher subscale is mainly due to its increase in the female section. Our results are in line with the results of the study of Prokop et al.(2007) that revealed that biology is somewhat more attractive to females compared to males but this effect of gender was not significant. In contrast to our study, Other studies indicated no difference between males and females attitude [Seymour and

Hewitt (as cited in French and Russell ,2001)], or more positive attitudes for boys[Shaw and Doan (as cited in French and Russell ,2001); Simpson & Oliver (as cited in Soylu, 2006)] . Similarly in their study Seymour and Hewitt (as cited in French and Russell, 2001) reported that female students are more likely to abandon the sciences as a major than their male counterparts and suggested the use of student centered pedagogies to balance this gender gap. In another study, students' attitudes toward biology improved for almost all student groups regardless of sex (French and Russell ,2001) while Usak et al.(2009) findings in contrary to our expectations , did not support the idea that females prefer biology more than males. Moreover ,Our study contradicts with previous Lebanese studies that studied attitude. In Lebanon, Raad(1997) found that males and females didn't differ in their attitude while Nokari (1998) found that males had more positive attitudes toward science than females.

As to self efficacy, the experimental male section did not show any significant variation in self efficacy (% of var: 4.10%, sig: 0.334) while the experimental female section showed a significant increase in self efficacy (% of var:-9.27% , sig:0.001). In contrary to our results, a review of the literature showed either no gender difference in self efficacy (Al-Abed,1998;Nicolaidou and Philippou, 2003) or lower self efficacy for girls(DeBacker & Nelson, 2000) while in the study of Pajares & Graham (as cited in Nicolaidou and Philippou, 2003), boys and girls reported equal self efficacy during elementary school, but, by high school, boys are more confident than girls .

As to the attitude toward the learning environment sub scale, experimental male section showed none significant decrease (% of var.9.83%, sig:0.352) while female section showed a none significant increase with (% of var.-4.50%, sig:0.321). It seems that this cooperation between girls helped them to get over their shyness, share their friends and help each other. This all lead to an increase in their attitude toward their learning environment. These positive and better results with the female students were expected especially because as to the researcher observation in the boys classes there was a lot of mess and the boys didn't take it seriously and as to their results in the open ended questionnaire they found modeling childish and would prefer technology interventions and changing the materials. In addition to that, as to students reflection on this modeling activity, the open ended questionnaire results showed that most of the students replied that they wouldn't like to change anything in this modeling activity(69.35%). Majority

of those who didn't like to change anything were from the mixed (37.21%,) while 30.23% from the girls alone and(32.56%)from the boys alone. These results are in line with Clark and Mathis (2000) whose students valued the materials and found it purposeful , creative , and worthwhile . Only30.65% of the students wanted to make changes recommending more time for these modeling activities, changing the materials, organizing the group work and adding more detailed notes while modeling.

5.2.3- Effect of modeling on the attitude and self efficacy of different kind of school students:

Discussion for Last Research Hypothesis:

Research Hypothesis # 8: There's no significant difference between the mean scores of different kinds of schools students in terms of attitude and self efficacy after implementing modeling .

The experimental mixed section and the boys alone section didn't show any significant variation in the self efficacy, attitude and all its subscales There was increase in enjoyment and leisure but not significant (For boys , self efficacy: % of var: 6.02 %; sig:0.233>0.05; attitude : % of var: 1.42%; sig:0.783>0.05; enjoyment : % of var: -2.56%; sig:0.736>0.05;leisure: % of var: -7.08%; sig:0.143>0.05;attitude toward the teacher: % of var: 6.04%; sig:0.341>0.05;attitude toward learning environment: % of var: 12.60%; sig:0.325>0.05 ;while for mixed there was increase in enjoyment and self efficacy but not significant (for enjoyment :% of var: -0.40% , sig:0.943>0.05; for self efficacy: :% of var: -4.00%; sig:0.360>0.05) while no significant variation in attitude and its other sub scales(for attitude: % of var: 0.81%, sig:0.891>0.05 ; leisure: % of var: 1.77%, sig:0.756>0.05; attitude toward the teacher: % of var: 1.14% ,sig:0.836>0.05;attitude toward learning environment :% of var: 0.53% , sig:0.965>0.05).while girls self efficacy increased significantly after modeling (% of var:-10.38%, sig:0.001). This contradicts with the study of Nokari (1998) who found that students in mixed schools had more positive attitudes toward science than students in single-sex schools. These results are consistent with results from the second instrument. As to the results of the open ended questionnaire, Among those who had low self efficacy, most of them were from boys alone school (52.94% from the boys alone school). As to experimental girls alone school, there was significant increase in enjoyment (% of var: -18.43% sig:0.000). Thus there was more increase in the

enjoyment subscale for girls. This is also in line with results from the second instrument. As to the results of the open ended questionnaire, a very low number of students didn't enjoy and found it time wasting and boring. Among those who didn't enjoy, most of them were boys (71.43%). More precisely, among those who didn't enjoy were none from the mixed and 28.57% from girls alone school.

As to experimental girls alone school, there was a significant increase in the attitude toward the teacher (% of var:-18.21% sig:0.005). Thus more increase in the attitude toward the teacher in the female sections. As to the results of the open ended questionnaire, those with negative attitude toward the teacher most of them were from boys alone school (58.82%) and preferred a teacher who explained finding it a waste of time, boring and preferred technology interventions. More precisely, among those who showed low attitude toward the teacher were none from the mixed so we suppose that their attitude toward the teacher should improve and 41.18% were from girls alone school.

In addition to that, the girls showed a significant increase in the overall attitude scale (% of var: -11.70% sig:0.001). Therefore, our hypothesis was not validated. Also, girls leisure and attitude toward learning environment increase but this increase was not significant,(for leisure: % of var: -2.39% , sig:0.421>0.05 ;for attitude toward learning environment: % of var: -7.69% ,sig:0.166>0.05).

This is in line with the results of the second instrument. As to the results of the open ended questionnaire, among those who had positive answers and increased their leisure, most of them were from girls alone school and mixed while least were from boys alone school(44.00% for mixed school, 32.00% for girls alone school while 24.00% were from boys alone school).

As to the results of the open ended questionnaire, most of those who showed decrease in their attitude toward the learning environment were from boys alone school (66.67%,). None from the mixed showed decrease in their attitude toward the learning environment while 33.33% were from the girls alone school.

These positive results in the female classes as to my observation were due to their suffering with their traditional teacher so they appreciated this modeling activity a lot and the low achievers among them who were daydreaming with their teachers

traditional talk chalk method were interacting with their friends during modeling and they were discussing their ideas. This all lead to their increase in their self efficacy .Moreover, Their attitude toward the teacher improved after the teacher changed her method . Thus the increase in attitude and self efficacy was mainly due to its increase in the female sections.

CHAPTER VI

CONCLUSION

This chapter summarizes the findings of the present study, makes several conclusions, points out the limitations, discusses pedagogical implications for students and teachers and finally proposes recommendations for further investigation and research.

5.1- Summary of Major Findings:

The results of our study present evidence that the modeling approach improves students achievement in biology more than the traditional lecture. Going further, students were assessed in which domain they showed progress. Students in the modeling group developed higher acquired knowledge. Thus, modeling increased students acquired knowledge. For both reasoning and communication domains, modeling didn't result in any increase in these domains.

In addition to that, taking students learning style into consideration and matching between kinesthetic method of teaching and kinesthetic students learning style lead to more student gains. Kinesthetic students showed more increase in test marks. More precisely, more increase in scientific reasoning for K learners but didn't result in increase in acquired knowledge or communication skills.

Moreover, as to their gender and kind of school, all groups showed improvement but female experimental students showed a greater increase in their total marks. In the reasoning and acquired knowledge domains, modeling lead to increase in reasoning and acquired knowledge mainly in female students while the decrease in communication domain was due to its decrease in male and female students . In the different kinds of schools, the highest increase in achievement was for mixed schools. Students in the mixed also showed a significant increase in acquired knowledge and reasoning domains while the decrease in D domain in the experimental was mainly due its decrease in boys and girls sections.

On the other hand, the results of the effect of modeling on students attitude and self efficacy were as follows:

The modeling approach led to higher attitude and self efficacy but the results were not significant. In addition to that, most of the students showed a positive attitude toward modeling. Going further into the attitude subscales. Modeling increased students attitude toward teacher and led to more leisure and enjoyment but in the open ended questionnaire leisure was lesser. The modeling effect was neutral as to the attitude toward the learning environment in the multiple choice questionnaire while modeling increases students attitude toward the learning environment in the open ended questionnaire. So further research is required to investigate these two issues.

By taking into consideration students learning style, results showed that modeling increased the leisure, enjoyment and total attitude of K learners more than NK but the results were not significant. Also this matching between the learning and teaching has positive effect on students attitude toward the learning environment while it didn't seem to have an effect on students attitude toward the teacher and their self efficacy.

Considering students gender and kind of school, the experimental female students showed more enjoyment and a more significant increase in the overall attitude and self efficacy and a higher attitude toward the teacher and the learning environment. Thus, the increase in the attitude toward the teacher subscale is mainly due to its increase in the female section

As to their Kind of school: The experimental mixed section and the boys alone section didn't show any significant variation in the self efficacy, attitude and all its subscales. While in girls section, The attitude and self efficacy increased significantly after modeling and there was more increase in the enjoyment, in the attitude toward the teacher, leisure and attitude toward learning environment subscales.

5.2- Limitations

This study has several limitations. First, the sample for the present study (151 participants) was small. It was drawn from three schools only. Therefore, the subjects of this study are not representative of all Lebanese Grade 11 students. Thus, the ability to generalize the results of this experiment to the population from which the sample was drawn will be questionable. In addition to that, the sample was from different areas from Beirut, Baabda and Aley and it was taught by three different teachers. Moreover the traditional groups were working individually while the experimental worked

cooperatively and the time as two months intervention and covering just one science unit was not sufficient then it might not be generalized to other science units. Second, the present study was based on reporting the learning style on VAK questionnaire, it was better to use other models of learning style which are more valid. Third, The open ended questionnaire contained just one question to measure each subscale. We couldn't refer to the results of the open ended questionnaire since only one question for each subscale and we are referring to it just to support the results of our multiple choice questionnaire

In the light of the above results the following recommendations are made:

5.3- Recommendations for Practice:

Researchers (Van Driel & Verloop, 2002) stated that most teachers do not realize the value of using models in science teaching, and do not know how to effectively engage their students in modeling. In addition, there is a problem in the lack of existing information, frameworks, and structures for guiding teachers in engaging learners in model-based inquiry practices (Schwarz and Gwekwerere, 2007). Lebanon is not an exception. Therefore it is recommended that the Ministry of Education and Higher Education (MEHE) in Lebanon give teachers the opportunity to participate in workshops regarding the nature of modeling and the different models that teachers can use in their classes depending on the class level. Those workshops and meetings make it easier for teachers to plan and implement modeling activities. The MEHE should also help teachers by providing guidelines for modeling activities and ready-made activities that are ready to be implemented in class or by incorporating modeling activities at the end of each activity in our books. In addition to that, there should be more time allocation given for biology so that teachers can spend more time in these modeling activities.

Moreover, it is recommended that the schools provide the teachers with all the physical amenities needed for modeling activities. Furthermore, Windschitl et al. (as cited in Chabalengula & Mumba, 2012). argued that a few science teachers who employ models tend to use them as end-products of inquiry rather than as tools to help students explain and generate knowledge about concepts being illustrated at any point in the inquiry. The problem lies in classroom practice which typically uses models for communication of (finalized) ideas. Therefore, it is

recommended that students use models as tools to help them generate their own knowledge about a science concept. This would ensure that young students are involved in generating knowledge by manipulating models other than just being told the answers by the teachers.

Science teachers should be promoting Biological Knowledge Generation using Model-Based Inquiry Instruction .They should be aware of teaching strategies that qualify the inquiry science teaching such as models.

On the other hand, Frankel (2009) sound a note of caution reporting that many training programs lack effectiveness because teaching methods do not match individuals' learning styles. So increased awareness of learning styles should be a part of teacher training development. Teachers should investigate both their teaching styles and students' learning styles and attempt to match both as much as possible. It is recommended that teachers present new information and material in different ways and use a variety of activities that cater to various learning styles. In other words, they should strive for a balanced teaching style that accommodates multiple learning styles. . To accommodate the Visual learners in class, use videos while for auditory learners, use class discussions , lectures, peer tutoring, and give oral explanation and instructions ,on the other hand encourage hands-on work and using of models for kinesthetic learners.

On the basis of our findings, we conclude that it is worthwhile for teachers to integrate physical model activities in the teaching of biological phenomena .Our recommendation is also in harmony with the growing emphasis on integrating models in science education (Gilbert & Boulter, 1998; Van Driel & Verloop, 2002). This modeling method kept up students positive attitude and led to higher achievement and self efficacy. The difference between males and females and between students in mixed, male ,and female schools and between students with different learning styles need to be considered by teachers. If our aim is to educate all students we need to help them all irrespective of their learning style and gender to develop positive attitude and higher achievement.

5.4- Recommendations for Future Research

Students who received modeling instruction in this study were rarely exposed to modeling prior to this study. It is possible that with on-going involvement in modeling the same learners would be more academically successful. Over the long run, modeling

might have a more positive influence on students' academic achievement. It is recommended that this same study to be carried out for a longer period of time and on a larger sample, including many schools, many classes, and many teachers. Any such large-scale study should moreover investigate the effects of modeling on lower- and higher-classes.

It is possible that students had positive attitudes towards it since it was almost a new methodology with respect to them. In order to be sure whether this is true or not, another study should be conducted where students have an on-going exposure to modeling. This study should be a longitudinal study to investigate modeling effect on students' attitudes towards biology and knowledge retention over time.

Moreover, in our study, results differ between the two instruments (multiple choice and open ended questionnaires) regarding modeling effect on students leisure and their attitude toward learning environment. So, further research should be done to investigate these two issues. Another study should be conducted where modeling activities are inquiry based where students make more revision for their model and reflection on the materials to be used. In addition to that, more research could be done to study the effect of modeling activities on changing students learning styles.

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WWW.LessonPlanInc.com

<http://Teach.Genetics.Utah.edu>

<http://www.vark-learn.com/english/page.asp>

Appendix I: Teacher's Interview

- 1- What are your practices to make your students active in your classroom?
- 2- Do you think modeling is a beneficial informative tool?
- 3- Do you like to try modeling with your students?
- 4- Have you ever made a modeling activity for your students before? If not, what are the reasons?
- 5- Do you consider modeling a waste of time?
- 6- Is there any suggestion that you can give for this modeling activity to make it better?

- As to teachers methodology, all teachers replied that they rarely make practices to make their students active in the classroom.

- As to teachers modeling experience, all teachers had never made a modeling activity for their students before because they didn't know how to model and what materials to use. The boys teacher added that she only used ready made models which are end products and not made by the students.

- As to teachers attitude toward modeling, all teachers in the three schools replied that they like to try it with their students .

- As to teachers awareness of the importance of modeling, the three teachers consider modeling a beneficial and interesting informative tool, mixed school teacher said:"students never forget what they make by their hands."The boy teacher argued that in the traditional way the concept might not reach all students so the teacher has to change in her methodology." The girls teacher emphasized its importance too. In addition to that, all teachers didn't consider it a time waste, adding that it might be time consuming that makes hard to be applied in this packed curriculum.

Appendix II: Student's Attitude , Self Efficacy and Learning Style Questionnaire

Dear students,

The following questionnaire will be used to identify students' attitude and self-efficacy toward biology, and their learning style. We hope that the results of the study will contribute to the improvement of both teachers and students performance in Biology Class.

All the information that you provide will be kept strictly confidential.

Introduction

This questionnaire is divided into four sections. The first section requests personal information. The second section consists of 20 questions. This section gives information on students attitude toward biology. The third section consists of 10 questions that request students self efficacy toward biology. While the last section consists of 15 questions to identify students learning style. **Time: 25-30minutes**

Section I: personal Information

- Date:..... -Name of School:.....
- Name of Student:.....
- Gender: Female..... Male :.....
- Grade level :..... section:.....
- Name of Biology teacher:.....

Section II: Measuring Students' attitude toward Biology

This section contains statements about attitudes toward biology. There is no right or wrong answers. This is not a test and only your opinion is what is wanted. All answers should be given on the separate answer sheet. Please do NOT write on this booklet. For each statement, draw a circle around SA if you Strongly Agree. A if you Agree with the statement. N if you are not sure or neither agree or Disagree. D if you Disagree . SD if you strongly Disagree.

- 1- 1-I would enjoy school more if there were no biology.
- 2- I would like to do science experiments at home.
- 3- I like my biology teacher.
- 4- I like to participate in our biology class.
- 5- I would like to have biology lessons more often
- 6- I dislike making biology projects after school
- 7- My biology teacher makes the learning environment enjoying by using different methods.
- 8- I like to express my opinions and thoughts in our biology class.
- 9- I dislike biology lessons
- 10- Doing biology activities is one of my hobbies.

- 11- There is a friendly relationship with our teacher.
- 12- I like to share my ideas and learn from my friends.
- 13- Biology is the subject that I enjoyed most
- 14- I spend my free time in biology activities
- 15- My teacher is my personal model; if I teach I would like to work like her.
- 16- I like to work with my friends in groups in biology class.
- 17- During biology lessons, I am bored.
- 18- I often discuss biology matters with my friends and with members of my family .
- 19- I don't like the way that biology is being taught by our teacher.
- 20- I prefer to work alone in biology class.

Section III- Measuring Students Self Efficacy toward Biology. The items 21-30 measures students self-efficacy. Use the same scale as above on the answer sheet.

- 21- I usually help my friends to understand biology.
- 22- Whether the biology content is difficult or easy, I'm sure that I can understand it.
- 23- No matter how much effort I put, I can't learn biology.
- 24- I think I'm a good biology learner.
- 25- I need extra help from a teacher or from students in biology.
- 26- Trying to understand biology is a waste of time.
- 27- When biology activities are difficult, I give up or only do the easy part.
- 28- During science activities, I prefer to ask other students for the answer rather than think for myself.
- 29- Biology is one of the easiest courses for me.
- 30- I don't have any idea about how to go about learning biology.

Section IV: VAK Learning Styles Questionnaire

Dear participant, the purpose of this questionnaire is to figure out your favorite learning style. Therefore, we would like you to answer the following questions as accurately as possible .For each of the questions below select either "a" or "b" or "c" to indicate your answer. Please choose only one answer for each question. If both "a" and "b" or "c" seem to apply to you, choose the one that applies more frequently.

1. When I am doing a lab exercise, I generally prefer to:
 - a) read the lab book
 - b) listen to an explanation from one of my friends
 - c) go ahead and do it by myself

2. When I need directions for solving an exercise, I generally prefer to:
 - a) look at the instructions (given information)
 - b) ask my friends for an explanation.
 - c) go ahead and try to solve it by myself

3. If the teacher asked me to explain something to my friends, I tend to:
 - a) write instructions down for them on the board
 - b) give them a verbal explanation (explain to them)
 - c) demonstrate (act it in front of them)

4. When I am learning, I prefer most:
 - a) watching what the teacher is doing
 - b) discussing with the teacher what I'm supposed to do
 - c) try it myself

5. When I am studying, I most often:
 - a) concentrate on the words or the pictures in front of me
 - b) discuss and study at loud voice.
 - c) move around a lot while studying

6. I prefer lessons where we can:
 - a) look at something as picture
 - b) discuss things
 - c) we can do something practical

7. When I was a child, I liked most to:
 - a) watch a story on the TV
 - b) hear a story on the radio
 - c) act a story with my friends on stage

8. I prefer teachers who:

- a) write the explanation on the board
- b) read for us extra notes to copy
- c) make for us a lot of lab sessions and modeling activities

9. I remember things best by:

- a) writing notes
- b) saying them aloud or repeating words in my head
- c) doing and practicing the activity

10. When learning a new skill I prefer to :

- a) Watch someone else show me how to make it.
- b) Have someone to explain to me how to do it
- c) Get on with it by doing it myself.

11. If I want to build a physical model I prefer to :

- a) follow the picture in the book
- b) Have someone to read instructions to me how to do it
- c) work it out alone by trying different ways in building it

12. My preferred hobby is:

- a) watching TV
- b) listening to the radio
- c) playing outside

13. I prefer the lesson most when teachers:

- a) show us animation and PowerPoint.
- b) make discussions with us.
- c) allow us to make models

14. I prefer

- a) teachers who draw diagrams on the board
- b) teachers who explain a lot
- c) get us to do something

15. When I am recalling what happened in class, I remember what the teacher:

- a) write in class
- b) say in class
- c) get us to do in class

Thank you for responding the questions.

ANSWER SHEET

Section I: personal Information

-Date:..... Student number:.....

-Name of School:.....

-Name of Student:.....

-Gender: Female..... Male :.....

Grade level :.....section:.....

- Name of Biology teacher:.....

Please answer as honestly as you can. For the attitude and selfefficacy section , circle one of these possible answers. SA= Strongly Agree, A= Agree, N= Neither agree nor disagree, D= Disagree, SD= Strongly Disagree.

For the learning style section , answer by a, b, or c.

Note: circle one and only one answer. If you changed your mind, cross the item and circle another

<u>Sections 2 and 3: Attitude + Self Efficacy questionnaire</u>					<u>Section IV: Learning Style</u>								
1- SA	A	N	D	SD	16- SA	A	N	D	SD	2.1	a	b	c
2- SA	A	N	D	SD	17- SA	A	N	D	SD	2.2	a	b	c
3- SA	A	N	D	SD	18- SA	A	N	D	SD	2.3	a	b	c
4- SA	A	N	D	SD	19- SA	A	N	D	SD	2.4	a	b	c
5- SA	A	N	D	SD	20- SA	A	N	D	SD	2.5	a	b	c
6- SA	A	N	D	SD	21- SA	A	N	D	SD	2.6	a	b	c
7- SA	A	N	D	SD	22- SA	A	N	D	SD	2.7	a	b	c
8- SA	A	N	D	SD	23- SA	A	N	D	SD	2.8	a	b	c
9- SA	A	N	D	SD	24- SA	A	N	D	SD	2.9	a	b	c
10- SA	A	N	D	SD	25- SA	A	N	D	SD	2.10	a	b	c
11- SA	A	N	D	SD	26- SA	A	N	D	SD	2.11	a	b	c

12-SA	A	N	D	SD	27-SA	A	N	D	SD	2.12	a	b	c
13-SA	A	N	D	SD	28-SA	A	N	D	SD	2.13	a	b	c
14-SA	A	N	D	SD	29-SA	A	N	D	SD	2.14	a	b	c
15-SA	A	N	D	SD	30-SA	A	N	D	SD	2.15	a	b	c

Appendix III-

Biology achievement Pretest:

List Of Objectives:

- 1- The students should be able to define replication.
- 2- The students should be able to list the molecules that compose the DNA polymer.
- 3- The students should be able to indicate the characteristics of mitosis.
- 4- The students should be able to indicate the number and types of chromosomes in a human somatic cell.
- 5- The students should be able to define a karyotype.
- 6- The students should be able to calculate the number of cells obtained after three mitotic divisions.
- 7- The students should be able to compare between the cells which have replicated their DNA and those which are just about to begin mitosis
- 8- The student should be able to recognize a diploid cell.
- 9- The students should be able to specify the characteristics of a diploid cell.
- 10- The student should be able to calculate the percentage of thymine from a DNA specimen that contains a specific percentage of guanine.
- 11- The student should be able to identify the type of bonds that hold the two DNA strands together.
- 12- The students should be able to name the process that leads to the formation of a chromosome of two chromatids from a chromosome of one chromatid.
- 13- The student should be able to describe the experimental steps of Taylor's experiment.
- 14- The students should be able to formulate a hypothesis concerning the mode of DNA replication.
- 15- The students should be able to interpret the consequences of ultra violet radiation on DNA replication.

Pretest Format:

Please, do not write on these papers, write your answers on an extra paper

I- Answer the following multiple choice questions: Circle 1 answer only.

1. Replication is when...

- a) proteins are made
- b) RNA is made from the DNA template
- c) another copy of DNA is made
- d) DNA is made from the RNA template

2. DNA is an organic polymer (a big molecule) composed of monomers (building blocks) called...

- a) amino acids
- b) nucleic acids
- c) nucleotides
- d) phospholipids

3. Mitosis:

- (a) divides the nucleus and distributes identical sets of chromosomes to daughter nuclei,
- (b) divides the cytoplasm producing two genetically identical daughter cells,
- (c) divides the total chromosome number of the cell by one-half,
- (d) choices "a" and "b" are both correct

4 What number and types of chromosomes are found in a human somatic cell?

- a) 44 autosomes and 2 sex chromosomes
- b) 22 autosomes and 1 sex chromosome
- c) 45 autosomes and 1 sex chromosome
- d) 21 autosomes and 2 sex chromosomes

5- Which of the following defines a Karyotype?

- 1. a genome
- 2. representation of a complete set of a cell's polypeptides

3. the complete set of an organism's chromosomes
4. the complete set of an organism's polypeptides

6- 3 Mitotic divisions results in the formation of how many cells?

1. eight cells
2. two cells
3. Six cells
4. Four cells

7- How do cells at the completion of mitosis compare with cells that have replicated their DNA and are just about to begin mitosis?

1. They have the same number of chromosomes and half the amount of DNA.
2. They have half the number of chromosomes and one-fourth the amount of DNA.
3. They have half the number of chromosomes and half the amount of DNA.
4. They have half the amount of cytoplasm and twice the amount of DNA.

8- Look at the cell in the figure. Based on this figure, which of the following statements are true?

1. This cell is diploid.
2. It is impossible to tell whether the cell is haploid or diploid.
3. This cell is haploid.

9-What is the best evidence telling you whether this cell is diploid or haploid?

- a) The cell is diploid because each chromosome consists of two chromatids.
- b) The cell is diploid because it contains two sets of chromosomes.
- c) The cell is haploid because the chromosomes are not found in pairs.

II- Answer the following questions.

- 1- A DNA specimen that contains 30% guanine . Calculate its percentage of thymine.
- 2- Identify the type of bonds that hold the two DNA strands together.
- 3- Name the process that leads to the formation of chromosome of 2 chromatids from a chromosome of 1 chromatid.

III- Taylor Experiment

A- Taylor cultivated young roots on a medium containing radioactive thymidine. Thymidine is a nucleotide entering in the composition of DNA. Radioactive thymidine was then localized in the cells by the autoradiography technique .He added equal amounts of colchicines to the culture .This prevented the separation of the chromosomes in the end of metaphase by inhibiting the formation of mitotic spindle .The chromosomes issued from the successive mitoses thus remained in the same cells .The document below indicates the result of this experiment.

1- Describe the experimental steps of Taylor's experiment

2- Formulate a hypothesis concerning the mode of DNA replication.

B- Xeroderma Pigmentosum type B (XP), is a disease characterized by the appearance of brown spots (patches) on the skin. Ultra violet radiation (UVR) may affect the DNA of cells. It can, for example, causes the formation of a chemical bond between two successive thymine bases (dimer), as shown in document below. The presence of this dimer causes perturbation in the skin cell function and blocks its DNA replication thus causing its death.

Interpret the document.

Pre test validation:

The following validation of the pretest was based on the matching validation with the objectives and the domains.

Question	Domain	Objective
I.1	A	1
I.2	A	2
I.3	A	3
I.4	A	4
I.5	A	5
I.6	B	6
I.7	B	7
I.8	A	8
I.9	B	9
II.1	B	10
II.2	A	11
II.3	A	12
III.1	D	13
III.2	B	14
IV	B	15

Pre test Scoring

Question I (2.25 pts, 0.25 per each question)

1-C, 2-C, 3-D,4-A,5-C,6-A,7-A, 8-A, 9-B

Question II

- 1- Guanine=30%, this means that Cytosine is also 30%.
Cytosine + guanine= 60 %, this implies that Adenine + Thymine=40%, so the percentage of Thymine is 20% since A=T and C=G(0.75 Pts)
- 2- Since these bonds open during replication or transcription, then these are H weak bonds(0.75 pts)
- 3- Replication is the process that leads to the formation of chromosomes of two chromatids from chromosomes of 1 chromatid(0.75 pts)

Question III

- 1- When culturing the roots of *Bellevalia* in the presence of radioactive thymidine and then adding colchicine, 2 chromatids of a chromosome appear radioactive. These roots are then transferred to a non radioactive medium and cultured during a supplementary cycle , one strand of which is radioactive leads to the formation of two different molecules, one is radioactive and the other not. Only one chromatid of the two chromatids of each chromosome is radioactive. (1.5 pts)
- 2- Hypothesis: DNA replication is semi conservative.(0.75 pts)

Question IV (1 pt)

Formation of a chemical bond between two successive thymine bases blocking DNA replication and leading to the disease Xeroderma Pigmentosum when skin is exposed to Ultra violet radiation . This indicates that ultra violet radiation causes the Xeroderma Pigmentosum disease.

Appendix IV: Biology Achievement Post Test

List of Objectives:

- 1- To indicate the product of transcription
- 2- To state the role of T RNA
- 3- To state the function of MRNA
- 4- To list the correct order of events required for protein synthesis
- 5- To indicate the relationship between gene and protein
- 6- To justify the differences in the sequence of amino acids in the protein molecules of different organisms
- 7- To deduce based on DNA sequences closely related organisms.
- 8- To conclude the kind of unknown organism by referring to its gene sequence
- 9- To differentiate between the seeds that produced different flower colors
- 10- To indicate the process that occurs in the ribosome
- 11- To list three main differences between RNA and DNA
- 12- Using the DNA Sequence, the students should be able to build a complimentary RNA strand from the human DNA
- 13- Using the genetic code table, the students should be able to determine what amino acids are assembled to make the insulin protein
- 14- To formulate a hypothesis on how different kinds of mutations might result in normal or diseased individuals
- 15- To interpret the results of the evolution of the quantity of mRNA and the synthesized protein
- 16- To describe the experimental steps in protein synthesis

Post test Format

Please don't write on this question sheet, write your answers on another paper.

I. Multiple choice Questions:

Choose the correct answer, there is only one answer for each question.

1. The product of transcription is

- A. DNA.
- B. protein
- C. mRNA.
- D. a ribosome.

2-. A function of transfer RNA (t RNA) is to

- A. stay in the nucleus and be copied by DNA.
- B. carry amino acids to the growing polypeptide chain.
- C. copy DNA and carry the information to the ribosome.
- D. read the codons and provide the site for protein synthesis.

3- Which of the following best describes the function of mRNA?

- A. It stays in the nucleus and is copied by DNA.
- B. It carries amino acids to the growing polypeptide chain.
- C. It makes up the ribosomes and provides the site for protein synthesis.
- D. It is transcribed from the DNA and carries the information to the ribosome.

4- Use the following events to answer the question.

1. mRNA is formed.
2. DNA segment opens (unzips).
3. mRNA attaches to ribosomes.
4. amino acids form peptide bonds.

The correct order of events required for protein synthesis is

- A. 1, 2, 3, 4, 5.
- B. 2, 1, 3, 4, 5.
- C. 2, 1, 3, 5, 4.
- D. 2, 1, 4, 5, 3.

5- What is the relationship between gene and protein?

- A- The gene codes for protein synthesis.
- B- The gene codes for nucleic acid synthesis.
- C- The gene and the protein both consist of nucleic acids
- D- The gene consists of amino acids, which produce proteins.

6- The differences in the sequence of amino acids in the protein molecules of different organisms are due to:

- A- The sequence of nitrogen bases in the DNA molecule.
- B- The types of nitrogen bases in the DNA molecule.
- C- The proportion of different nitrogen bases in the DNA molecule.
- D- The types of amino acids that the organism consumes.

7-DNA sequences are often used to determine relationships between organisms. DNA sequences that code for a particular gene can vary, though organisms that are closely related will have very similar sequences. This table shows the amino acid sequences of 4 organisms.

Chimpanzee: C C A T A A C A C C T A	Human: C C A T A G C A C C T A
--	--------------------------------

Cricket: C C T A A A G G G A C G

Pig: C C A T G T A A A C G A

Based on these sequences, which two organisms are most closely related?

- A- Human and pig
- B- Human and Chimpanzee
- C- pig and cricket
- D- cricket and chimpanzee

8- An unknown organism is found in the forest and the gene is sequenced as follows:

Unknown: C C A T G G A A G C G A

What kind of an animal do you think this is?

- A-** Human
- B-** chimpanzee
- C-** cricket
- D-** D- Pig

9 - Pea seeds were planted in the garden. The plants that grew from these seeds had flowers of different colors. What are the differences between the seeds that produced the different flower colors?

- A- The seeds include different types of pigments.
- B- The seeds include DNA that consists of different kinds of nucleotides.
- C- The seeds include DNA that consists of different nucleotide sequences.
- D- The seeds include different types of ribosome.

II- Answer the following open ended questions

- (1) Which process occurs in the ribosome?
- (2) List three main differences between RNA and DNA

III- How DNA Controls the Workings of the Cell

a- Below is a partial sequence of DNA bases (shown for only one strand of DNA). This Sequence is from a human. In human this sequence is part of a set of instructions for controlling a bodily function. In this case, the sequence contains the gene to make the protein insulin. Insulin is necessary for the uptake of sugar from the blood. Without insulin, a person cannot absorb sugars the same way others can, and will have a disease called diabetes.

Sequence 1 – Normal Person A Transcribed strand: C C A T A G C A C G T T A C A
A C G T G A A G G T A A

1 Using the DNA sequence, make a complimentary RNA strand from the human DNA.

2. Use the codon table to determine what amino acids are assembled to make the insulin protein in this person A.

b- Gene mutations are a source of change in the insulin gene ,this may sometimes lead to abnormal insulin and consequently to diabetes. Often a person with diabetes has a defective DNA sequence that codes for the making of the insulin protein. Suppose a person B has a mutation in their DNA and the second triplet for the insulin gene reads T A T (instead of the normal TAG). Even though there is mutation, the person with this mutation is not diabetic.

Another mutation in another person C changes the insulin gene to read TC T (instead of the normal T A G) this person with this kind of mutation has diabetes.

Formulate a hypothesis on how both humans B and C have differences in their DNA sequences for insulin from the normal person A , yet B is normal while C is diabetic(0.75 pts)

IV- The quantity of mRNA and synthesized proteins

During an experiment , we add cytoplasmic constituents extracted from bacteria, amino acids are added at time t and 30 minutes later mRNA is added. We measure the quantity of synthesized proteins and the quantity of mRNA present in the medium during the experiment. The results are represented in the following graph.

Dakroub, R. and

Chalhoub, E. (2007)

The evolution of the quantity of mRNA and the synthesized protein as a function of time

a- Interpret the obtained results in the graph

b- The following document represents two moments of the protein synthesis

Dakroub, R. and Chalhoub, E. (2007).

molecule x: DNA ; molecule y: mRNA; molecule z: tRNA

1: amino acid; 2: anticodon; 3: growing polypeptide chain; 4: peptide bond; 5: ribosome

Step 1: Transcription process in the nucleus step

Step 2: Translation process in the cytoplasm

- Describe the experimental steps in the following figure(1.5 pts)

		Nucleotides 2 nd position							
		U	C	A	G				
U	UUU	phenylalanine (Phe)	UCU	serine (Ser)	UAU	tyrosine (Tyr)	UGU	cysteine (Cys)	U
	UUC		UCC		UAC		UGC		C
	UUA	leucine (Leu)	UCA	stop	UAA	stop	UGA	G	
	UUG		UCG		UAG		UGC	A	
C	CUU	leucine (Leu)	CCU	proline (Pro)	CAU	histidine (His)	CGU	arginine (Arg)	U
	CUC		CCC		CAC		CGC		C
	CUA		CCA		CAA	CGA	G		
	CUG		CCG		CAG	CGG	A		
A	AUU	isoleucine (Ile)	ACU	threonine (Thr)	AAU	asparagine (Asn)	AGU	serine (Ser)	U
	AUC		ACC		AAC		AGC		C
	AUA	methionine (Met)	ACA	stop	AAA	lysine (Lys)	AGA	arginine (Arg)	G
	AUG		ACG		AAG		AGG		A
G	GUU	valine (Val)	GCU	alanine (Ala)	GAU	aspartic acid (Asp)	GGU	glycine (Gly)	U
	GUC		GCC		GAC		GGC		C
	GUA		GCA		GAA	GGA	G		
	GUG		GCG		GAG	GGG	A		

A: Adenine

U: Uracil

G: Guanine

C: Cytosine

Genetic code:

Post test validation:

The following validation of the post test was based on the matching validation with the objectives and the Domains.

Question	Domains	Objectives
I.1	A	1
I.2	A	2
I.3	A	3
I.4	A	4
I.5	A	5
I.6	A	6
I.7	B	7
I.8	B	8
I.9	B	9
II.1	A	10
II.2	A	11
III.1 , III.2	B, B	12, 13
III.3	B	14
IV	B	15
IV	D	16

Post Test Scoring

Question I: Multiple choice questions (2.25 pts, 0.25 per each question)

1-C, 2- B, 3- D, 4-B , 5-A, 6-A, 7-B, 8-D,9-C

Question II:

- 1- Translation(0.5 pts)
- 2- The main differences between DNA and RNA are: DNA is double stranded and contains the sugar de oxy ribose while RNA is single stranded and contains the sugar ribose. In addition to that, the nitrogenous bases in DNA are Adenine, Thymine , Cytosine and Guanine while RNA contains same nitrogenous bases , only uracil is present instead of thymine (1pt)

Question III:

Part A (0.75 pts)

- 1- GGUAUCGUGCAAUGUUGCACUCCAUAU(0.25 PTS)
- 2- Gly- Ile- Val- Gln- Cys- Trp- Thr- Ser-Ile(o.5pts)

Part B (0.75 pts)

- 1- Hypothesis: The mutation in B codes for same amino acids leading to same protein while in C it leads to different amino acids and to another protein.

Question IV-(1 pt)

From 0 to 30 minutes, the quantity of mRNA and synthesized protein is null. At 30 minutes, mRNA start increasing to reach its maximum 6 a.u. then decrease to become null during fifty minutes, at the same time protein increases to reach its maximum 3a.u. at 40 min and then stabilizes and remains constant at 3 a.u.. This indicates that the presence of mRNA triggers the synthesis of Proteins.(1 pt.)

B-(1.5 pts.)

The first step in protein synthesis occurs when molecule X which is the DNA is transcribed into molecule Y which is the mRNA, this process takes place in the nucleus.

This process is called transcription. In the second process the mRNA travels to the cytoplasm . A t RNA specific of an amino acid occupies the P site of the ribosome. Then a new t RNA carrying an amino acid is placed facing a second codon on mRNA, a peptide bond is formed between both amino acids, then the ribosome is trans located thus liberating site A and allowing the placement of a third amino acid- t RNA. Termination then occurs when the ribosome reaches a stop codon on mRNA

Appendix V- Modeling Activity Open Ended questionnaire

The questions below give us a feedback on your attitude toward the modeling activity. So please, answer the following questions

1. Have you ever experienced modeling with your teachers in the previous years before? (modeling experience)
2. Did you like this modeling activity in biology classes? If yes, why? If no, why not? (attitude toward modeling)
3. Did this modeling activity help you in getting better understanding in biology? If yes, why? If no, why not? (understanding)
4. Did you find the biology hour more enjoying while modeling? If yes why? If no, why not? (attitude, enjoyment)
5. Do you like to make more modeling activities in biology as projects in your free time at home? (attitude, leisure sub scale)
6. Do you like to have a teacher who makes modeling activities so often? If yes, why? If no, why not? (attitude toward the teacher)
7. How was the relation with your friends while modeling? (Attitude toward learning environment)
8. Did you find yourself a good biology learner in this modeling activity? If yes, why? If no, why not? (Self efficacy)
9. What are the things that you would like to change in this modeling activity? (Students reflection on this modeling activity)

Appendix:VI

Validity of the scales of the attitude and self efficacy questionnaire

Cronbach's Alpha is a coefficient of reliability. It is commonly used as a measure of the internal consistency or reliability of a psychometric test score for a sample of examinees. It was first named alpha by Lee Cronbach in 1951.

This indicator should be greater than 0.7 to consider the internal consistency between items as strong; if the indicator was weak we can also use the correlation test between each item and the average of the items for each factor, if the degree of significance (Sig) was less than the error ratio ($\alpha = 5\%$)→ we consider the correlation valid and we don't delete any item.

Table 1: validity of attitude and self efficacy scale

	Cronbach's Alpha	
	Pre	Post
Enjoyment	0.657	0.675
Leisure	0.712	0.705
Attitude toward Teacher	0.698	0.709
Attitude toward the learning environment	0.745	0.731
Attitude	0.709	0.721
Self efficacy	0.825	0.823

Appendix VII: Modeling Activities

Teaching students how to model. Students in the experimental group who used modeling activities were taught how to construct a model using the following procedure.

Session I (1 hour): The teacher announced to the students in the experimental group that she will teach them how to use modeling activities as an application technique. The teacher told the students that she planned to teach this technique to help them in their studies. Then the teacher drew the students attention that they needed to master constructing the models in order to get the optimum results. The teacher helped the students to model DNA building, then she encouraged them to construct their own models. Once the students finish the modeling activity, the teacher discussed with them the criteria and conditions for a good modeling activity and its limitation.

Session II (2 hours): During the second session, the researcher gave the teacher materials that the students will use to propose building replication.

Session III (3 hours): Also the research covered in the experimental group section the same material covered in the control group section. Both sections had a lecture on supercoiling, but only the experimental group had an extra modeling activity for DNA supercoiling.

Session IV (4 hours): The concept in the chapter taught for both sections (control and experimental) during this period was protein synthesis. Then only students in the experimental groups used these concepts to construct a model. The students were asked to revise the models by comparing to their friends and to think of its limitation.

Teachers gradually minimized the guidance to their students in building the models.

Session V(2 hours):The teacher in the control and experimental groups explained the different kinds of mutation to their students while at the end of this session only experimental group students were asked to propose a model for mutation by using the same materials they had in building DNA.

Topic 1: Double Helix Activity (www.LessonPlanInc.com)

Summary: Students will build a classroom size model of the double helix using paper

Standards:

Students know the general structures and functions of DNA. Students know how to apply base pairing rules.

Objectives:

Students should be able to conclude that the double helix is made of many nucleotides

Students should be able to deduce that the strands of the double helix are complementary based upon the 5' prime and 3'prime ends

Students should be able to differentiate between the number of H bonds between different nitrogeneous bases.

Time: 1 hour

Materials: Construction paper- 7 colors

Tape

Scissors

Tooth picks or cotton swabs (optional)

Procedure:

The teacher remind the students of the different parts of a nucleotide, base pairing rules, 5 prime and 3 prime ends. Then the students work as group of two and they arrange their supplies. Two of the strips, 1 paper of circles, pentagons and each base is a good amount of supplies to start with.

Before the students start to cut out each part from the construction paper, the teacher explain how to assemble the helix and give information on the different materials. The

long strip(it is the backbone), the small circle(the phosphate group) ,the pentagon(the sugar) ,the tape or tooth pick or cotton swab (it is the H bond)and the different bases papers.

First the students start to cut the parts from the construction paper and build a nucleotide. Second the students take the long strip and tape the small circle (the phosphate group) on top of the strip. Third to the upper right of the circle, they tape a pentagon (the sugar) onto the side of the strip. Fourth they tape a base to the right of the sugar. The teachers should make sure that the students are not trying to take a short cut and they should build it one nucleotide at a time and not tape several phosphates on the strip then several sugars and so forth.

Once the student has done one nucleotide, the student continues to make more of the same helix. The student should fit about 5-6 phosphates per backbone strip.

The student then takes another strip and does the exact opposite of the first strip. The student then needs to select the correct complimentary base to fit with the base at the bottom of the first strip making sure that the sugar is pointing in the opposite direction.

Students then attach the two bases together. They should draw with a marker over the tape used to connect the phosphate sugar for the phosphodiester bond. Students should use a different color marker to color over the tape holding together the two complimentary nitrogen bases demonstrating the hydrogen bonds.

The researcher suggested a small modification on the activity by using short cut tooth picks and sticking it inside the tape to represent only H bonding: 2 picks to represent 2 H bonds in the binding between adenine and thymine and 3 picks to represent 3 H bonds in the binding between cytosine and Guanine

Then the student continued to build the second helix one nucleotide at a time.

Once completed the students then work on making the double helix longer by sticking their DNA helixes together. The longer is the double helix the easier it is for super coiling.

Topic 2: Modeling Replication

Summary: Students should be able to devise a modeling activity on how DNA replicates (Approach: Inquiry based modeling Instruction).

Standards: Students know that Replication is the synthesis of “daughter” nucleic acid molecules that are identical to the parental nucleic acids.

Students know that during DNA replication, the preexisting, or “parent” strands become separated, each acting as the template for biosynthesis of a complementary “daughter” strand.

Objectives: Students should be able to deduce that DNA Replication is semiconservative

Time: 1 hour

Materials: Construction paper- 8 colors

Tape

Scissors

Tooth picks or cotton swabs (optional)

Cardboard model of DNA polymerase

Procedure:

- The teacher should ask the students to come up with a way to replicate their DNA
- The teacher should also give them the instruction that a new material should be used in addition to the materials used before which was different color strip
- The teacher should give them the rules that only the hydrogen bonds could be broken and not the phosphodiester bonds.
- The teacher should have the students revise their models after comparing to their friends and find its limitation in comparing to real DNA replication.

Topic 3: DNA and Histone Model (<http://Teach.Genetics.utah.edu>)

Summary: Students will build an accessible and inaccessible DNA Histone Model.

Objectives:- Students should be able to model DNA depicting how histone, acetyl and methyl molecules control access to DNA and affect gene expression.

- students should be able to portray the dynamic nature of the genome's physical structure by having them manipulate their models in response to "gene on" or "gene off" signals

Time: 1 hour

Materials

- Copies of molecule cut outs and student directions
- Scissors
- Tape
- Paperclips

Standards:

- Students should know that DNA is coiled around histones.
- Students should know that Nucleosome is a single histone spool with its associated DNA.

- Students should know that tightly coiled DNA is inaccessible to gene reading machinery.
- Students should know that methyl and acetyl control gene expression by controlling access to DNA.

- Students should know that methyl molecules bind to DNA and block access to genes when DNA is wound
- Students should know that Methyl attaches to DNA between a Cytosine (C) and Guanine (G) in locations known as CpG islands

- Students should know that acetyl molecules bind to histones and improve access to genes causing DNA to be wound more loosely around histones.

Procedure:

MAKING DNA INACCESSIBLE

In a group of 2 the students should sort their materials(Scissors, Invisible tape, 8 standard size paperclips)

The students should choose a region of the DNA ribbon to represent a gene, they should also color it with a highlighter before attaching the DNA ribbon to their histone spools and winding it to visually keep track of the gene as they carry

out the activity.To assemble the DNA ribbon and histone spools. Students should gather 8 paperclips and start attaching one end of the DNA ribbon to a histone by folding one of the histone tails over the DNA ribbon to help hold it in place and securing it with a paperclip. Then attaching the remaining histones along the DNA ribbon at a distance of 2 strips of DNA apart (roughly 16 cm). So in their modeling the students should follow the following directions

Hold the first histone upright in one hand. Wind the DNA ribbon clockwise around it roughly two times or until you bump in to the next histone. Fold all of the histone tails over the DNA ribbon to help hold it in to place and secure with a paperclip.

Trying not to fold or bend the DNA ribbon, wind it around the next histone. Again, fold the histone tails around the DNA ribbon and secure with a paperclip. Repeat until all of the DNA ribbon has been wound. The histones should begin to stack on top of one another as you wind.

Use tape to attach the methyl molecule cut outs to exposed areas of your DNA ribbon. Trying to attach and move the Gene Reading Machinery cut-out to any length of the DNA ribbon that is not spooled around a histone or covered by methyl. The machinery couldn't read any significant stretch of DNA making it an inactive gene.

Remove the methyl molecules and de-construct your model if moving to the next step

2: MAKING DNA ACCESSIBLE

The students should follow the following instructions:

Attach two acetyl molecules to each histone at different locations. To attach the molecules, pull a histone tail through the cut in the center of the acetyl molecules. Now your histones are “acetylated”.

Attach an acetylated histone to one end of your DNA ribbon, secure it with a paperclip. Attach the remaining acetylated histones along the length of the DNA ribbon at distances of 2 DNA strips apart (roughly 16 cm).

Hold the first histone upright in one hand. Wind the DNA ribbon clockwise around it two times or until the first histone touches the next one. Be sure that no part of the neighboring histones, including the acetyl molecules are touching. If they are, unwind the DNA ribbon a little bit to put some space between the histones. Secure the DNA ribbon with a paperclip. Wind the DNA ribbon clockwise around the next histone.

Again, be sure that no part of neighboring histones are touching then secure the DNA ribbon with a paperclip. Repeat until the DNA ribbon has been wound around all the histones. The histones and DNA should be spooled loosely, with some space between histones. Try to attach and move the Gene Reading Machinery cutout to any length of the DNA ribbon that is not spooled around a histone. These reading molecules can now attach and move down a length of accesible DNA, “reading” the DNA code as they go along.

Topic 4: Transcription(First step in Protein synthesis)

(www.LessonPlanInc.com)

Summary :Students will model transcription of the DNA into mRNA copy .

Goals and Objectives :Students will be able to explain the complimentary base pairing between DNA and mRNA.

Students will be able to explain the structure of mRNA

Students will be able to differentiate between the m RNA and DNA.

Standards: Students know that Transcription is the enzymatic process, whereby the genetic information contained in one strand of DNA is used to specify a complementary sequence of bases in a mRNA chain.

Students know the structure of RNA

Students know that in RNA the sugar is Ribose instead of Deoxy ribose.

Students know how to apply transcription of information from DNA into mRNA.

Materials :Construction paper- 8 colors (extra different color for ribose sugar), tape, scissors, tooth picks or cotton swabs(optional), cardboard model of RNA polymerase

Time: 1 hour

Procedure : The teacher should introduce to the students that RNA binds in a complimentary way to one strand of DNA after the unwinding of DNA strands.

The teacher should also state the role of RNA polymerase.

Pre modeling, the teacher should photocopy pages with different colors as in the DNA activity and give them instructions on these materials clarifying that the de oxyribose paper must have different color from the ribose paper .

To save time, the students could use the DNA built in the previous activity and cut it by a scissor at the hydrogen bonds. Students start building the complementary RNA. While modeling mRNA synthesis, the students should bind the Adenine with the Uracil .In the RNA backbone, the students should follow same steps while modeling the DNA while the sugar to be added should be ribose (different color pentagon paper).

The students should differentiate between the RNA and DNA model. The students should also compare the mRNA model to each of the DNA strands

Topic 5: Polypeptide Activity

(Translation: Second step of Protein synthesis.)

Summary: Students will learn how proteins are built from the DNA code. Students will learn how mRNA, ribosomes, tRNA and peptide bonds are used in the formation of a polypeptide

Goals and Objectives: Students should be able to model the process of translation in protein synthesis.

Standards: Students know that translation is the process in which the genetic information present in a mRNA molecule specifies the sequence of amino acids during protein synthesis in the ribosome.

Students know that translation requires tRNA which carries an amino acid to a specific codon in mRNA.

Students know that tRNA “translates” the nucleotide sequence of a mRNA into the amino acids sequence of a polypeptide.

Students know that covalent bonds chemically link amino acids together to form a polypeptide chain or link other kinds of chemical subunits together to form the chemical structures of many other components of the protein synthesis process, but are not involved directly in the flow of genetic information.

Students know the general pathway by which ribosomes synthesize proteins using tRNA to translate genetic information in mRNA.

Students know how to apply the genetic coding rules to predict the sequence of amino acids from a sequence of codons in RNA.

Time duration: 1 hour

Materials: Paper model of a cell just containing a nucleus and a cytoplasm

DNA molecules

Two mRNA pieces of paper

Many Photocopied pages of the amino acids, cut each separated and sorted

Beverage coasters (optional, the researcher made a small modification on the activity by adding this material).

T RNAs paper models

Ribosomes Cardboard model

Scissors

Two different color tapes

Procedure: On the desk, have the students tape the DNA molecules inside the nucleus, the students should also tape the cytoplasm labels on the second half of the table and place the associated amino acids in an easy accessible tray or container to help with organization and prevent mixing of amino acids.(optional: the students could glue each amino acid inside a beverage coaster).

Students should also tape the ribosome paper models on each students desk inside the cytoplasm.

Students should go to the nucleus with the mRNA paper and transcribe the DNA code from the nucleus to the mRNA molecule.(to save time: students could use the mRNA model attained from transcription in the modeling hour before).

Students should write down the codons into the spaces provided-three letters per underline space.

Students should move this mRNA model from the nucleus into the ribosome found in the cytoplasm.

Students should write the anti codon on the bottom of the tRNA model

The student should look up the amino acid that the t RNA is supposed to pick from the cytoplasm and bring it back to the ribosome and place the t RNA anti codon at the p site

The students should look up the next amino acid and write the anti codon onto a new t RNA molecule and then get the next amino acid and bring it back to the A site in the ribosome. The T RNA anti codon should match with the corresponding codon at the A site.

Then the students should tape the first amino acid to the next one. The tape should be of different color to represent a peptide bond. The student should move the tRNA to the left and the two amino acids are left at the p site. The amino acids should be vertical with the first amino acid being farther from the p site. The chain of amino acids should be perpendicular to the p site and the mRNA

This process should be repeated until a stop codon is reached. The students should bring the stop codon and release the poly peptide chain. Students should not tape the stop codon to the polypeptide.

Going farther into Inquiry based modeling activity: The teachers should ask the students to propose another modeling activity for translation by using materials from their own.

Topic 6: Modeling Mutations

Summary: Students will build many models of mutated DNA.

Standards: Students know that any modification in the nucleotide sequence of a gene leads to mutation.

Students know that there are different types of mutations: Insertion , deletion and substitution.

Students know that some mutations are silent while others lead to a modified protein.

Objectives: The students should be able to model different kinds of DNA mutations

Time: 1 hour

Materials: Construction paper- 7 colors

Tape

Scissors

Tooth picks or cotton swabs (optional)

Procedure:

- The teacher should ask the students to come up with a way to model different types of DNA mutations.
- Students should design using the selected materials a modeling activity that allows them to see different kinds of DNA mutations.
- The teacher should remind them that this mutation has its consequences on the amino acid sequence.
- Students should write the steps on their copy books.
- Students should share and discuss the selected materials and suggested procedure with their classmates.
- Students should agree on the materials and the procedure and conduct the modeling activity.

- The teacher should have the students revise their models after comparing to their friends and find its limitation.

- Appendix VIII: Achievement, Attitude and Self Efficacy Subscales in Different Learning Style, Opposite Gender, and Different Kind of School Control Group Students:
- Achievement Test Subscales in Different Learning Style Control Group Students:
- Table 1 presents control students% of variation in the pre tests and post tests and its subscales in the beginning and at the end of the study by referring to learning style.

Table1 : achievement test subscales in different learning style control students:

% of variation	NK		K	
	% of variation	Sig	% of variation	Sig
Acquired Knowledge	-11.28%	0.008	-0.49%	0.926
Scientific Reasoning	155.80%	0.000	107.91%	0.000
Communication	-21.24%	0.026	-26.01%	0.001
Total	11.79%	0.001	14.35%	0.002

As to control group, the NK group showed a significant increase in the total marks (% of var:11.79% , sig:0.001<0.05) more precisely scientific reasoning showed a significant increase(% of var:155.8%, sig:0.000<0.05) while they showed a significant decrease in acquired knowledge and communication domain(respectively,% of var:-11.28%, sig:0.008<0.05; ,% of var:-21.24% ,sig:0.026<0.05). Similarly the control K group showed significant increase in the total test marks(% of var:14.35%,sig:0.002<0.05)more precisely the increase was due to significant increase in scientific reasoning.(% of var:107.91%, sig:0.000<0.05).Students marks in both A and D domains decreased ,the decrease in acquired knowledge was not sig(% of var:-0.49%, sig:0.926>0.05) while they showed a significant decrease in the D domain(% of var:-26.01%,sig:0.001<0.05).

- Achievement Test Subscales in Opposite Gender Control Group Students:
Table 2 presents control students% of variation in the pre tests and post tests and its subscales in the beginning and at the end of the study by referring to gender.

Table 2: achievement test subscales in opposite gender control students:

% of variation	Male		Female	
	% of variation	Sig	% of variation	Sig
Acquired Knowledge	-19.63%	0.000	7.00%	0.084
Scientific Reasoning	122.92%	0.000	144.44%	0.000
Communication	-14.63%	0.148	-28.11%	0.000
Total	5.69%	0.117	20.91%	0.000

In the control male group there was significant decrease in acquired knowledge (% of var:-19.63% ,sig 0.000<0.05) and sig increase in scientific reasoning(% of variation:122.92%,sig:0.000<0.05). There was decrease in communication skills but this decrease was not significant (-14.63%,sig:0.148>0.05) .There was no significant increase in the overall test marks while in the female group, there was significant increase in scientific reasoning(% of variation:144.44% sig:0.000<0.05), female group showed an increase in acquired knowledge but this increase was not significant(% of var:7.00%, sig:0.084>0.05). Girls also showed significant increase in their total test marks(% of var:20.91%, sig:0.000 <0.05). On the other hand, girls showed significant decrease in communication domain(% of var:-28.11%, sig:0.000<0.05).

- Achievement Test Subscales in Different Kind of School Control Group Students: Table 3 presents control students% of variation in the pre tests and post tests and its subscales in the beginning and at the end of the study by referring to kind of school.

Table 3: achievement test subscales in different kind of school control students:

% of variation	Mixed		Boys		Girls	
	% of var	Sig	% of var	Sig	% of var	Sig
Acquired Knowledge	7.11%	0.201	-23.70%	0.000	8.51%	0.111
Scientific Reasoning	84.54%	0.000	116.80%	0.000	237.88%	0.000
Communication	27.03%	0.004	-8.59%	0.488	-30.99%	0.002
Total	15.44%	0.001	2.86%	0.465	26.26%	0.000

As to control group, the mixed school showed a significant increase in the total marks (% of var:15.44% ,sig:0.001<0.05).This was due to significant increase in scientific reasoning(% of var:84.54%,sig 0.000<0.05). Their communication skills decrease significantly(-27.03%, sig:0.004<0.05).Students showed increase in A domain but this increase was not significant. In the boys school, no sig. increase in total test marks.

Boys show a significant increase in scientific reasoning(%of var:116.80%, sig:0.000<0.05) while acquired knowledge showed a significant decrease(% of var:-23.70%, sig0.000<0.05).As to girls alone school, the total test marks showed a significant increase(% of var.:26.26%, sig:o.000<0.05),this was due to their sig increase in scientific reasoning(% of var: 237.88%,sig0.000<0.05). On the other hand, students showed a significant decrease in communication domain (%of var:-30.99%, sig:0.002<0.05)

Attitude and Self efficacy Subscales in different Learning Style Control Group

Students:

- Table 4 presents control students% of variation in the attitude and self efficacy and its subscales in the beginning and at the end of the study by referring to learning style.

Table 4: K and NK control students attitude and self efficacy subscales (pre and post test)

% of variation		NK		K	
	% of variation	Sig	% of variation	Sig	
Enjoyment	1.15%	0.786	-4.27%	0.182	
Leisure	1.55%	0.547	-6.01%	0.113	
Attitude toward Teacher	2.47%	0.492	-0.91%	0.811	
Attitude toward the learning environment	3.65%	0.292	4.00%	0.328	
Attitude	2.21%	0.337	-2.14%	0.318	
Self efficacy	4.42%	0.131	-6.28%	0.172	

As to control group, both K and NK didn't show any significant variation in any of attitude and self efficacy sub scales (sig > 0.05).

- Attitude and Self Efficacy Subscales in Opposite Gender Control Group Students: Table 5 presents control students% of variation in the attitude and self efficacy and its subscales in the beginning and at the end of the study by referring to gender.

Table 5: Opposite gender control students attitude and self efficacy subscales(pre and post test)

% of variation		Male		Female	
	% of variation	Sig	% of variation	Sig	
Enjoyment	-6.32%	0.050	2.36%	0.520	
Leisure	-8.07%	0.005	3.70%	0.228	
Attitude toward Teacher	1.42%	0.810	1.27%	0.685	
Attitude toward the learning environment	7.96%	0.037	1.54%	0.676	
Attitude	-2.11%	0.358	2.26%	0.268	
Self efficacy	-1.95%	0.627	1.71%	0.559	

As to the control female group, there was no significant variation in any of these sub scales after they were post tested(sig > 0.05), while the control male group showed a significant increase in leisure(% of variation:-8.07% , sig:0.005<0.05) and a significant decrease in the attitude toward learning environment(% of var:7.96%, sig:0.037<0.05) while the other sub scales didn't show any significant variation.

Attitude and Self efficacy Subscales in Different Kind of School Control Group Students:

- Table 6 presents control students% of variation in the attitude and self efficacy and its subscales in the beginning and at the end of the study by referring to school type.
- Table 6: Different kind of school control students attitude and self efficacy subscales(pre and post test)

% of variation	Mixed		Boys		Girls	
	% of var	Sig	% of var	Sig	% of var	Sig
Enjoyment	-3.45%	0.390	-5.73%	0.154	3.08%	0.498
Leisure	-3.53%	0.294	-7.55%	0.029	5.44%	0.153
Attitude toward Teacher	-9.85%	0.048	3.86%	0.550	7.55%	0.072
Attitude toward the learning environment	0.47%	0.928	8.22%	0.044	3.61%	0.446
Attitude	-4.75%	0.042	-1.12%	0.678	5.24%	0.049
Self efficacy	-	0.077	4.20%	0.303	3.28%	0.264

As to control group, the mixed school students showed a significant increase in the attitude toward the teacher (% of variation: -9.85% with sig 0.048 <0.05). In addition to that, their total attitude increased significantly (% of var: - 4.75% with sig:0.042 <0.05) while the boys school students showed a significant increase in leisure (-7.55% with

sig:0.029<0.05) while their attitude toward the learning environment showed a significant decrease with % of var:8.22% and sig 0.044 <0.05. In the girls school, the girls showed a significant decrease in the over all attitude (% of var:5.24%,sig:0.049<0.05).